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Deliverable 23.2

FUTURE NEEDS IN STATISTICS

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Abstract

The InGRID workpackage 23 on high-performance statistical quality management focuses on important developments and future needs of statistical indicators in the social sciences. That requires the construction of a shared knowledge on theories and best practices to evaluate the quality and appropriateness of indicators through an empirical analysis. This covers methodological advances as well as practical considerations of indicators for poverty, social exclusion, and related fields. Additionally to methodological advances, a simulation lab is developed to foster open and reproducible research for future developments in the InGRID research area using SILC related data. This second deliverable covers especially future needs in three areas:

- Missing values, non-probability samples, and big data
- Multi-dimensional indicators
- Regional indicators and advances in small area applications

The major aim of this deliverable aims to identify research gaps in these areas and, hence, to indicate ways for future research in the InGRID research area.

Ralf Münnich, Co-ordinator of WP23

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1 Empirical Likelihood Approach for Unit Non-Response

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Survey data is often clustered; that is, the target population is split into small groups of units, called clusters. Units are selected within each clusters sampled. This is a widely used technique called multi-stage sampling. Suppose we wish to make inference about a model parameter which can be expressed as the unique solution to a set of estimating equations. We consider a design-based inference; that is, the parameter of interest is a population parameter and the sampling distribution is specified by the sampling design. Although, model-based techniques are widely used, empirical likelihood non-parametric design-based approaches are mostly neglected. Empirical likelihood has been mostly developed under the assumption of independent and identically distributed observations. This assumption is violated under multi-stage sampling. OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2016a) proposed an empirical likelihood design-based approach for multiple parameters, under full-response. We show how this approach can be extended for non-response. The proposed inference approach takes into account of the design, the response mechanism, the randomness of the estimated response propensities and the population level information. This confidence interval does not rely directly on the normality of the point estimator and does not require variance estimation, linearisation, re-sampling and estimation of a design effect.

1.1 Introduction

Consider a finite population U containing \mathcal{N} units labelled $\{1, \dots, \mathcal{N}\}$. Let \mathbf{v}_i be a vector of variables \mathbf{v} associated with a unit $i \in U$. This vector may contain variables of interest and auxiliary variables. We consider that the set \mathbf{v} of variables is split into two type of variables: \mathbf{y} and $\boldsymbol{\xi}$; that is, $\mathbf{v}_i = (\mathbf{y}_i^\top, \boldsymbol{\xi}_i^\top)^\top$. The variables \mathbf{y} are subject to missingness; that is, if the unit i is missing, the whole vector \mathbf{y}_i is missing. The variables $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ are not subject to missingness. The variables $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ denotes had-hoc variables that explains the missingness of some of the values of \mathbf{y} . For example, the $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ may contain some geographical variables,

variable specifying the type of accommodation or variable available in a population register or census.

We consider a non-parametric approach; that is, consider a population parameter β_0 is the solution of p estimating equations (GODAMBE and THOMPSON, 1986),

$$\mathbf{G}(\beta) := \sum_{i \in U} \mathbf{g}_i(\beta) = \mathbf{0}_p,$$

with $\mathbf{g}_i(\beta) = \mathbf{g}(\beta, \mathbf{v}_i)$ where $\mathbf{g}(\beta, \mathbf{v}_i)$ is a p -vector function of β and \mathbf{v}_i . Here, $\mathbf{0}_p$ denotes the p -vector of zeros. We adopt a design-based approach (NEYMAN, 1938); where β_0 and the values of the variables \mathbf{v}_i are fixed constants. The sampling distribution is specified by the random selection of the sample (i.e. the sampling design) and by the response mechanism.

Example 1.1.1. The population parameter β_0 can be a vector of population regression coefficient of a generalised linear regression model or a M-quantile model (e.g. BINDER and PATAK, 1994, CHEN and VAN KEILEGOM, 2009). For example, for a logistic regression model, the vector $\mathbf{g}_i(\beta)$ is given by

$$\mathbf{g}_i(\beta) = \mathbf{x}_i y_i - \mathbf{x}_i \exp(\mathbf{x}_i^\top \beta) \{1 + \exp(\mathbf{x}_i^\top \beta)\}^{-1},$$

where $\mathbf{v}_i = (y_i, \mathbf{x}_i^\top, \dots)^\top$ and y_i is the value of a dichotomous variable.

In this paper, the logistic model is used as an example, although this paper's approach is not limited to this model. Other examples can be found in CHEN and VAN KEILEGOM (2009) and OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2016b).

Many surveys use known population-level information is often know; that is, we often know a set of parameters from large external censuses or surveys, such as means, counts or proportions. These known population-level parameters are given by the q -vector φ_0 . We assume the φ_0 is a non-random (deterministic) vector, which is the solution to q estimating equations,

$$\sum_{i \in U} \mathbf{f}(\varphi, \mathbf{y}_i) = \mathbf{0}_q,$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\varphi, \mathbf{y}_i)$ is a q -vector function of φ and \mathbf{y}_i . In what follows, we shall replace $\mathbf{f}(\varphi_0, \mathbf{y}_i)$ by \mathbf{f}_i , because φ_0 is treated as a deterministic constants.

1.2 Response mechanism

We consider a reverse approach (FAY, 1991, SHAO and STEEL, 1999); that is, the response mechanism is the first phase and the second phase is the selection of a multi-stage sample described in section 1.3. Figure 1.1 illustrate the random selection of units. The first phase is the response mechanism, which split the population into respondents and non-respondents. The second phase is the selection of a sample.

Figure 1.1: Response mechanism and sample.

The first phase is therefore the response mechanism which split the population into respondents and non-respondents. Let ρ_i be the ‘response indicator’; that is, $\rho_i = 1$ if \mathbf{y}_i is not-missing and $\rho_i = 0$ if \mathbf{y}_i is missing, where $i \in U$. We suppose that the ρ_i are independent random variables. We assume that the distribution of ρ_i is specified by a logistic ‘missing at random’ response mechanism; that is, ρ_i follows independent Bernoulli($\mathbb{E}_r(\rho_i)$) distribution, for $i \in U$, where $\mathbb{E}_r(\cdot)$ denotes the expectation with respect to the response mechanism, given by

$$\mathbb{E}_r(\rho_i) = p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_0),$$

with

$$p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) := \exp(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\lambda}) \{1 + \exp(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\lambda})\}^{-1}. \quad (1.1)$$

and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_0$ is the *response parameter* and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ are the values of the variables that does not contain missing values.

If we wish to use re-weighting classes, we simply define $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ as the vector of dummy variables

specifying the classes. In this case, λ_0 is the vector of response propensities for each classes.

1.3 Multi-stage sampling design

The second phase is the random selection of a *stratified multi-stage unequal probability with-replacement sample*, which is commonly used for social surveys.

1.3.1 First stage

Suppose that the population U is divided into M non-overlapping subsets called *Primary Sampling Units* (PSU), denoted \tilde{U}_k , where $k \in \tilde{U} = \{1, \dots, M\}$; that is, $\cup_{k=1}^M \tilde{U}_k = U$ and \tilde{U} denotes the population of M . We assume that \tilde{U} is divided into H non-overlapping strata, $\tilde{U}_1, \dots, \tilde{U}_H$, such that $\cup_{h=1}^H \tilde{U}_h = \tilde{U}$. We assume that a sample \tilde{S}_h of n_h PSUs is selected independently with-replacement within \tilde{U}_h , with probabilities $p_k = \pi_k/n_h$, where $\sum_{k \in \tilde{U}_h} \pi_k = n_h$. The overall sample of PSU's is denoted $\tilde{S} = \cup_{h=1}^H \tilde{S}_h$ and contains $m = \sum_{h=1}^H n_h$ PSUS labels.

We assume that the sampling fraction m/M is negligible, which is a common feature of social surveys. In this case, sampling with and without replacement are approximately equivalent (HÁJEK, 1981, p.112).

1.3.2 Second stage

Within each PSU \tilde{U}_k sampled, we select a without replacement sample S_k of ν_k units. Let $\pi_{i|k}$ denotes the inclusion probability of a unit i within \tilde{U}_k . Any sampling designs can be used to select the samples S_k . The final sample $S = \cup_{k \in \tilde{S}} S_k$ contains $\nu = \sum_{k \in \tilde{S}} \nu_k$ units. The vectors \mathbf{y}_i are observed for all $i \in S$ with $\rho_i = 1$, and \mathbf{y}_i are missing if $\rho_i = 0$.

1.4 Empirical likelihood approach

We have two unknown parameters: β_0 the unknown parameter of interest, and λ_0 the parameter describing the response mechanism. Let $\psi_0 = (\beta_0^\top, \lambda_0^\top)^\top$ denotes the overall parameter. Let $\psi = (\beta^\top, \lambda^\top)^\top$, for any vectors β and λ in their respective parameter space.

1.4.1 Empirical likelihood function

The ‘*empirical likelihood function*’ is defined by

$$\ell(\boldsymbol{\psi}) := \max \left\{ \sum_{k \in \tilde{S}} \log m_k : m_k > 0, \sum_{k \in \tilde{S}} m_k \widehat{\mathbf{c}}_k^*(\boldsymbol{\psi}) = \mathbf{C}^* \right\}, \quad (1.2)$$

where

$$\widehat{\mathbf{c}}_k^*(\boldsymbol{\psi}) := \{ \widehat{\mathbf{a}}_k(\boldsymbol{\psi})^\top, \widehat{\mathbf{c}}_k^\top \}^\top, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{c}}_k := (\mathbf{z}_k^\top, \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_{0k}^\top)^\top, \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^* := (\mathbf{0}_{t+p}^\top, \mathbf{C}^\top)^\top, \quad \mathbf{C} := (\mathbf{n}_H^\top, \mathbf{0}_q^\top)^\top, \quad (1.4)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{a}}_k(\boldsymbol{\psi}) := \sum_{i \in S_k} \pi_{i|k}^{-1} \mathbf{a}_i(\boldsymbol{\psi}), \quad (1.5)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_{0k} := \sum_{i \in S_k} \pi_{i|k}^{-1} \rho_i p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})^{-1} \mathbf{f}_i, \quad (1.6)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_i(\boldsymbol{\psi}) := [\boldsymbol{\xi}_i^\top \{ \rho_i - p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) \}, \rho_i p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})^{-1} \mathbf{g}_i(\boldsymbol{\beta})^\top]^\top, \quad (1.7)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_k := (z_{k1}, \dots, z_{kh}, \dots, z_{kH})^\top,$$

$$\mathbf{n}_H := (n_1, \dots, n_H)^\top$$

and $t = \dim\{\boldsymbol{\xi}\}$ is the dimension of the vector $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$. Here, $z_{kh} = \pi_k$ for $k \in U_h$ and $z_{kh} = 0$ otherwise. The \mathbf{z}_k are the stratification variables. Note that it is necessary to multiply $\mathbf{g}_i(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ and \mathbf{f}_i by $\rho_i p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})^{-1}$ in equation (1.7) and equation (1.6), because $\mathbf{g}_i(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ and \mathbf{f}_i are missing, when $\rho_i = 0$. The value of $\ell(\boldsymbol{\psi})$ for a given $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ can be computed using Lagrangian multipliers. The function $\ell(\boldsymbol{\psi})$ is treated as a likelihood.

1.4.2 Point estimation

The ‘*maximum empirical likelihood estimator*’ is defined as the vector $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}$ that maximises the function $\ell(\boldsymbol{\psi})$ defined by equation (1.2). It can be shown that $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}$ is also the solution to

$$\sum_{k \in \tilde{S}} \widehat{m}_k \widehat{\mathbf{a}}_k(\boldsymbol{\psi}) = \mathbf{0}_{t+p}, \quad (1.8)$$

where

$$\widehat{m}_k = (\pi_k + \boldsymbol{\eta}^\top \widehat{\mathbf{c}}_k)^{-1} \quad (1.9)$$

(e.g. BERGER and DE LA RIVA TORRES, 2016). Here, the vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ is such that the constraints $m_k > 0$ and $\sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}} m_k \hat{\mathbf{c}}_k = \mathbf{C}$ holds, where $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_k$ and \mathbf{C} are respectively defined by equation (1.3) and equation (1.4).

By using equation (1.7) and equation (1.5), we have that equation (1.8) reduces to

$$\sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} \rho_i p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})^{-1} w_{i|k} \mathbf{f}_i = \mathbf{0}_q, \quad (1.10)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} \rho_i p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})^{-1} w_{i|k} \mathbf{g}_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbf{0}_p, \quad (1.11)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} w_{i|k} \boldsymbol{\xi}_i \{\rho_i - p_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda})\} = \mathbf{0}_r, \quad (1.12)$$

where $w_{i|k} = \hat{m}_k \pi_{i|k}^{-1}$. The quantities \hat{m}_k and $w_{i|k}$ are respectively the PSU level survey weights and the unit-level weight. The weights $w_{i|k}$ are calibrated because of equation (1.10). Equation (1.10) takes into account of the population-level information. The parameter $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$ is estimated from the equation (1.11). Note that equation (1.11) equation (1.10) are sum over the non-missing unit i , such that $\rho_i = 1$.

The non-response parameter $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_0$ is estimated from equation (1.12), which is the estimating equation of a logistic model. For example, if we use re-weighting classes, the $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ are the vectors of dummy variables specifying the classes. In this case, the estimator of $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_0$ is the observed (weighted) response rates (or response propensities) within each classes.

1.4.3 Statistical tests and confidence intervals

Consider that the parameter of interest $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ is a sub-vector of $\boldsymbol{\psi}_0$. The remaining parameters are nuisance parameters denoted $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$. The respective maximum empirical likelihood estimators are denoted $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}$; that is, $(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^\top, \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^\top)^\top = \hat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}$. In practice, the non-response parameter $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_0$ is often a nuisance parameter, which is part of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$. The function $\ell(\boldsymbol{\psi}_0)$ is a function of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$; that is, let $\ell(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) := \ell(\boldsymbol{\psi})$, where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ denote vectors in the parameter space of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$.

The *profile empirical likelihood ratio statistic* is defined by the following function of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

$$r(\boldsymbol{\theta}) := 2\{\ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}) - \max_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \ell(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\mu})\} \quad (1.13)$$

It can be shown that $\ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}) = \sum_{k \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}} \log(\hat{m}_k)$, with \hat{m}_k defined by expression equation (1.9).

OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2016a) proposed an algorithm to compute $\max_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \ell(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\mu})$.

Under some regularity conditions, we have that $r(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is pivotal; that is,

$$r(\boldsymbol{\theta}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_{df=p}^2, \quad (1.14)$$

where p is the number of estimating equations that define $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$. The result equation (1.14) can be used to test hypotheses on $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ and to derive confidence intervals.

Consider the following test hypotheses

$$\begin{cases} H_0 : \boldsymbol{\theta}_0 = \boldsymbol{\theta}_0^* \\ H_1 : \boldsymbol{\theta}_0 \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}_0^* \end{cases}$$

The *p-value* is

$$\text{p-value} = \int_{\widehat{r}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_0^*)}^{\infty} f(p, x) dx,$$

where $f(p, x)$ is the density of a χ^2 -distribution with p degrees of freedom. The value of this integral can be obtained from any statistical table of χ^2 -distribution.

The pivotal statistics $r(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ can also be used to construct confidence intervals for a scalar ($p = 1$) sub-parameter θ_0 of $\boldsymbol{\psi}_0$. In this case, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$ denotes the remaining parameters of $\boldsymbol{\psi}_0$; that is, $(\theta_0, \boldsymbol{\mu}_0^\top)^\top = \boldsymbol{\psi}_0$. Hence, $\widehat{r}(\theta_0)$ defined by equation (1.13) follows asymptotically a χ^2 -distribution with one degree of freedom. Thus, the $\alpha\%$ empirical likelihood confidence interval for θ_0 is given by

$$\{\theta : r(\theta) \leq \chi_{df=1}^2(\alpha)\},$$

where $\chi_{df=1}^2(\alpha)$ is the upper α -quantile of the χ^2 -distribution with one degree of freedom. Note that $r(\theta)$ is a convex function of θ with a minimum value when θ is equal to the empirical maximum likelihood estimator $\widehat{\theta}$. Based on this property, the bisection method can be used to find the lower and upper bounds. This involves calculating $r(\theta)$ for several values of θ . Figure 1.2 gives a visual representation of the confidence interval.

Figure 1.2: Empirical likelihood confidence interval.

1.5 Numerical illustration based on synthetic EU-SILC data (AMELIA)

The ‘*European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions*’ (EU-SILC) survey is an European survey which collects information on income and living conditions (EUROSTAT, 2012). This surveys is used for measuring poverty within the European Union. ALFONS et al. (2011) created a synthetic dataset, called AMELIA, based on EU-SILC. AMELIA maintains the association between key variables. A full description of the AMELIA data can be found in ALFONS et al. (2011).

We consider a subset of AMELIA defined by the 3 regions with the variable ‘*PROV*’ equal to 1, 2 and 3. We also select only the individuals between 19 and 79 years of age. These three regions will be used as strata. This subset is replicated twenty times to create an artificial population of 1,539,368 individuals. The strata sizes are 148,236, 567,376 and 823,756. These individuals are grouped into cities/communities (variable ‘*CIT*’), which will play the role as PSUs. The first stratum contains 1420 PSUs, the second stratum contains 2,540 PSUs, and the third stratum contains 2640 PSUs. We select respectively 72, 128 and 132 PSUs within stratum 1, 2 and 3. A randomised systematic sample of PSUs are selected with probabilities proportional to their sizes. Within each PSUs selected, 20% of individuals (with a minimum of 5) are selected with simple random sampling. Non

respondents are generated randomly with the probabilities equation (1.1) with

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_i &= [1, \xi_i^{(a)}, \xi_i^{(b)}, \delta\{\text{Urb}_i = 1\}, \delta\{\text{Urb}_i = 3\}]^\top, \\ \lambda_0 &= (0.5, -0.2, 0.2, -0.2, 0.2)^\top.\end{aligned}$$

where $\xi_i^{(a)}$ and $\xi_i^{(b)}$ are values generated independently from a Bernoulli(0.05) distribution. Here Urb_i is the level of urbanisation of the individual i : $\text{Urb}_i = 1$ for densely-populated areas, $\text{Urb}_i = 2$ for intermediate areas and $\text{Urb}_i = 3$ for thinly-populated areas. The function $\delta\{A\} = 1$ when A is true and $\delta\{A\} = 0$, otherwise. The response probabilities lies between 52% and 72%.

The model of interest is the following logistic model

$$\text{Logit}\{Pr(\text{Emp}_i = 1)\} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Age}_i + \beta_2 \text{Educ}_i + \beta_3 \text{Married}_i + \beta_4 \text{Male}_i,$$

where $\text{Emp}_i = 1$ if the individual i is employed and $\text{Emp}_i = 0$ otherwise. The explanatory variables are:

- (I) Age_i , the age of i ,
- (II) $\text{Educ}_i = 1$ if the highest ISCED level attained is strictly larger than 3 and $\text{Educ}_i = 0$ otherwise,
- (III) $\text{Married}_i = 1$ if i is married and $\text{Married}_i = 0$ otherwise,
- (IV) $\text{Male}_i = 1$ if i is male and $\text{Male}_i = 0$ otherwise.

We consider three approaches for the inference estimation the regression parameters: EL denotes the empirical likelihood approach described in Section 1.4.2, PseudoL denotes the pseudo-likelihood approach (BINDER, 1983), and the naïve approach based on maximum likelihood. The pseudo-likelihood approach is implemented using the R (R DEVELOPMENT CORE TEAM, 2014) function `svyglm()` within the package `Survey`. This approach does not take the non-response into account, because it treat the sample of respondents as the sample selected by the two-stage design. The naïve approach is implemented using the R function `glm()`. In order to investigate the performance of the different approaches, we selected 1000 two-stage samples to compute the observed expectation, mean squared errors (MSE) and coverages of the confidence intervals.

In Table 1.1, we have the observed expectations and MSE for the three approaches. The

naïve approach gives slightly biased estimates. The MSE of the naïve approach is smaller, but with larger biases. The empirical likelihood and pseudo-likelihood approaches give similar bias and MSE.

Table 1.1: Observed expectation and mean squared errors (MSE) for the three approaches.

	β_0	Expectation			MSE		
		EL	PseudoL	Naïve	EL	PseudoL	Naïve
β_0 : Intercept	-1.836	-1.851	-1.851	-1.836	0.051	0.050	0.043
β_1 : Age	-0.020	-0.020	-0.020	-0.020	0.000	0.000	0.000
β_2 : Educ	-0.186	-0.185	-0.185	-0.192	0.033	0.033	0.029
β_3 : Married	0.115	0.113	0.113	0.120	0.033	0.032	0.028
β_4 : Male	0.019	0.027	0.027	0.025	0.027	0.027	0.022

In Table 1.2, we have the observed coverages of the 95% confidence intervals and the (left and right) tail error rates. The naïve approach can give coverages as high as 97.8%, and tail error rate as low as 0.6% or 1%. This is due to the bias of the variance estimator obtained with naïve approach. The coverages of the empirical likelihood and pseudo-likelihood approaches are not significantly different from the nominal value (95%), except with β_4 . We do not observe major differences between the empirical likelihood and pseudo-likelihood approaches.

We should not draw general conclusion from this limited simulation study, because the logistic model considered is less sensitive to non-response. In another simulation study in OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2016a) shows that empirical likelihood may give better coverages. The empirical likelihood approach proposed has then advantage of taking into account of the non-response parameter. It can be also extended to missing not at random response mechanism.

Table 1.2: Observed coverages of the 95% confidence intervals and (left and right) tail error rates.

	Coverage (%)			Left err. rate (%)			Right err. rate (%)		
	EL	PseudoL	Naïve	EL	PseudoL	Naïve	EL	PseudoL	Naïve
β_0 : Intercept	95.9	95.4	97.8†	1.92	1.80	0.80†	2.22	2.80	1.40†
β_1 : Age	94.2	94.5	98.4†	3.60†	3.60†	1.00†	2.20	1.90	0.60†
β_2 : Educ	94.3	94.8	94.3	2.60	2.60	2.80	3.10	2.60	2.90
β_3 : Married	93.0†	93.4†	93.6†	3.80†	3.60†	3.80	3.20	3.00	2.60
β_4 : Male	94.0	94.4	95.2	3.10	2.90	2.20	2.90	2.70	2.60

†Coverages (or rates) significantly different from 95% (or 2.5%). p-value ≤ 0.05 .

2 Compensating for Missing Data in Longitudinal Panel Studies

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2.1 Introduction

Whereas imputation for cross-sectional data is already well-known, especially for the case when the data is missing at random (MAR), we present here an example of imputation for missing data in a longitudinal study. There are still future developments that need to be addressed in the imputation of longitudinal data but some preliminary approaches which preserve the hierarchical nature of the data have already been proposed and will be described in this report. Our chosen longitudinal dataset is the birth cohort study of the 1958 National Child Development Study (NCDS). The NCDS follows the lives of all people born in England, Scotland and Wales in one particular week of March 1958. Since the birth survey in 1958, there have been nine further ‘sweeps’ of all cohort members at ages 7, 11, 16, 23, 33, 42, 46, 50 and 55. In the first three sweeps (at ages 7, 11 and 16), the target sample was augmented to include immigrants born outside of Great Britain in the same week. The survey cohort members remain part of the target sample until they either die or permanently emigrate from Great Britain. The total eligible sample, including those not resident in Great Britain up to the age of 16 in 1974, is 18558. The survey data is collected at individual level across Great Britain making it a nationally representative longitudinal cohort study.

For this particular study, we investigate Socioeconomic status (SES) as a key predictor for various outcomes at various times throughout the life course. We define a continuous repeated measure of life course SES as the main exposure of interest. In section 2.2 we define the model of interest and the derivation of the SES and covariates. In section 2.3, we examine the missing data in our study with respect to the model of interest and carry out two types of imputation methods. Results are shown in section 2.4 with a brief discussion and future work in section 2.5.

2.2 Model of Interest on SES

We derive our life course measure of SES from the Occupational Earnings Scale (BUKODI et al., 2011). This measure injects a form of hierarchy by classifying occupations into Standard Occupational Classes and then by ordering each these classes according to their mean hourly wage rate using ONS Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings data (1997-2013). These mean hourly wages have been adjusted for inflation and wages are deflated to 1997 prices using ONS Consumer Price Index data. These hourly wage data have also been transformed onto the natural logarithmic scale to correct for positive skewness. We use this Occupational Earnings Scale to develop NCDS occupation data as a continuous, repeated measure of SES over the life course (age range 23-55 over 6 time points). We denote this (transformed) variable as “Mean Hourly Occupational Earnings” (MHOE).

Our main covariate of interest is the NCDS cohort members’ parental SES. We define the covariate as a formatively causal composite response to observed variables that are associated with SES; namely social class (2 variables consisting of 8 categories for both parents), age left education (2 variables consisting of 10 categories for both parents) and housing tenure status (1 variable consisting of 6 categories). These variables were collected when survey cohort members were aged 16 (1974). We apply the ordinal Principal Component Analysis (oPCA) methodology developed by KOLENIKOV and ANGELES (2009) to derive the main component which represents a linear summary of our selected parental SES variables. Each of the five ordinal variables were first normalised so that their ranges were bounded between zero and one. Then oPCA was employed to uncover the main principal component which proved to be the only principal component with an eigenvalue greater than one and the individual component scores were all positive indicating that a higher weighted value implied a greater SES score. The predicted scores for the main principal component were estimated for each NCDS cohort member, transformed onto the natural logarithmic scale to account for positive skewness and then standardised to aid with interpretation. We denote this person-level variable as PSES16 . We adjust the relationship between PSES16 and MHOE by controlling for key socio-demographic variables namely sex and region of residence.

Multilevel modelling provides a method for analysing change over time whereby repeated measures are viewed as outcomes that are dependent on some metric of time and predictors of interest at either level (time/individual) including cross-level interactions can also

be incorporated into the model (STEELE, 2008). The dataset is prepared in such a way that the occasions (time) appear as separate records nested within individuals. Therefore, there is no requirement to have balanced data, so individuals who contribute fewer than the maximum number of occasions, i.e. partially observed, can be retained in the analysis without further adjustment. Within a multilevel framework, these individuals can “borrow strength” from other individuals with full information. This approach is reasonable assuming the missing data are missing at random (MAR), which implies the probability of data being missing does not depend on the unobserved data conditional on the observed data, and so long as a full information estimation procedure is used such as maximum likelihood assuming normally distributed data. If these two conditions are satisfied then the actual missingness mechanism can be ignored (RASBASH et al., 2015).

In our modelling approach, we treat the time function as a step function (categorical) as this allows emphasis on exploring relative inequities between individuals over the life course with a variance-covariance structure that is fully described by random terms at the person-level with no occasion-level residuals. This time function is not as naive as a simple linear function but allows for easier interpretation compared to more complex models. We therefore employ a life course step function multilevel model (MLM) as our model of interest with six age dummy variables and no model intercept to aid with interpretation. Each age dummy variable has a random slope attached to it allowing for individual variation at each time point in relation to the MHOE response variable. We employ cross-level interactions between each of the age dummies (occasion-level) and both of the person-level explanatory variables, namely PSES16 and Female, to explore life course developmental effects of these person-level predictors in relation to the MHOE response variable. To ensure model identification, the age 23 cross-level interaction effects are omitted and act as reference categories. The reference category for our nominal categorical occasion-level Region of residence predictor is North & Midlands. Our life course step

function random slope MLM of interest is specified as follows:

Mean Hourly Occupational Earnings_{tj} =

$$\begin{aligned}
& \beta_{0j}\text{age}23_{tj} + \beta_{1j}\text{age}33_{tj} + \beta_{2j}\text{age}42_{tj} + \beta_{3j}\text{age}46_{tj} + \beta_{4j}\text{age}50_{tj} + \beta_{5j}\text{age}55_{tj} \\
& + \beta_{6j}\text{PSES}16_j\beta_{7j}\text{Female}_j + \beta_{8j}\text{age}33 * \text{PSES}16_{tj} + \beta_{9j}\text{age}42 * \text{PSES}16_{tj} \\
& + \beta_{10j}\text{age}46 * \text{PSES}16_{tj}\beta_{11j}\text{age}50 * \text{PSES}16_{tj} + \beta_{12j}\text{age}55 * \text{PSES}16_{tj} \\
& + \beta_{13j}\text{age}33 * \text{Female}_{tj} + \beta_{14j}\text{age}42 * \text{Female}_{tj} + \beta_{15j}\text{age}46 * \text{Female}_{tj} \\
& + \beta_{16j}\text{age}50 * \text{Female}_{tj} + \beta_{17j}\text{age}55 * \text{Female}_{tj} \\
& + \beta_{18j}\text{South \& East}_{tj}\beta_{19j}\text{Wales}_{tj} + \beta_{20j}\text{Scotland}_{tj} \\
& + u_{0j}\text{age}23_{tj} + u_{1j}\text{age}33_{tj} + u_{2j}\text{age}42_{tj} + u_{3j}\text{age}46_{tj} + u_{4j}\text{age}50_{tj} + u_{5j}\text{age}55_{tj}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{u} \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \Omega_{\mathbf{u}})$$

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbb{V} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{0j} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_{5j} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{u_0}^2 & \cdots & \sigma_{u_0u_5} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{u_0u_5} & \cdots & \sigma_{u_5}^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

2.3 Missing Data

From the total eligible sample size of 18558, we restrict ourselves to 14268 individuals omitting 4290 (23.1%) cohort members who have no occupation data over the life course and hence no MHOE at any time point. Therefore, our target population is based on those with known employment over the life course. Table 2.1 displays the number of completed survey sweeps for the MHOE dependent variable. Almost 22% (n = 3083) of eligible cohort members can be considered complete case (CC) with no missing data. The remaining 78% (n = 11185) can be considered partially observed (PO) with 1 to 5 data time points missing. Nearly 60% of the sample has 4 or more data points.

Regarding missing values on the predictors, 9647 (32.4%) observations out of 14268 is missing on the PSES16 variable. The variable entitled ‘‘Female’’ contains no missing data (50.9% males (n = 7261)). Region of residence records where every responding cohort member resides at each age throughout the life course (range 23-55 over 6 time points). This 4-category nominal variable is approximately distributed as follows: North & Mid-

lands (life course average = 42.3%), South & East (life course average = 43.0%), Wales (life course average = 5.4%) and Scotland (life course average = 9.3%) with a life course average of 10414 (27%) observations out of 14268.

Table 2.1: Completed survey sweeps – MHOE

Completed sweeps	# cohort members	%	Cumulative %
6	3083	21.6%	21.6%
5	3297	23.1%	44.7%
4	1980	13.9%	58.6%
3	1613	11.3%	69.9%
2	1921	13.5%	83.4%
1	2374	16.6%	100%
Total	14268	100%	

As there are a total of 14268 person-level available cases in this analysis, that allows for a possible total of 85608 (14268*6 time points) occasion-level observations over the life course. However, with missing data in our response variable this number is reduced to 53958 occasion-level observations. Including the model covariates with their missingness reduces the number of occasion-level observations to 37478 and the number of person-level observations to 9622 representing 44% and 67% respectively of the sample at each level. This will be the data used for the available case (AC) analysis.

Figure 2.1 displays the average life course MHOE trajectories for CC (n = 3083; 21.6%), PO (n = 11185; 78.4%) and AC (n = 14268; 100%). Discrepancies exist between CC and PO trajectories most prevalently at ages 23 and 33 and appear to diminish thereafter. The AC trajectory is a weighted average of CC and PO curves and is located closer to the PO curve given PO cases account for 78.4% of the life course survey sample. Furthermore, the life course trend appears to show linearity between the ages of 23 and 42 (1981 – 2000) and concavity between the ages of 42 and 55 (2000 – 2013). This concavity might be explained by the Great Recession which began in 2008 with the financial crisis when the survey cohort members were aged 50 and/or by the effects of early retirement.

HAWKES and PLEWIS (2006) report that there are systematic differences between respondents and non-respondents at every sweep of the NCDS with the more disadvantaged survey members being more likely to be lost from the study. Table 2.2 presents t-test results whereby the average MHOE at each age is distinguished by whether or not survey cohort members are missing their MHOE at all other time points throughout the life course. A positive mean difference between the groups indicates that the ‘not missing’

group at one time point have a higher average MHOE at another time point (significance at the 0.1% level is marked by ***). The general pattern is for those who are not missing MHOE throughout the life course to have higher MHOE at each time point with the exception of being missing at age 23. This exception may be explained by those delaying their entry into the workforce through higher education pursuits. The evidence here adds weight to Hawkes and Plewis' assertions that the less advantaged are more likely to be missing and these data are not MCAR.

Figure 2.1: Life course Mean Hourly Occupational Earnings by Response Profile

While the evidence suggests these data are not MCAR, Figure 2.2 presents evidence of MAR. Each model covariate can discriminate between CC and PO individuals and all variables reflect the overall situation with higher MHOE experienced by the CC individuals. Furthermore, Figure 2.1 already established that age throughout the life course can also discriminate between CC and PO individuals in relation to MHOE.

The evidence presented in Figure 2.2 strengthens the argument for assuming our data

are MAR. It also suggests that a full information maximum likelihood (FIML) approach using all available cases should provide optimal estimation and inference (BARTLETT and CARPENTER, 2013). We use this evidence of MAR validity to conduct Multiple Imputation (MI) in an effort to compensate for the non-trivial amount of missing data within our study sample. When addressing our missing data situation we do not include any additional auxiliary or instrumental variables in the imputation model as there are very few NCDS variables that are fully (or almost fully) observed containing information on respondents and non-respondents. This is a limitation of our study. Therefore, for the imputation model, we have followed GOLDSTEIN (2009) whereby any variable used in the analysis model of interest is used in the imputation model. We test two imputation models, one that adheres to the hierarchical data structure of the data using a multilevel multiple imputation (MLMI) approach where the occasions are nested within individuals, and the other the standard multiple imputation chained equations (MICE) where the data is prepared under the wide format, i.e. each individual represents one record and all occasions listed sequentially on the record.

MLMI for missing data in a longitudinal setting: CARPENTER et al. (2011) developed the Realcom-Impute software which can perform MLMI and can handle ordinal and unordered categorical data appropriately. With this approach, a MLM is specified for the partially observed variables given the fully observed variables. This MLM is fitted to the observed data and multiple imputations of the missing data are generated typically using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods. This approach models the joint distribution of the incomplete variables conditional on the complete variables using a multivariate latent normal model which allows for the proper handling of a two-level structure whereby person-level variables are constant over the observations at the occasion-level. Using a multilevel imputation model with random coefficients and cross-level interactions helps avoid biasing the parameter estimates if using a MLM of interest with random coefficients and cross-level interactions thereby reducing the likelihood of producing potentially invalid estimates of precision.

MICE for missing data in a longitudinal setting: A popular MI approach involves employing chained equations, also referred to as the fully conditional specification (FCS) algorithm, which specifies separate univariate imputation models for each variable with missing data conditional on all other variables (VAN BUUREN et al., 1999). Therefore, we can choose a model appropriate to the variable type, e.g. continuous, count, ordered

Table 2.2: Mean difference in MHOE by not missing vs missing at every other time point

MHOE by age		Mean Difference	Std Err
23	Not missing – missing MHOE at 33	0.05***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 42	0.06***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 46	0.06***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 50	0.06***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 55	0.08***	0.01
33	Not missing – missing MHOE at 23	-0.08***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 42	0.12***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 46	0.12***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 50	0.11***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 55	0.11***	0.01
42	Not missing – missing MHOE at 23	-0.08***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 33	0.05***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 46	0.10***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 50	0.09***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 55	0.09***	0.01
46	Not missing – missing MHOE at 23	-0.08***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 33	0.05***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 42	0.14***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 50	0.07***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 55	0.07***	0.01
50	Not missing – missing MHOE at 23	-0.07***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 33	0.06***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 42	0.14***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 46	0.12***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 55	0.07***	0.01
55	Not missing – missing MHOE at 23	-0.07***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 33	0.01	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 42	0.08***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 46	0.06***	0.01
	Not missing – missing MHOE at 50	0.01	0.02

categorical, unordered categorical, and characteristics measured at fixed times over the life course are treated as distinct variables. WELCH et al. (2014) report that this method is easier computationally than directly specifying a multivariate distribution for a mixture of continuous and categorical variables with missing data, as required in parametric MI's original form. In the same paper, they also advocate a two-fold FCS algorithm for applying MI to longitudinal data. This modified version of the original FCS algorithm imputes missing values at a given time point from a model that only uses information from that time point and immediately adjacent time points. However, this simplification may induce bias in parameter estimates if the measurements excluded from imputation models have

Figure 2.2: Life course Mean Hourly Occupational Earnings by covariate subgroup

independent effects, i.e. there exists dependency over the life course. It is for this reason we opt for the FCS algorithm instead of the two-fold version.

We produce 10 imputed datasets using the MLMI method for 8 variables with missingness conditional on 12 fully observed variables (long data matrix format) with 2000 iterations burn-in phase followed by 500 iterations between each imputed dataset (7000 iterations in total). This took approximately 6 days, whereas completing 10 imputed datasets using the MICE procedure for 13 incomplete variables plus 1 fully observed (wide data matrix format) with 7000 iterations took less than 24 hours.

2.4 Results

Tables 2.3 and 2.4 display the fixed effect model results on the natural log scale for the available case (AC), complete case (CC), partially observed (PO) and the two types of multiple imputation: MLMI and MICE. Table 2.5 displays the random effect model results.

Regarding the AC case, we see the age dummies follow the sample MHOE means at each time point adjusted for the model covariates. Order of magnitude among the main covariate effects sees sex as being the strongest predictor of life course MHOE and region of residence being the weakest. The life course interaction effects demonstrate the positive legacy effect of experiencing higher parental SES at age 16 and being a male in relation to life course MHOE. From this analysis, we infer that females with lower parental SES at age 16 residing in Wales are at a MHOE disadvantage compared to males with higher parental SES at age 16 residing in the South & East region.

Table 2.3: MHOE life course MLM fixed effects (I)

	AC		CC		PO		MLMI		MICE	
Obs	37478		13561		23917		82654		82654	
Groups	9622		2263		7359		14268		14268	
Min	1		5		1		1		1	
Av	3.9		6		3.3		5.8		5.8	
Max	6		6		5		6		6	
Main Effects	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE
<i>Age</i>										
23	2.016	0.006	2.050	0.011	2.002	0.007	2.006	0.005	2.013	0.005
33	2.161	0.007	2.195	0.012	2.151	0.008	2.159	0.006	2.163	0.006
42	2.279	0.007	2.310	0.013	2.269	0.008	2.273	0.007	2.277	0.006
46	2.380	0.007	2.414	0.012	2.368	0.009	2.379	0.008	2.380	0.006
50	2.421	0.007	2.458	0.012	2.406	0.009	2.419	0.006	2.421	0.006
55	2.338	0.007	2.368	0.012	2.327	0.009	2.339	0.007	2.339	0.007
PSES16	0.091	0.004	0.085	0.007	0.089	0.004	0.099	0.006	0.091	0.004
Female	-0.148	0.007	-0.145	0.013	-0.148	0.008	-0.146	0.025	-0.147	0.005

Comparing the different modelling we see little difference between the coefficients. One noticeable difference is in the interaction with age and PSE16 which have turned coefficients to be negative under the MLMI. To summarize the impact of the imputation we turn to Table 2.6 which presents a comparison of average life course step function MLM predictions. The AC results are displayed as mean predictions and the other results are

displayed as predicted percentage differences compared to the AC values. Relative to AC, the average life course predicted percentage difference between CC and PO is just over 2% with the gap between the groups narrowing over the life course. This finding is consistent with the descriptive statistics presented in Figure 2.1. By contrast, the average life course predicted percentage difference between CC and PO is larger than the gap between MLMI and MICE by a factor greater than 10 relative to AC. The differences between MLMI and MICE, with respect to these predictions, appear to be negligible. Given the underlying data and model of interest, the evidence suggests that these two MI methods produce similar results. Furthermore, both MLMI and MICE methods produced results that were more similar to PO than CC but more similar to AC than PO.

2.5 Discussion

We assess multiple imputation solutions for correcting for missing data in longitudinal studies under the assumption that the missing data is under the MAR non-response mechanism. We contrasted the faster MICE approach with the approach that provided a closer fit between the imputation model and analytical model, MLMI, given the structure of our data and model of interest. We discovered that the MICE method can produce similarly plausible empirical results compared with the computationally slower MLMI method. Moreover, both sets of results were more similar to AC results compared with CC and PO results on average. This evidence suggests the full information maximum likelihood (FIML) approach using all available cases is sufficient in this study and the MI process amounted to a robustness check for the model results and inferences.

In the future, we will assess other imputation models which include auxiliary variables under different types of models of interest for longitudinal studies and also carry out a more comprehensive analysis on the impact of imputation with respect to both point estimates and their variance. In particular, new software has recently been developed for MLMI imputation called Stat-JR software (CHARLTON et al., 2012) which will likely reduce the computational time and hence will allow more possibility for carrying out comparison studies. We include other approaches for dealing with missing data in longitudinal studies such as inverse propensity weighting and Heckman Selection Models. We also aim to extend to both MAR and NMAR non-response mechanisms and carry out further sensitivity analysis.

Table 2.4: MHOE life course MLM fixed effects (II)

	AC		CC		PO		MLMI		MICE	
	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE
<i>Region of residence</i>	<i>Ref: North & Midlands</i>									
South & East	0.025	0.006	0.010	0.010	0.030	0.007	0.029	0.005	0.018	0.009
Wales	-0.038	0.012	-0.038	0.023	-0.035	0.014	-0.003	0.010	-0.018	0.017
Scotland	0.011	0.009	0.014	0.018	0.012	0.011	0.010	0.009	0.001	0.012
Interaction Effects	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE	B	SE
	<i>Ref: 23 * PSES16</i>									
33 * PSES16	0.043	0.005	0.024	0.008	0.052	0.006	0.001	0.009	0.043	0.005
42 * PSES16	0.038	0.005	0.005	0.009	0.054	0.006	-0.014	0.012	0.039	0.005
46 * PSES16	0.034	0.005	0.016	0.009	0.043	0.006	-0.020	0.012	0.033	0.005
50 * PSES16	0.024	0.005	0.006	0.009	0.033	0.006	-0.029	0.013	0.022	0.006
55 * PSES16	0.022	0.005	0.008	0.009	0.030	0.007	-0.029	0.014	0.023	0.005
	<i>Ref: 23 * Female</i>									
33 * Female	-0.075	0.009	-0.075	0.016	-0.075	0.011	-0.077	0.009	-0.078	0.007
42 * Female	-0.083	0.010	-0.075	0.017	-0.087	0.012	-0.077	0.011	-0.077	0.008
46 * Female	-0.032	0.010	-0.021	0.017	-0.040	0.012	-0.032	0.013	-0.030	0.008
50 * Female	-0.029	0.010	-0.030	0.017	-0.027	0.013	-0.027	0.014	-0.024	0.008
55 * Female	-0.022	0.011	-0.005	0.017	-0.038	0.014	-0.018	0.014	-0.013	0.010

Table 2.5: MHOE life course MLM random effects

	AC		CC		PO		MLMI		MICE	
Obs	37478		13561		23917		82654		82654	
Groups	9622		2263		7359		14268		14268	
Min	1		5		1		1		1	
Av	3.9		6		3.3		5.8		5.8	
Max	6		6		5		6		6	
Random Effects	B	SE								
var(age23)	0.086	0.001	0.090	0.003	0.082	0.002	0.093	0.002	0.085	0.001
cov(age23,age33)	0.045	0.001	0.045	0.003	0.044	0.002	0.045	0.002	0.046	0.002
var(age33)	0.139	0.002	0.138	0.004	0.140	0.003	0.151	0.003	0.142	0.002
cov(age23,age42)	0.040	0.002	0.037	0.003	0.041	0.002	0.042	0.001	0.041	0.002
cov(age33,age42)	0.082	0.002	0.075	0.003	0.085	0.002	0.086	0.002	0.082	0.002
var(age42)	0.156	0.003	0.155	0.005	0.155	0.003	0.170	0.003	0.157	0.002
cov(age23,age46)	0.038	0.002	0.036	0.003	0.037	0.002	0.038	0.002	0.038	0.002
cov(age33,age46)	0.072	0.002	0.067	0.003	0.074	0.002	0.077	0.002	0.070	0.002
cov(age42,age46)	0.101	0.002	0.098	0.004	0.102	0.003	0.107	0.002	0.101	0.002
var(age46)	0.144	0.003	0.142	0.004	0.144	0.003	0.167	0.004	0.146	0.002
cov(age23,age50)	0.035	0.002	0.032	0.002	0.037	0.002	0.036	0.001	0.035	0.002
cov(age33,age50)	0.070	0.002	0.063	0.003	0.072	0.003	0.074	0.002	0.069	0.002
cov(age42,age50)	0.094	0.002	0.089	0.004	0.097	0.003	0.101	0.002	0.095	0.002
cov(age46,age50)	0.109	0.002	0.103	0.004	0.112	0.003	0.113	0.003	0.110	0.002
var(age50)	0.145	0.003	0.138	0.004	0.148	0.003	0.166	0.002	0.145	0.002
cov(age23,age55)	0.033	0.002	0.031	0.002	0.033	0.002	0.033	0.002	0.033	0.002
cov(age33,age55)	0.064	0.002	0.059	0.003	0.067	0.003	0.069	0.002	0.064	0.002
cov(age42,age55)	0.083	0.002	0.081	0.003	0.083	0.003	0.090	0.002	0.084	0.002
cov(age46,age55)	0.091	0.002	0.087	0.003	0.093	0.003	0.101	0.002	0.093	0.002
cov(age50,age55)	0.100	0.002	0.095	0.003	0.102	0.003	0.106	0.002	0.102	0.002
var(age55)	0.138	0.003	0.133	0.004	0.139	0.004	0.164	0.004	0.142	0.002

Table 2.6: Subject Specific life course MHOE (log scale) MLM predictions

Age	AC	CC	PO	MLMI	MICE
23	1.954	2.0%	-0.9%	-0.4%	-0.3%
33	2.065	1.9%	-0.8%	-0.2%	-0.3%
42	2.182	1.6%	-0.7%	-0.3%	-0.4%
46	2.322	1.2%	-0.7%	-0.8%	-1.0%
50	2.357	1.3%	-0.7%	-0.4%	-0.6%
55	2.287	1.0%	-0.7%	-0.6%	-0.8%
Average	2.194	1.5%	-0.7%	-0.4%	-0.6%

3 Compensating for Measurement Errors from Random Noise Addition

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3.1 Introduction

Providers of datasets for research purposes are typically confronted by a tension between making available useful fit-for-purpose data retaining the fine grain with which the data were obtained, and ‘perturbing’ the data sufficiently so that, even without obvious identification information such as name, birth data, address location, an ‘intruder’ or ‘attacker’ cannot easily obtain the identity of any given person within the dataset. A review of procedures for anonymization of such public use datasets is given by WILLENBORG and DE WAAL (2001) and HUNDEPOOL et al. (2012) and references therein.

In this report we show that a data analyst can fit models that respect the fine grain of the original data when random noise has been added to some or all variables in a data set to protect the confidentiality of individuals. The noise so generated can then be removed at the analysis stage if its characteristics are known, requiring disclosure of the distribution parameters generating the noise by the statistical agency. This leads to consistent model parameter estimates, although a loss of efficiency will occur. In contrast, the usual method of anonymisation through coarsening the data such as grouping, would not allow the retrieval of the model parameter estimates.

This concept is discussed in some detail by FULLER (1993). He points out that the optimum approach is where the random noise is added independently for each variable in the dataset and we shall also make this assumption. He treats the case of normal measurement errors and true data that have a multivariate normal distribution (with an approximation for discrete data). He derives a probability that any given record in the released data can be identified as the ‘correct’ one based upon a subset of the variable values that are known to the attacker. His method of constructing the perturbed data is designed to provide almost unbiased inferences for linear models and he discusses some of the difficulties for non-linear and non-additive models.

Following the work of FULLER (1993), for example SHLOMO (2010) adds noise that is a linear function of the variables to be perturbed. This preserves sufficient statistics in the form of means and covariance matrices, without requiring knowledge of the precise parameter values used to generate the noise, which Fuller’s procedure requires. The main drawback again, is that it is restricted to models that can be fitted using sufficient statistics, and thus excludes, for example, generalised linear models other than multiple regression and also multilevel models. It also does not allow diagnostics based on residuals since the production of residual estimates requires knowledge of the noise parameters.

Releasing parameters used to generate the noise is common practice in cryptography literature in Computer Science in order to be able to decode encryptions although it is rarely done at statistical agencies. COX et al. (2011) discuss the need for transparency in which a statistical agency released information about the disclosure control processes used to transform the original data to the masked released data. They distinguish between legitimate users and intruders and advocate controlled release of the parameters used to generate the noise so that legitimate users can carry out statistical inferences.

The technique described below for the analysis of perturbed data applies generally to complex models including non-linear and multilevel ones.

3.2 Measurement errors

Consider a subset of q variables, y , that are potentially disclosive. We deal first with the case of a set of continuously distributed variables assumed to be multivariate normal (MVN).

We suppose that the attacker has a set of values on q variables, say y^* , that she intends to match against records in the dataset. We introduce random noise in the form of q variates m and for simplicity we shall consider the special case where these variates are independent. We have

$$z = y + m, \quad y \sim MVN(\mu, \Omega), \quad m \sim MVN(0, \Omega_m), \quad z \sim MVN(\mu, \Omega + \sigma_m^2 I), \quad \Omega_m \text{ diagonal}$$

The value of Ω_m will determine the strength of the resistance to attack.

We make no distinction between primary and quasi identifiers, although all could be incorporated in the weighting matrix if needed. Our proposed method is essentially prob-

abilistic rather than one that guarantees a given level of anonymity, as in the standard k -anonymisation methods. The key element, however, is that from the data analysts viewpoint there is no data coarsening, for example by grouping or truncating extreme values, with potentially enhanced quality for the inferences. It is applicable to all statistical models for which the measurement error methods can be applied and also allows residual and other diagnostics to be used.

Adding noise is a special case of the so-called synthetic data approach where data is generated from a series of predictive distributions (RUBIN (1993) and REITER (2005)). Our proposed approach carrying out analysis is applicable in this setting as well.

3.3 Mis-classifications for categorical variables

A common approach for the mis-classification of categorical variables is the post-randomisation method (PRAM) (GOUWELEEUW et al. (1998)). Let P be a $L \times L$ transition matrix containing conditional probabilities $p_{ij} = p(\text{perturbed category is } j | \text{original category is } i)$ for a categorical variable with L categories. In each record of the data set, the category of the variable is changed or not changed according to the prescribed transition probabilities in the matrix P and the result of a draw of a random multinomial variate u with parameters p_{ij} ($j=1, \dots, L$). If the j -th category is selected, category i is moved to category j . When $i = j$, no change occurs.

For multicategory, including ordered and unordered variables, we can alternatively consider the following, simpler, procedure. Numbering the categories $j = \{1, \dots, L\}$ we independently add noise to the true category code:

$$m_j \sim N(j, \sigma_\gamma^2), \quad 1 \leq m_j \leq L \quad (3.1)$$

This results in a truncated normal distribution. The purpose of the truncation is to avoid easy detection for the extreme category codes. We could also generalise the noise addition to allow different variances for each category. We note that the noise is simply added to the category codes $\{1, \dots, L\}$, irrespective of whether this is an ordered or unordered variable.

3.4 Fitting models with known measurement error

Bayesian procedures for fitting models with measurement errors have been proposed (RICHARDSON and GILKS (1993)) and these have been further developed to fit multi-level data structures and allow models that include interaction and power terms. An outline of a general algorithm with details specific to data anonymisation is given below, and further details of the estimation algorithm can be found in GOLDSTEIN and BROWNE (2016).

The following exposition is for a single level linear model with a single predictor variable that has measurement error – the case of several predictors with error, the case where we have a generalised linear model and the multilevel case follow straightforwardly. We assume multivariate normality and where we have categorical or count variables or continuous variables for which a normalising transformation exists (GOLDSTEIN et al. (2009)), then the appropriate extra steps are inserted into the MCMC algorithm to enable a random draw from underlying normal distributions.

Define the true values of the variable with measurement error as X_1 and those without measurement error as X_2 , and $X = [X_1 \ X_2]$.

Define the joint model - the measurement error model (MEM) in two parts, equation (a) and equation (b) and the model of interest (MOI) equation (c) – see derivation below:

$$x_1 = X_1 + \gamma_1 \tag{a}$$

$$X_1 = X_2^T \alpha + \gamma_2 \tag{b}$$

$$Y = X\beta + e \tag{c}$$

We note that the MOI equation (c) may contain functions of X_1 , such as interaction or power terms. Lower case variables define observed and upper case true values, and we assume the residual terms in equation (a)-equation (c) are independent. A Metropolis step is used for record i , where a current value is proposed. If we denote this by X_{1i} , the joint log likelihood for equation (a), equation (b) and equation (c) is the product of the

following components that involve the true values:

$$-\frac{0.5(x_{1i} - X_{1i})^2}{\sigma_{\gamma_1}^2}, \quad -\frac{0.5(X_{1i}^T - X_{2i}^T \alpha)^2}{\sigma_{\gamma_2}^2}, \quad -\frac{0.5(\tilde{y}_i)^2}{\sigma_e^2} \quad (3.2)$$

where $\tilde{y}_i = y_i - X_i \beta$.

For a proposal distribution we can use

$$p(X_1 | x_1) \sim N(x_1 R, R(1 - R) \sigma_{x_1}^2) \quad (3.3)$$

where R is the reliability $= \frac{\text{var}(X_1)}{\text{var}(x_1)}$. This formulation is similar to RICHARDSON and GILKS (1993) where they have a ‘gold standard’ validation sample that provides the information contained in equation (a). In other cases, we may wish to carry out sensitivity analyses for different values of $\sigma_{\gamma_1}^2$ or even place an informative prior on this parameter.

For the case where we have several variables with measurement error we can propose the set of values defined independently for each variable or look at the joint proposal distribution in the case where correlated noise has been used, namely $f(X_1 | x_1) \sim MVN(X_1 \Omega_{x_1}^{-1} \Omega_{X_1}, \Omega_{X_1} - \Omega_{X_1} \Omega_{x_1}^{-1} \Omega_{X_1})$, although the use of correlated noise, generally would seem to be unnecessary and serves only to complicate the analysis. Further details can be found in GOLDSTEIN et al. (2016).

For discrete variables where we have misclassification errors, there is an analogous procedure (GOLDSTEIN and BROWNE (2016)), but this becomes complicated when there are multiple categories. Instead we apply the procedure given by equation (3.1) as follows:

The variable X_1 in equation (a) and for each of these independently (assuming that independent noise has been used), we now have the set of category codes $(0, \dots, L-1)$. Associated with this variable we will have $L-1$ dummy variables D_1 . The proposal distribution is conveniently chosen as the observed distribution across the categories, based on choosing the nearest integer, or the ‘true’ distribution could be made available by the data provider. The log-likelihood contribution is given by

$$-\frac{0.5(m_{ij} - j^*)^2}{\sigma_{\gamma_1}^2} \text{ if } 0 < m_{ij} < L - 1$$

$$\log\left(\int_{-\infty}^0 \phi(f) df\right), \quad f \sim N(j^*, \sigma_\gamma^2) \text{ if } m_{ij} \leq 0$$

$$\log\left(\int_{p-1}^{\infty} \phi(f) df\right), \quad f \sim N(j^*, \sigma_\gamma^2) \text{ if } m_{ij} \geq L - 1$$

where j^* is the proposed value and m_{ij} is the observed ‘noisy’ value truncated at zero and $L - 1$.

In some cases we may wish to present perturbed categorical data to a data analyst only as a set of discrete values, for example as the nearest integer to the ‘noisy’ value. Thus, for example for a perturbed value in the range $(-\infty, 1.5)$ we would report the value as 1 and generally as j if in the interval $(j - 0.5, j + 0.5)$. For the likelihood contribution for a proposed value j^* we now have the likelihood contributions:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{0.5} \phi(f) df \text{ if } m_{ij} = 0$$

$$\int_{m_{ij}-0.5}^{m_{ij}+0.5} \phi(f) df \text{ if } 0 < m_{ij} < L - 1$$

$$\int_{p-1.5}^{\infty} \phi(f) df \text{ if } m_{ij} = L - 1$$

For each proposed category in categorical variable X_1 we will have an entry of ‘1’ in the corresponding dummy variable in D_1 . This set of dummy variables will enter the MOI as predictors and the response vector corresponding to equation (b), where the default link function is the multivariate probit as described in GOLDSTEIN et al. (2009). If we wish to allow actual measurement errors for continuous predictors as well as the imposed anonymization categorical measurement errors, it will be convenient to propose true values for the former in a separate step, conditional on all the current categorical predictor values. Where we have imposed anonymization measurement errors for continuous variables as well as actual measurement errors, we may simply add the variances for the former to the corresponding diagonal terms of the actual measurement error covariance matrix.

Standard errors quoted are the standard deviations computed from the MCMC chains in

the usual way.

In some cases we may have additional constraints on the data values. For example, if the perturbed value x_1 is constrained to be no larger than a chosen value, we may have

$$\text{if}(x_1 > C_1), \text{ set } x_1 = C_1$$

where the value C_1 does not occur in the data set. Then, whenever $x_1 = C_1$, we would sample a value from the upper tail of the normal distribution defined by the current values from equation (b) and use this in the Metropolis step. A similar procedure could be used more generally where grouping of values takes place. Care will be needed, however, to ensure that there is not too much loss of efficiency associated with this.

For a response variable with added noise, the situation is more complex but for normally distributed responses we can carry out an analysis using the observed values to obtain consistent estimates. In this case we can obtain a consistent estimate for the residual variance by subtracting the (known) variance for the measurement error in the response, say σ_δ^2 , from the final estimated residual variance. For categorical responses the situation is more complex and is the subject of further research. As we show in our example, however, this may result in a large increase in the standard errors when the measurement error variance is large relative to the residual variance. When data are released it may be acceptable to provide any variable(s) to be treated as a response with the true values or just a small amount of noise and this may not be too disclosive.

For categorical responses with misclassification or measurement errors a further modification is required. Thus, for example, in the case of a binary response where normally distributed noise has been added as in equation (3.1) we round the observed value to the nearest integer (0,1), denoted by y_i , and for the likelihood for the model of interest we can write

$$\delta_1 = \Pr(\text{obs} = 1 \mid \text{true} = 0) = \int_{0.5}^{\infty} \phi_\delta(t) dt \quad ,$$

$$\Pr(\text{obs} = 1 \mid \text{true} = 1) = 1 - \int_{0.5}^{\infty} \phi_\delta(t) dt$$

and this leads to

$$\Pr(y_i = 1 \mid X\beta) = \delta_1 + (1 - 2\delta_1) \int_{-X\beta}^{\infty} \phi(t) dt, \quad \phi_\delta \sim N(0, \sigma_\delta^2) \quad (3.4)$$

Thus for the β parameters, since σ_δ^2 is known, we will have a Metropolis step for each one in turn using the observed (0,1) values, subject to $\delta_1 + (1 - 2\delta_1) \int_{-\mathbf{X}\beta}^{\infty} \phi(t) dt < 1$.

Other methods for estimation of models with measurement errors are also available, such as the simulation-extrapolation method, SIMEX (DELAIGLE and HALL (2008)) and moment based estimators described by FULLER (2006), and these can be used also. The Bayesian model procedure, that we describe, has the advantage that it is a fully specified probabilistic model that is readily generalised to handle complex data structures including multilevel generalised linear models without approximations, with straightforward computation of interval estimates.

After fitting a suitable measurement error model, the original variable scales and relationships are fully recovered, albeit with a loss of efficiency – which with very large datasets may not be an important issue. The loss of efficiency, in terms of interval estimates or standard errors associated with parameter estimates can be estimated for any proposed model to be fitted to the perturbed data, given the noise parameters. Thus, for example, in the simple regression case where independent normal noise with a common variance σ^2 has been added to the set of predictors \mathbf{X} , we can use as a simple overall measure for the relative efficiency the determinantal ratio ($|\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}| / |\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X} + \sigma^2|$). The data provider would be able to supply such estimates, or those for individual parameters, alongside the released data. We illustrate the effects on standard errors in our example.

Where the original variables also are subject to measurement errors with known distributions the fitted model will be based upon the total measurement error.

In the case where the data provider wishes to impose additional, known, data constraints some modification to the estimation algorithm will be needed to incorporate these.

POLETTINI and ARIMA (2015) propose a method that has similarities to our own. They develop it in the context of small area estimation where the covariates have been subject to misclassification through PRAM. They apply a Bayesian algorithm to the data measured at the aggregate small area level, where categorical data are approximated by a multivariate normal distribution, where the adequacy of the approximation is a function of the number of individual records within an area. Our own procedure primarily operates at the level of individual records and does not involve such approximations. It can also be used to deal with data aggregated to higher levels as explained below.

Table 3.1

Estimates from addition of noise. (standard errors in brackets*). MCMC burn in =500 iterations=500. Simulations from model equation (3.5) Sample size = 1000, number of simulations = 100.				
Parameter	Simulation parameters	Noisy data no adjustment	Noisy data adjusted	Noisy data adjusted % bias
β_0	1.0	0.974 (0.004)	0.997 (0.003)	-0.3
β_1	1.0	0.887 (0.002)	1.004 (0.003)	0.4
β_2	1.0	1.051 (0.005)	1.003 (0.005)	0.3
σ_e^2	1.0	1.0	1.0	0
The standard error estimates are the standard deviations computed from the MCMC chains.				

3.5 A simulation of a measurement error model

We carry out a simple simulation from the following model, in order to illustrate that we can readily recover the signal from noisy data for both a binary and continuous predictor. The model we simulate from is given by

$$y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{ij} + \beta_2 x_{2ij} + e_{ij}, \quad e_{ij} \sim N(0, 0.2), \beta_0 = \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 1 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2^* \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right), x_2 = 0 \text{ if } x_2^* \leq 0; \quad x_2 = 1 \text{ if } x_2^* \geq 1;$$

Independent noise with variance 0.2 is added to x_1, x_2 . We carry out two sets of 100 simulations with 1000 records. The results are given in Table 3.1.

We see negligible bias, no more than 0.5% for the adjusted estimates and in all cases the 95% confidence interval overlaps the true value.

3.6 Example analyses

Our first example illustrates just the use of a measurement error model for two level data where we have added noise and used the procedures to estimate the true model parameters, and the data will be referred to as the Tutorial dataset (GOLDSTEIN et al. (1993)). The response is a normalised examination score taken at age 16 by 4059 students in 65 schools

Table 3.2: Tutorial dataset

Estimates from addition of noise (standard errors in brackets). MCMC burn in =500 iterations=500			
Parameter	Original model	Noisy data no adjustment	Noisy data adjusted
β_0	-0.097 (0.050)	-0.082 (0.044)	-0.093 (0.042)
β_1	0.559 (0.013)	0.460 (0.012)	0.549 (0.014)
β_2	0.174 (0.033)	0.109 (0.030)	0.155 (0.035)
σ_u^2	0.097 (0.021)	0.102 (0.022)	0.100 (0.020)
σ_e^2	0.563 (0.013)	0.614 (0.013)	0.562 (0.014)

in Inner London. The predictor variables are a standardised reading test score taken at age 11 (x_1) before pupils attended their secondary school and the binary variable gender (x_2). A 2-level variance components model is fitted:

$$y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{ij} + \beta_2 j + u_j + e_{ij}, \quad u_j \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2), \quad e_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_e^2) \quad (3.6)$$

We add normally distributed noise with mean 0 and variance 0.2 independently to the reading score and gender. For gender, values less than 0 are set to 0 and values greater than 1 are set to 1.

Table 3.2 shows the results from fitting the model before adding noise, fitting the model with added noise but without adjusting for measurement error and fitting adjusting for measurement error. Only one application of measurement error addition has been used to produce these results.

We note that the adjusted estimates are close to those using the original data whereas ignoring the measurement error produces estimates with considerable biases.

Our second example uses a dataset from a 1982 survey of the sugar cane farm industry in Queensland, Australia that was used in CHAMBERS and DUNSTAN (1986)).

The model of interest has the sugar cane yield receipt as response (y) and predictors are region (x_1 , Northern=1, Southern=0), sugar cane harvest (x_2 , continuous in tonnes) and cost (x_3 , in Australian dollars). There are 333 farms in the dataset with no missing data.

The model to be fitted is

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \beta_3 x_{3i} + e_i \quad e_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2) \quad (3.7)$$

Table 3.3

Sugar cane farm data. Results of fitting equation (3.3) to 5% and 17% relative variance noisy data to predictors only. Standard errors in brackets.					
Parameter	True data with no added noise	True data with 5% of variance added correlated noise on predictors only	True data with 5% of variance added independent noise on predictors only	True data with 17% of variance added correlated noise on predictors only	True data with 17% of variance added independent noise on predictors only
β_o	-7.89 (1.70)	-6.01 (2.25)	-5.71 (1.70)	-3.56 (3.35)	-9.16 (2.27)
β_1	11.35 (1.37)	10.13 (1.83)	10.03 (1.38)	14.20 (2.68)	13.05 (1.83)
β_2	0.022 (0.0007)	0.022 (0.0009)	0.022 (0.0007)	0.021 (0.0014)	0.021 (0.0011)
β_3	0.00013 (0.00004)	0.00008 (0.0006)	0.00010 (0.00004)	0.00015 (0.00008)	0.00022 (0.000070)
σ^2	146.2 (11.23)	254.02	150.1 (11.63)	530.2	170.8 (17.86)

We have added noise to the data in two different ways. In the first case we use correlated Gaussian noise as described in SHLOMO (2010) and in the second case we add independent Gaussian noise to each variable. In both cases, we add two levels of noise: the variance of noise is 0.05 and 0.17 times the variance of the corresponding variance of the true values for each variable.

We present the results of fitting equation (3.7) to each of the noisy datasets in Table 3.3 und 3.4. We note that for correlated noise the model is simply fitted to the observed data after a single draw. For independent additive noise we use the proposed procedures.

Table 3.3 presents the results of fitting equation (3.7) when no noise is added to the response variable just to the predictors and Table 3.4 presents the results when noise is also added to the response variable as well as to the predictors.

We see in Table 3.3 the negative effect of releasing one draw of correlated noise to users without providing the parameters of the noise distribution. When only some of the variables intended for the statistical modelling have added correlated random noise, users will obtain biased estimates with very large standard errors. This is not the case in Table 3.4 where all variables intended for the statistical modelling have correlated noise added

Table 3.4

Sugar cane farm data. Results of fitting equation (3.3) to 5% and 17% relative variance noisy data to both response variable and predictors. Standard errors in brackets.					
Parameter	True data with no added noise	True data with 5% of variance added correlated noise on all variables	True data with 5% of variance added independent noise on all variables	True data with 17% of variance added correlated noise on all variables	True data with 17% of variance added independent noise on all variables
β_o	-7.89 (1.70)	-7.33 (1.71)	-8.95 (2.88)	-7.56 (1.81)	-7.04 (4.39)
β_1	11.35 (1.37)	11.82 (1.41)	11.91 (2.26)	11.36 (1.43)	11.38 (3.64)
β_2	0.022 (0.0007)	0.022 (0.0007)	0.021 (0.0014)	0.022 (0.0007)	0.022 (0.0031)
β_3	0.00013 (0.00004)	0.00011 (0.0004)	0.00023 (0.000086)	0.00014 (0.0004)	0.00016 (0.00019)
σ^2	146.2 (11.23)	148.01	180.7 (28.32)	150.46	179.8 (73.3)

to them. In that case, we obtain similar parameter estimates and standard errors to the model run on the original true data. Given that it is generally unknown what types of analysis will be carried out on the released perturbed data, it is essential that users obtain the noise parameters and be able to analyse the data under measurement error using the proposed procedures. We see in Tables 3.3 and 3.4 under these procedures that we obtain unbiased parameter estimates taking into account the measurement error regardless of which variables have been perturbed. We also see some considerably increased standard errors as greater amounts of noise are added. For example, under the 17% of the variance of the true response variance for receipts, the variance of the response noise was set at 411 and this is nearly three times the true residual variance as estimated in Tables 3.3 and 3.4. This governs the size of the standard errors. Even when the variances are chosen to be just 5% of the variances of the true values, we still see an increase in the standard errors.

3.7 Discussion

The generality of our procedure is that it makes no assumptions about the final model to be fitted, which we point out can be a generalised linear model or a multilevel model with some or all of the variables perturbed, and the procedure allows a full range of exploratory

analyses. This is in contrast to procedures based upon the production of synthetic data simulated from estimates of the structure of the real data where exploratory analyses are recommended prior to the choice of a small number of models to be fitted to the real data within a secure environment. Such procedures not only rely upon good estimates of the real data structure, they also rely upon exploratory analyses converging on the appropriate set of final models, and this is by no means guaranteed.

For a response variable with added noise, the situation is more complex but for normally distributed responses we can carry out an analysis using the observed values to obtain consistent estimates. In this case we can obtain a consistent estimate for the residual variance by subtracting the (known) variance for the measurement errors in the response from the final estimated residual variance. The drawback, as illustrated in our second example on the sugar cane farms dataset, is that where the proportion of variance explained is high, this will lead to large standard errors. In this case we can either add less noise to any variables that a given data analyst wishes to use as responses, or no noise at all. This may have little effect on the disclosiveness and in practice therefore will often be acceptable. For categorical responses as with continuous responses, when data are released it may be acceptable to provide any variable(s) to be treated as a response with its true values or with just a small amount of added noise. Where a categorical response has added noise it is rounded to the nearest category value, for example 0 or 1 in the case of binary data, and these values are then used as responses.

In some cases we can improve on disclosiveness by first transforming one or more variables. This will often arise with skewed distributions with long tails where, for example, a logarithmic transformation will create fewer extreme values. In such cases the noise will be added to the transformed variable. In an analysis where the original variable is required in the model of interest, then for the likelihood term associated with the model of interest the back-transformed value of the proposed value will be used.

A key issue, of course, is the requirement that the data provider supplies to the data analyst the necessary parameters used to generate the noise. Since the degree of privacy established needs to be published and the degree of privacy established is a function of these parameters, in a weak sense aspects of the noise will become publicly available. This, however is not seriously disclosive since a guarantee of protecting confidentiality is only weakly informative about the noise parameter values themselves. Moreover, the noise information need only be released to an accredited data analyst under secure conditions,

and thus unavailable to a malicious attacker.

Finally, whilst our proposed procedure can provide general protection against attacks, a data provider may wish to guard against specific aspects of disclosiveness in the data, such as the presence of one or two very large influential data subjects where the use of truncation on the perturbed data may be adequate. So long as the relevant information is made available, the analyst typically will be able to take account of these additional constraints in the analysis. As discussed, it is possible to incorporate judicious groupings of data values within the estimation algorithm, and this allows the data provider some freedom in deciding where to coarsen particular data ranges.

4 The Use of Big Data from Twitter for Small Area Estimation of Households' Share of Food Consumption Expenditure in Italy

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4.1 Introduction

In the last years an increasing number of researchers and analysts around the world have investigated the value of using the so-called big data in socio-economic studies. As big data we refer to the huge amounts of digital information about human activities produced by a wide range of high-throughput tools and technologies. Indeed, GPS data, calls from mobile phones, internet searches and social networking are nowadays suggesting new approaches to conduct socio-economic studies. The main advantage of these data is their availability at an unprecedented spatial and temporal detail, which may enable to use them to infer some relevant socio-economic characteristics for entire nations as well as for microregions composed of just a few households (BLUMENSTOCK et al., 2015).

Recent studies have shown the value of mobile phone data to tackle problems related to economic development and humanitarian action. For example, EAGLE et al. (2010) showed that the diversity of individuals' relationships - as measured by the entropy of mobile phones' calls - is strongly correlated with the economic development of communities. BLUMENSTOCK et al. (2015) analyzed the power of anonymized data from mobile phone networks to predict the poverty and wealth of individual subscribers, as well as to create high-resolution maps of the geographic distribution of wealth in Africa. DECUYPER et al. (2014) assessed the suitability of indicators derived from mobile phone data as a proxy for food security indicators.

In resource-constrained environments where censuses and household surveys are rare, the approach used in the previous studies may create an option for gathering localized and timely information at a fraction of the cost of traditional methods.

In countries where official surveys are regularly conducted, big data represent a valu-

able resource also because they can be used to improve the accuracy of local estimates. MARCHETTI et al. (2015) suggested three approaches to use big data in synergy with small area estimation methods. These methods are currently used by many researchers to produce estimates of several socio-economic target indicators - for example, poverty indicators - for unplanned domains such as Provinces and Municipalities in Italy (LAU 1 and 2 in Eurostat nomenclature), as their knowledge can help in planning local policies and distributing welfare resources. Another approach to use big data in small area estimation was suggested by PORTER et al. (2014).

In this paper we focus on the use of data coming from the social network Twitter to investigate their potential in predicting the share of food consumption expenditure of Italian households at local level, following the second approach on the use of big data presented in MARCHETTI et al. (2015). We show here that the iHappy indicator derived from Twitter has a good predictive power for the share of expenditure that Italian households devote to the consumption of food and beverages - an indicator that can be used as a proxy to measure households' living conditions, as we better explain in the next section.

4.2 Description of the data

The Household Consumption Expenditure represents a crucial measure for assessing households' living conditions both at national or at more detailed geographical level (MARCHETTI and SECONDI, 2016). The primary source of data on households' expenditure in Italy is the Household Budget Survey (HBS) carried out annually by ISTAT. In 2012 the sample of the HBS was composed by approximately 28000 households. Data were collected on the basis of a two-stage sample design where the first stage were the municipalities (476 out of approximately 8000 in 2012) and the second stage were the households. The Regions (NUTS 2 level according to Eurostat) are the finest geographical level for which direct estimates of the target indicators are reliable. However, the knowledge of measures able to assess households' living conditions and well-being at a more detailed geographical level is often crucial, since this knowledge can for example enable policy makers in planning local policies aiming at reducing poverty and social exclusion (GIUSTI et al., 2016).

Using small area methodologies, MARCHETTI and SECONDI (2016) produced reliable estimates of the monthly equivalised¹ Household Consumption Expenditure in Italian provin-

¹ The equivalence scale is the Carbonaro scale used by ISTAT, according to which the expenditure of a family is divided by a specific coefficient depending on the household size (for example equal to 0.66

ces in 2012, also taking into account the local differences in the prices by using Purchasing Power Parities (PPPs).

Using the same data, the households' consumption expenditure can be classified into food (and beverages) and non food expenditure. The share of total expenditure that an household dedicate to food items is an important indicator of the household living conditions: at risk of poverty households usually spend an higher share of their total expenditure on food with respect to the other households, with a lower impact of the share of expenditure dedicated to other resources and commodities (LECHENE, 2000, REGMI et al., 2001, DEATON, 2003, MEYER and SULLIVAN, 2003, BARIGOZZI et al., 2009). As we are interested in the estimation of the share of food consumption at a local level, we resort to the small area methodologies.

Small area methods require auxiliary information able to predict the response variable, as we better explain in section 4.3. In our case we need auxiliary variables able to predict households' share of food consumption expenditure in 2012 for the 110 Italian provinces. As possible sources of auxiliary variables we use data coming from the Population and Housing Census 2011 and from the Survey² on Social Actions and Services on Single and Associates Municipalities 2012.

From the Population Census we collected information at provincial level such as the number of households, the average households' size, the tenure status, the female-headed households quota. As the target variable of our analysis can be considered as a proxy of the households' living conditions, we also considered as valuable source of auxiliary information the expenditure that Italian municipalities made in 2012 for interventions of social protection. These interventions includes the costs information on local welfare policies, such as services, benefits and transfers directed to households with children, old-age persons, poor and social excluded persons, immigrants.

Besides these sources of official statistics, we also considered as a potential source of auxiliary information big data from Twitter, following the second approach for the joint use of big data and small area methods presented in MARCHETTI et al. (2015). In particular, we considered here as potential covariate for our small area working models the iHappy

for a household with 1 member, 1.33 for a household with 3 members and up to 2.40 for a household with 7 members or more). In this way the expenditures of households of any size can be directly compared with those of households composed by two members.

² This survey is a census survey, although some nonresponses can occur. Here we ignore the nonresponses and we use these data as census data.

indicator referring to the year 2012. The iHappy indicator is made available every year since 2012 for all the 110 Italian provinces on the Opinion Analytics platform *Voices from the Blogs*. The iHappy indicator referring to the year 2012 was computed by collecting and coding more than 43 millions of tweets posted on a daily basis in all the Italian provinces. The words and emoticons of the tweets were classified using a training set in two categories: “happy” and “unhappy”, together with a residual class “other”. Then, CURINI et al. (2015) derived the frequency distribution of the happy and unhappy tweets in the entire population. The iHappy indicator was then computed for each Italian province as the percentage ratio of the number of happy tweets to the sum of happy and unhappy tweets. The overall average of the iHappy indicator in 2012 was equal to 44.5%, with a minimum value of 35.1% for Oristano and a maximum value of 56.6% for Sassari, both provinces of the Sardinia region. Indeed, the spatial variability of the iHappy values was rather high, as it is evident from the “emotional map” of Figure 4.3b.

CURINI et al. (2015) also performed some econometric analysis to investigate the determinants of Italians’ happiness, as measured by the iHappy indicator - using available data. They considered some static variables such as the overall quality of institutions, that seemed to matter only marginally in affecting the average level of happiness of the Italian provinces. On the contrary, meteorological variables and events related to specific days, such as the variability of the spread between German and Italian Bonds or the payday, resulted to have the largest impact. Thus, in a certain sense the iHappy indicator can be considered as a “thermometer of emotional mood” of Italian Provinces.

In the present work we are not interested in an econometric approach to find out the factors influencing the target variable at local level. We focus instead on the predictive power that the iHappy indicator may have at provincial level as covariate in an operational model to estimate the outcome. Thus, our research question is: can the iHappy indicator be a good covariate in a small area model for the estimation of the share of food consumption expenditure of Italian households? In the next sections we present the methodologies and the results of our analyses aiming at investigating this question.

4.3 The Fay-Herriot model for small area estimation

Data obtained from surveys are often used to estimate characteristics for subsets of the survey population. If the sample from a subset is small, then a traditional design-based survey estimator can have unacceptably large variance. These subsets has been defined as

small areas (RAO and MOLINA, 2015).

In literature a wide range of methods have been used for obtaining reliable small-area estimates (PFEFFERMANN, 2013a, RAO and MOLINA, 2015), mostly model-based estimators, which can be classified into area- and unit-level models.

Model-based estimators are derived from small area models linking the study variable and the auxiliary information. These models are often based on random area-specific effects that account for between area variation beyond that explained by auxiliary variables included in the model. Area- (or aggregate-) level models relate small area direct estimates to area-specific auxiliary variables, unit-level models relate the unit values of a study variable to unit-specific auxiliary variables. Both area- and unit-level model-based estimators have been extended to account for time-series and spatial information (RAO and MOLINA, 2015). In the family of unit-level models an alternative (frequentist) approach to the traditional link model – based on random area-specific effects – has been proposed in literature by CHAMBERS and TZAVIDIS (2006) and TZAVIDIS et al. (2010), and it is based on M-quantile models. Applications of this last approach can be found in GIUSTI et al. (2012) and PRATESI et al. (2012). For a review of the small area methods applied to the analysis of poverty data see also PRATESI (2016).

In this study the available data allow us to rely only on area-level models. In addition, we do not have time-series data and the spatial correlation of the target direct estimates is low. So our choice falls on the FAY and HERRIOT (1979) estimator (FH). In what follows a short description of the method is given.

Let us assume that there are m small areas of interest and that θ_i represents the target parameter of the area i , such as a mean, a proportion or a percentile. A survey provides a direct estimator $\hat{\theta}_i^{dir}$ of θ_i for some or all of the small areas. As usual, we assume that under the sampling design $E[\hat{\theta}_i^{dir}] = \theta_i$. A p -vector X_i contains the auxiliary data sources of population characteristics for area i .

Let us assume that the auxiliary variables X_i are known exactly. The FH model is as follows

$$\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} = X_i^T \beta + u_i + e_i \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (4.1)$$

where $u_i \stackrel{iid}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_u^2)$, $i = 1, \dots, m$ are the model errors and $e_i \stackrel{ind}{\sim} N(0, \psi_i^2)$, $i = 1 \dots, m$ are the design errors, with e_i independent from u_j for all i and j . It is assumed that the

quantity of interest in area i is $\theta_i = \mathbf{X}_i^T \beta + u_i$.

Under the assumption of normality of both the errors (model and sampling design), the best linear unbiased predictor of θ_i is

$$\tilde{\theta}_i^{FH} = \gamma_i \hat{\theta}_i^{dir} + (1 - \gamma_i) \mathbf{X}_i^T \tilde{\beta}, \quad \gamma_i = \frac{\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_u^2 + \psi_i^2}, \quad (4.2)$$

where $\tilde{\beta}$ is the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator of β . The predictor $\tilde{\theta}_i^{FH}$ is a convex combination of the direct estimator $\hat{\theta}_i^{dir}$ and of the predicted value $\mathbf{X}_i^T \tilde{\beta}$ from the regression model. The extent to which it depends on the the direct estimator or on the predicted value for the area is determined by γ_i and hence by the relative sizes of the model error variance σ_u^2 and the sampling error variance ψ_i^2 .

According to the theory of small area estimation (RAO and MOLINA, 2015), the parameters β and σ_u^2 are unknown and must be estimated, while ψ_i^2 is assumed to be known. The estimators of the ψ_i^2 s are often smoothed, and the smoothed estimators are treated as if they were the true sampling variances (DATTA et al., 2005).

Estimators of β and σ_u^2 can be obtained using the restricted maximum likelihood from the marginal distribution $\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} \sim N(\mathbf{X}_i^T \beta, \sigma_u^2 + \psi_i^2)$ (RAO, 2003, see paragraph 6.2.4 page 100). By plugging in the estimates of β and σ_u^2 into equation equation (4.2) we obtain the empirical best linear unbiased predictor

$$\hat{\theta}_i^{FH} = \hat{\gamma}_i \hat{\theta}_i^{dir} + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i) \mathbf{X}_i^T \hat{\beta}, \quad \hat{\gamma}_i = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_u^2}{\hat{\sigma}_u^2 + \psi_i^2}. \quad (4.3)$$

The terms $\hat{\gamma}_i$ are commonly known as *shrinkage* factors.

When all the parameters (σ_u^2, β) are known the mean squared error (MSE) of the estimator equation (4.2) is

$$MSE(\tilde{\theta}_i^{FH}) = E[(\tilde{\theta}_i^{FH} - \theta_i)^2] = \gamma_i \psi_i^2 = \mathbf{g}_{1i}. \quad (4.4)$$

When the parameters in equation (4.2) are estimated we obtain the estimator equation (4.3) that has the following MSE

$$\begin{aligned} MSE(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH}) &= \gamma_i \psi_i^2 + (1 - \gamma_i)^2 \mathbf{X}_i^T V(\hat{\beta}) \mathbf{X}_i + \psi_i^4 (\psi_i^2 + \sigma_u^2)^{-3} V(\hat{\sigma}_u^2) \\ &= \mathbf{g}_{1i} + \mathbf{g}_{2i} + \mathbf{g}_{3i}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

where \mathbf{g}_{2i} is the contribution to the MSE from estimating β and \mathbf{g}_{3i} is the contribution

to the MSE from estimating σ_u^2 . In equation (4.5) $V(\hat{\beta})$ and $V(\hat{\sigma}_u^2)$ are the asymptotic variances of an estimator $\hat{\beta}$ of β and an estimator $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$ of σ_u^2 , respectively. An estimator of equation (4.5) is as follows

$$mse(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH}) = \hat{g}_{1i} + \hat{g}_{2i} + 2\hat{g}_{3i}, \quad (4.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } \hat{g}_{1i} &= \hat{\gamma}_i \psi_i^2, \\ \hat{g}_{2i} &= (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i)^2 X_i^T \left[\sum_{i=1}^m X_i X_i^T / (\psi_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_u^2) \right]^{-1} X_i \quad \text{and} \\ \hat{g}_{3i} &= \psi_i^4 (\psi_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_u^2)^{-3} 2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^m 1 / (\hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \psi_i^2)^2 \right]^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

More details concerning analytic MSE estimation for area level model can be found in RAO and MOLINA (2015), DATTA and LAHIRI (2000), PRASAD and RAO (1990a).

Usually, for $M - m$ out of sample areas, estimates are obtained using a regression-synthetic estimator

$$\hat{\theta}_l^{syn} = X_l^T \hat{\beta}, \quad (4.7)$$

where X_l , $l = m + 1, \dots, M$, is the vector of auxiliary variables for the out of sample area l . The MSE of $\hat{\theta}_l^{syn}$ is given by

$$MSE(\hat{\theta}_l^{syn}) = \sigma_u^2 + X_l^T \left[\sum_{i=1}^m X_i X_i^T / (\psi_i^2 + \sigma_u^2) \right]^{-1} X_l + o(m^{-1}).$$

A second order unbiased MSE estimator under the REML estimation of σ_u^2 is given by

$$mse(\hat{\theta}_l^{syn}) = \hat{\sigma}_u^2 + X_l^T \left[\sum_{i=1}^m X_i X_i^T / (\psi_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_u^2) \right]^{-1} X_l. \quad (4.8)$$

4.4 Estimates of the share of food consumption in the Italian provinces *with* and *without* Twitter data

In this section we show that the use of Twitter data can improve the precision of the Share of Food Consumption Expenditure (SFCE) estimates in the Italian provinces, obtained using small area methods. As discussed in section 4.2, the HBS is designed to obtain reliable estimates at a regional level in Italy. Direct estimates at a finer geographical level, such as the province level, can have a too large coefficient of variation and can

be considered unreliable. Small area estimation methods have been recognized as a cost effective solution to overcome to this problem. As we have already noticed, the availability of auxiliary information at provincial level and not at unit-level (household-level) restricts our choice to the area-level approach. Moreover, the low spatial autocorrelation of the SFCE at provincial level and the absence of time-series data lead us to the use of the FH estimator (4.3), described in section 4.3.

First, we estimated the SFCE at provincial level using the FH model (4.1) selecting the more predictive variables among the data described in section 4.2 without considering the iHappy variable, the one computed using Twitter 2012 data. In this way we obtained a reduction in MSE in all the provinces. Second, we added the iHappy variable to the other auxiliary variables and we estimated the SFCE again. If the iHappy variable is linearly correlated with the SFCE and this relation is not yet explained by the other auxiliary variables, then we expect a better performance in terms of MSE when using iHappy. We will show that the results obtained support this expectation.

Under both models - with and without the iHappy indicator - the target variable, the SFCE, was obtained from the HBS 2012 survey as the ratio between the consumption expenditure for food (including beverages) and the total consumption expenditure. Its direct estimate at provincial level was obtained using the HORVITZ and THOMPSON (1952) expansion estimator,

$$\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} y_{ij} w_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{ij}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (4.9)$$

where the survey weights w_{ij} , which are computed by ISTAT, are the inverse of the inclusion probability of household j in area i , calibrated according to known totals in the population and adjusted for the non-response. In (4.9) y_{ij} is the SFCE for household j in area i . In 2012 the Italian provinces were 110 in total. However, in 2012 no HBS sample data were available for the province of Enna (Sicily) therefore it was not possible to obtain a direct estimate for this province, so we computed a synthetic estimator given that we know the auxiliary data for this province.

The selected auxiliary variables for the model without the iHappy variable are the share of owners of the house x_1 , the share of households lead by a female x_2 , the per-household local government expenses to support several categories of citizens, households with children (x_3), old-aged persons (x_4), immigrants (x_5), at risk of poverty persons (x_6), services to

families³ (x_7). So let $X_i = [1, x_{1i}, x_{2i}, x_{3i}, x_{4i}, x_{5i}, x_{6i}, x_{7i}]^T$ be the design p -vector for model (4.1) for the area i , where x_{ki} , $k = 0, \dots, p = 7$, $i = 1, \dots, m$, is the value of the k th auxiliary variable in area i (with $x_{0i} = 1$).

In some recent works (JIANG et al., 2001, CORDERO et al., 2016) the authors do not model the raw proportions but an arcsin square-root transformation of the proportions. This transformation is used to stabilize the variance and to guarantee that the predictions fall in the space $[0, 1]$. However, there are works where the raw proportions are modeled, for example see RAO and MOLINA (2015, Example 6.1.4), HIDIROGLOU et al. (2007) and SALVATI et al. (2013). In our work we chose to model the raw proportions given that the area-level random errors can be considered normally distributed and the estimates are all in the range $0 - 1$ (and similar to the point estimates).

The FH model without the iHappy variable is then $\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} = X_i^T \beta + u_i + e_i$. Estimates of β and σ_u^2 were obtained under the Normality assumptions made in section 4.3 using the restricted maximum likelihood (REML), while $\psi_i^2 = (\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (w_{ij}^2 - w_{ij}) y_{ij}^2) / (\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{ij})^2$. From the analysis of $\hat{u}_i = \hat{\gamma}(\hat{\theta}_i^{Dir} - X^T \hat{\beta})$, the Normality assumption seems reasonable. Indeed, the SHAPIRO and WILK (1965) Normality test is equal to 0.978 with a p -value of 0.063. In figure 4.1a it is represented a non-parametric density estimate with 95% confidence interval bands (obtained according to BOWMAN et al. (1998)) of \hat{u}_i with a superimposed Normal density obtained from the data. The Normal curve falls inside the confidence bands, giving us another evidence that the Normality assumption is reasonable.

To check the hypothesis that big data can help to increase the precision of the small area estimates - if used as auxiliary variables - we added the iHappy variable (x_8), obtained from the analysis of Twitter data as explained in section 4.2, to the set of the selected auxiliary variables (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_7). Let $Z_i = [X_i, x_{8i}]^T$, where x_{8i} is the iHappy value for area i . The FH model is $\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} = Z_i^T \beta^{BD} + u_i^{BD} + e_i^{BD}$, where the superscript BD refers to parameters under the model that makes use of big data (the Twitter data). Point and mse estimates are then obtained according to the methodology described in section 4.3 (replacing X_i by Z_i).

In both the models - with and without iHappy variable - we selected the auxiliary variables using a step-wise procedure based on AIC (HASTIE and PREGIBON, 1992). The selected variables show a negative linear correlation with the target that range from -0.130 to

³ Intended as households consisting of two or more individuals who are related by birth, marriage or adoption, although they also may include other unrelated people.

−0.509 (table 4.1). The negative correlations were expected for all the variable, but the share of households lead by a female. In general, in Italy, households lead by a female are positively correlated with poverty indexes and deprivation variables. However, we can suppose that the households lead by a female are associated with a reduction of the household size, so the expenses in food and beverages decreases so that to increase the SFCE. This hypothesis is supported by a linear correlation between the share of the households lead by a female and the household size equal to −0.857. As done for the model

Table 4.1: Linear correlation (ρ) between the selected auxiliary variables for the FH model and the SFCE variable.

	ρ
iHappy	−0.350
Share of owners of the house	−0.258
Share of household lead by female	−0.497
Expenses for household with children	−0.500
Expenses for old-aged persons	−0.332
Expenses for immigrants	−0.335
Expenses for at risk of poverty persons	−0.130
Expenses for services to families	−0.509

without iHappy variable, we estimated β^{BD} and σ_u^{BD} under the Normality assumptions made in section 4.3 using the REML (ψ 's remain unchanged). The SHAPIRO and WILK (1965) Normality test for \hat{u}_i^{BD} s is equal to 0.980 with a p -value of 0.107. Figure 4.1b represents a non-parametric density estimate with 95% confidence interval bands of \hat{u}_i^{BD} with a superimposed Normal density estimated from the data. The Normal curve falls inside the confidence bands giving us another evidence that the Normality assumption is reasonably.

The regression parameters estimated for both the models - with and without iHappy - are showed in table 4.2. The β s obtained under the two models are similar, the introduction of the iHappy variable in the FH model does not change significantly the model, it just add predictive power to it. The parameter σ_u is estimated equal to 0.020 for the model without iHappy and to 0.019 for the model with iHappy. To verify the null hypothesis that $\sigma_u^2 = 0$, we used the test proposed by DATTA et al. (2011), with

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \psi_i^{-2} (\hat{\theta}_i^{dir} - Z_i^T \hat{\beta}_{wls})^2 = T \sim \chi_{m-p}^2 \text{ under } H_0,$$

Figure 4.1: Non-parametric density estimate with 95% confidence interval bands of \hat{u}_i (4.1a) and \hat{u}_i^{BD} (4.1b) with a superimposed Normal density.

Table 4.2: Regression parameters of the FH model with and without the iHappy variable.

	$\hat{\beta}^{BD}$	p-value ^{BD}	$\hat{\beta}$	p-value
Intercept	0.7165	0.0000	0.6446	0.0000
iHappy2012	-0.0019	0.0067	-	-
Share of owners of the house	-0.0038	0.0000	-0.0039	0.0000
Share of household lead by female	-0.3164	0.0009	-0.3222	0.0012
Expenses for household with children	-0.0001	0.2121	-0.0002	0.0513
Expenses for old-aged persons	-0.0001	0.0123	-0.0001	0.0280
Expenses for immigrants	-0.0013	0.0003	-0.0013	0.0009
Expenses for at risk of poverty persons	0.0006	0.0009	0.0007	0.0006
Expenses for services to families	-0.0005	0.0460	-0.0006	0.0246

where $\hat{\beta}_{wls} = (\sum_{i=1}^m \psi_i^{-2} Z_i Z_i^T)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^m \psi_i^{-2} Z_i \hat{\theta}_i^{dir}$ is the weighted least square estimator of β under the null hypothesis. If $T \geq \chi_{m-p, \alpha}^2$ - where $\chi_{m-p, \alpha}^2$ is the upper α -point of χ_{m-p}^2 - we reject the null hypothesis $\sigma_u^2 = 0$, as is in our application.

It is important to underline that the iHappy indicator is based on self-selected data, the Twitter data. However, in this application we are not able to treat the self-selection bias due to lack of information. Thus, we assume that the self-selection is negligible⁴. Moreover, the iHappy indicator can be affected by measurement error, since not any “happy tweet” corresponds to a “happy perso”. As it concerns the measurement error, one could apply the area level model proposed by YBARRA and LOHR (2008), which modify the FH model

⁴ In other social studies content analysis of the texts posted using social network seems to provide acceptable predictions of the behavior of the whole population, not only of those using Twitter. Particularly, the debate is lively on the electoral predictions (CERON et al., 2015).

by taking into account the random error in the auxiliary variables - i.e. when the auxiliary variables come from a survey. However, in our application the MSE of the iHappy is small, due to the very large sample size (43 millions of tweets), so that the model proposed by YBARRA and LOHR (2008) approximately corresponds to the traditional FH model.

Results on the SFCE estimates are summarized in table 4.3. From this table we can see that point estimates are very similar to each other, this is a desired result. The unique exception is for the FH estimates (with and without iHappy variable) in the highest quantiles where there is a known shrinkage effect of the FH estimator. For what concerns the gain in terms of reduction of *rmse* (estimated root mean squared error) the results are as desired. Using the FH estimator (4.3) with the set of auxiliary variables X_i s the *rmse* is reduced in all the provinces. The reduction of the *rmse* is on average about 30% with a 25% of provinces where the reduction is at least about 40%, as shown in table 4.3. Moreover, using also the iHappy variable the reduction of the *rmse* goes from about 30% to about 32% with an average gain of 2%. A clearer picture of the gain in precision due to the introduction of the iHappy variable in the FH model can be seen in the last line of table 4.3, which shows the ratio between the *rmse* of the FH estimator that use the iHappy variable ($\hat{\theta}_i^{FH.BD}$) and the FH estimator that does not use the iHappy variable ($\hat{\theta}_i^{FH}$). There is a gain in all the areas, but one where we observe a loss of 0.5%. The gain goes from about 2% up to about 7%. Given that the small area estimates obtained without the use of the iHappy variable show a remarkable gain in terms of reduction of *mse*, the further reduction of the *mse* due to the introduction of the iHappy variable in the model is a very good result. This is particularly important also because the iHappy variable can be computed every year, while updated census information on the population is not always available.

Table 4.3: Summary of point estimates of SFCE for 109 Italian provinces obtained using direct and small area estimators (without iHappy $\hat{\theta}_i^{FH}$ and with iHappy $\hat{\theta}_i^{FH.BD}$), and summary of the ratios between *rmse*s of direct estimates and *rmse*s of small area estimates with and without iHappy auxiliary variable.

	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
$\hat{\theta}_i^{Dir}(\%)$	15.38	19.44	21.34	22.45	25.56	35.42
$\hat{\theta}_i^{FH}(\%)$	15.37	19.70	21.60	22.19	24.47	29.91
$\hat{\theta}_i^{FH.BD}(\%)$	15.44	19.68	21.64	22.17	24.65	29.55
$rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH})/rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{Dir})(\%)$	19.79	60.66	74.90	70.38	82.16	99.39
$rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH.BD})/rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{Dir})(\%)$	18.44	58.29	72.37	68.49	80.35	99.43
$rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH.BD})/rmse(\hat{\theta}_i^{FH})(\%)$	93.18	95.73	97.33	97.02	98.22	100.50

The reduction of the mse obtained introducing the iHappy variable is graphically represented by the plot in figure 4.2. Here, we contrast the mse of the FH estimates obtained with and without the iHappy variable. The gain is present in all the areas, but one.

Figure 4.2: mse of the FH estimates obtained with (x axis) and without (y axis) the iHappy variable.

In order to obtain a clearer picture of the estimates across the country, we mapped them out in figure 4.3. In the same figure we contrast our estimates with the map of the iHappy variable to show the relationship between the two variables. The SFCE point estimate for the out of sample province of Enna has been computed using the regression synthetic estimator (4.7), while its MSE has been obtained using (4.8). In particular, the estimated SFCE for the province of Enna is 25.29% with an rmse of 1.98%. These results seem plausible according to the estimates obtained for the neighbors provinces.

As already discussed in section 4.2, the SFCE can act as a proxy to measure the living conditions in most of developed and developing countries. In Italy the SFCE is 22.2% at national level, showing that in average the consumption of food does not represent a large amount on total expenses for consumption. At provincial level, as shown in table 4.3, the SFCE varies between 15.44% (Ravenna, central Italy) and 29.55% (Caserta, southern Italy), so there is evidence of spatial heterogeneity of the indicator. About a quarter of the provinces has an SFCE greater than or equal to 25%. All these provinces are in the southern part of Italy. Nine provinces have a estimated SFCE that is below 18%, five of

Figure 4.3: Map of the FH estimates of the SFCE (4.3a) and map of the iHappy variable for 110 provinces in Italy (4.3b). In both the maps a darker color corresponds to a better situation.

these provinces are in the central part and the other four are in the northern part of Italy. All the provinces in the lowest quartile are in the central or northern part of Italy. These results confirm the well known Italian north-south divide concerning the socio-economic indicators.

4.5 Conclusions

In the era of data deluge there are many new sources of data tracking human behavior. In this paper we focused on the iHappy indicator obtained from the analysis of Twitter data. The data consist of all the geo-referenced tweets posted in 2012 in the Italian provinces, classified by CURINI et al. (2015) as the percentage of happy tweets to the total of tweets at provincial level.

In our analysis the iHappy indicator resulted a good additional covariate to predict households' SFCE, given the net influence of other covariates characterizing the provinces, such as the tenure status of the house, the gender of the head of the households, the level of the expenses of the local government to support vulnerable groups.

In Italy the SFCE shows a territorial variability that mimics that of many socio-economic indicators: in 2014 the north-eastern and north-western part of Italy had the lowest level

of SFCE (respectively 15.7% and 15.5%) while the southern part (islands included) had the highest (21%) (see ISTAT (2015)). This north-south divide is evident also from the territorial distribution of the iHappy indicator, with few exceptions (some provinces of Sardinia, Puglia and Sicily). Given that the iHappy indicator can be considered as a “thermometer of emotional mood” of Italian households, it would be interesting to test its predictive power to estimate the trend and the changes in households’ SFCE: however, at the moment this task is not achievable due to the cross-sectional availability of the HBS data we used to measure the SFCE.

Concluding, the iHappy indicator on happiness can provide useful covariates on yearly bases, free of charge and broken by provinces. It comes affected by self-selection bias and measurement error. In this application we assumed that the self-selection is negligible and that the measurement error appears to be a minor issue.

In the paper we have not considered issues related to Information Communication Technology (ICT) since we used the iHappy indicator as computed by CURINI et al. (2015). However, the heterogeneity, lack of structure (requiring important work to prepare the data for statistical production), and volume (which hampers the use of standard statistical tools) of the Twitter data are a challenge to exploit all the potentialities they have.

The above mentioned issues can be a limitation for the purpose of adopting Twitter data as current and not episodic sources of auxiliary information in small area methods. Here we limit to remark that: i) some issues share statistical methodological and IT aspects, as those linked to the application of the content analysis to the huge amount of considered tweets; ii) technological issues are important but probably easier to be solved than statistical and IT methodological issues, as some solutions are already on the market.

In few words, what is considered *big* today is going to be considered normal tomorrow. What it is necessary is the development of joint skills to treat the data and to envision their usage in statistical models, as we did in the small area estimation models. Hence, the skills for dealing with statistical models should come from the two worlds, by the data scientist profile.

5 Use of New Data & Non-Probability Sampling

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5.1 Introduction

Nowadays, many researchers have expressed their concerns about the accuracy of classic survey data. Especially when it comes to research on subgroups, be they of regional or demographic nature, this is a major issue. As one possible remedy, the better use of new data sources, such as Big Data or web data, are frequently proposed (cf. SZEKÉR and VAN GYES, 2015 and section 4 of this report).

Such new data sources, however, bring their own methodological challenges. At best, they can be seen as some form of non-probability sampling. Even though non-random samples and Big Data are increasingly being used in research, a common framework for sampling and inference with regard to non-probability sampling does not yet exist. Hence, different ways of compensating the possible selectivity of non-representative data have to be investigated and evaluated (cf. LENAU et al., 2016).

Starting from classical sampling theory, the major issues regarding non-probability samples are briefly presented in this section. Two different approaches are examined and evaluated: post-stratification and propensity weights. Both are used on either information about multivariate or marginal distributions regarding auxiliary variables from outside the sample.

5.2 Classical design-based estimation

In traditional (probability) sampling theory, following an inductive logic, statistical inference is made by linking the (not entirely known) population of interest to observed sample data in probabilistic terms. The link between a sample and the population of interest are the selection probabilities. The vast theoretical framework regarding design-based inference in random samples assumes the selection process to be known and under the control of the researcher. Assuming all inclusion probabilities of every population entity i to be in a sample \mathcal{S} , $\pi_i = P(i \in \mathcal{S})$ to be known and greater than zero, the (not entirely known) population of interest is linked to observed sample data in probabilistic terms need to be

known. The inverses of $w_i = \frac{1}{\pi_i}$ are called sampling weights. Furthermore, the probability of two entities i and j being in the sample simultaneously (second order inclusion probability) $\pi_{ij} = P(i \in \mathcal{S} \cap j \in \mathcal{S})$ need to be known for computing the sampling errors in design-based inference (cf. COCHRAN, 1963; WOLTER, 2007).

5.3 Issues when estimating from non-probability samples

In non-probability sampling, there are two major issues related to these assumptions.

1. Information about the sampling process may be missing.
2. As coverage of the target population of interest is not assured, non-random samples may be subject to lacking representativity and selection bias.

Both difficulties may, for example, result from self-selection in online surveys or due non-response. As the sampling process is either not (fully) controlled and known by the researcher or simply not random, the consequences are that the inclusion probabilities do not fulfil the requirements stated in section 5.2. They are either not known, or not strictly positive for all population entities. The likewise unknown second order inclusion probabilities are only an issue if the selection of two entities is not independent, since otherwise

$$\pi_{ij} = \begin{cases} \pi_i & , \quad i = j \\ \pi_i \cdot \pi_j & , \quad i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

The methods presented in the following section thus base on two assumptions in estimating from non-probability samples:

1. Coverage of the target population ($\pi_i > 0 \forall i$) is constituted
and
2. there is a suitable approximation at least for the first-order design-weights.

If those are fulfilled, estimation from non-probability samples might be done in a way similar to classical design-based estimation.

5.4 Approaches to compensate selectivity of non-probability sampling

Consequently, we are looking for a vector $w^\nu = (w_1, \dots, w_{n^\nu})^\top$ of pseudo-design-weights for each observation of the non-probability sample \mathcal{S}^ν of size n^ν . Suppose we have a set of variables \mathbf{X} , which are collected in the non-probability sample and for which we also have additional external information, denoted by \mathbf{X}^ρ . This can be the case if we have a reference sample, census information or administrative data. This external information can be used to reduce the possible bias due to selectivity in non-probability samples. This information does *not necessarily have to be on unit level*. In fact, depending on the different methods which are presented below, measures of multivariate or even marginal distributions are sufficient. For a profound presentation of the approaches, we nevertheless start with the unit level auxiliary variables. Having k auxiliary variables with n^ρ observations in our reference sample \mathcal{S}^ρ , the auxiliary variables are

$$\mathbf{X}^\rho = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11}^\rho & \cdots & x_{1k}^\rho \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{n^\rho 1}^\rho & \cdots & x_{n^\rho k}^\rho \end{bmatrix}$$

Analogously, the same k auxiliary variables are known for the n observations in the non-probability sample

$$\mathbf{X}^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11}^\nu & \cdots & x_{1k}^\nu \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{n^\nu 1}^\nu & \cdots & x_{n^\nu k}^\nu \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that dummy variables are used to represent each category in case of categorical variables. As the auxiliary variables can possibly come from another sample, we further use sampling weights $w^\rho = (w_{1,\rho}, \dots, w_{n^\rho,\rho})^\top$. In cases where no weighting is required (e.g. full censuses), they are simply all one.

There are two trends in using this external information to compensate for the possible selectivity of non-probability samples which we want to evaluate here. The first one is calibration, where the distribution of the sample \mathbf{X} -Variables is adjusted to that of the reference data. The second one is modelling of the response process by propensity scores, as a attempt to estimate the unknown inclusion probabilities of the non-probability sample.

5.4.1 Adjusting the auxiliary variable distribution: Calibration

In calibration, certain characteristics of the sample are calibrated to the corresponding values of the reference data. This is commonly done when population information is available for one or more variables. These weights can be determined by using the auxiliary variables \mathbf{X}^ρ and weights w^ρ by adjusting the weighted distribution of \mathbf{X}^ν to that of \mathbf{X}^ρ . First, we need a function to normalize the original weights w to sum to one:

$$g(w) = \frac{w}{\|w\|_1} \quad (5.2)$$

The estimated first moments (means) of the variables \mathbf{X} are then given by

$$\hat{\mu}_1(\mathbf{X}, w) = (g(w))^\top \mathbf{X} \quad (5.3)$$

The second moments (means of the products of the variables) of \mathbf{X} are estimated by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mu}_2(\mathbf{X}, w) &= \mathbf{X}^\top \mathbf{W} \mathbf{X} \quad , \quad \text{where} \\ \mathbf{W} &= \text{diag}(g(w)) \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

In case of only dummy variables in \mathbf{X} , this second moment contains the cross-table of all variables, including the first moments.

When determining the weights, calibrating the first moments (means) of the \mathbf{X}^ν -Variables to those of \mathbf{X}^ρ results in the calibration constraint

$$\hat{\mu}_1(\mathbf{X}^\nu, w^\nu) \stackrel{!}{=} \hat{\mu}_1(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho) \quad (5.5)$$

Analogously, the calibration constraint for the second moments is

$$\hat{\mu}_2(\mathbf{X}^\nu, w^\nu) \stackrel{!}{=} \hat{\mu}_2(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho) \quad (5.6)$$

(cf. MÜNNICH et al., 2012; DEVILLE and SÄRNDAL, 1992; SÄRNDAL et al., 1992). One example of this approach is post-stratification, where all auxiliary variables are of categorical nature. In the following, post-stratification is depicted as example for calibration, as there is an analytical solution for the weights fulfilling equation 5.5 or 5.6 in this case. This is not (generally) the case when including continuous variables.

Post-stratification weights fulfilling equation 5.5 can be computed by

$$w_{\nu,1}(\mathbf{X}^\rho) = \hat{\mu}_1(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho) \mathbf{X}^{\nu+} \quad , \quad (5.7)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^{\nu+}$ is the pseudoinverse of \mathbf{X}^{ν} .

Equation 5.6 is fulfilled by weights computed by

$$\begin{aligned} w_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}^{\rho}) &= 0.5 \cdot \left(\text{diag}(\mathbf{X}^{\nu} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{X}^{\nu\top}) - (\mathbf{X}^{\nu} \text{diag}(\mathbf{C})) \right) \\ \mathbf{C} &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^{\rho}, w^{\rho}) \oslash \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^{\nu}, \mathbf{1}_n) \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

where $\mathbf{1}_n$ is a $n \times 1$ vector of ones and \oslash is the Hadamard (element-wise) division. Note that to avoid undefined results, $\frac{z}{0} \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \forall z$ must be defined for this operation.

Equation 5.8 fulfils constraints 5.5 and 5.6, while 5.7 only considers 5.5. Nevertheless, it is still important to consider both, as they are based on different information about the auxiliary variables: While equation 5.7 can be used knowing only marginal counts of the reference data, equation 5.8 requires the complete cross-tabulation of \mathbf{X}^{ρ} to be known. Thus, the latter uses more auxiliary information than the first.

5.4.2 Estimated inclusion probabilities: Response propensities

While calibration uses the distribution of \mathbf{X}^{ρ} for weighting, another approach is to estimate the probability of element i being in the non-probability-sample \mathcal{S}^{ν} conditional $x_i = (x_{11}^{\nu}, \dots, x_{1k}^{\nu})^{\top}$.

Starting with the inclusion indicator

$$R_i = \mathbb{I}(i \in \mathcal{S}^{\nu}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad i \in \mathcal{S}^{\nu} \\ 0 & , \quad \text{else} \quad , \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

we are looking for an approximation for $\pi_i = P(i \in \mathcal{S}^{\nu}) = E(R_i = 1)$. Assuming that

$$R_i | x_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_i) \quad , \quad (5.10)$$

$\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_{n^{\nu}})^{\top}$ can be estimated by

$$\hat{\pi}_i = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + x_i^{\nu\top} \beta))} \quad . \quad (5.11)$$

Coefficients β_0 and β are estimates from a logistic regression model which can be obtained by maximising the log-likelihood

$$\log(\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{X}^{\nu}, \hat{\pi})) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(\hat{\pi}_i) + \log(1 - \hat{\pi}_i) \cdot \left(\frac{T_i - t_i}{t_i} \right) \quad , \quad (5.12)$$

where the number of elements in \mathcal{S}^ν having the respective combination of \mathbf{X} -variables is given by

$$\begin{aligned} t &= (t_1, \dots, t_{n^\nu})^\top \\ &= 0.5 \cdot n^\nu \cdot \left(\text{diag} \left(\mathbf{X}^\nu \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^\nu, 1_n) \mathbf{X}^{\nu\top} \right) - \left(\mathbf{X}^\nu \text{diag}(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^\nu, 1_n)) \right) \right) \quad \text{and} \\ T &= (T_1, \dots, T_{n^\nu})^\top \\ &= 0.5 \cdot \sum w^\rho \cdot \left(\text{diag} \left(\mathbf{X}^\nu \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho) \mathbf{X}^{\nu\top} \right) - \left(\mathbf{X}^\nu \text{diag}(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho)) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

is the number of elements in the universe (estimated from \mathcal{S}^ρ) with the respective combination of \mathbf{X} -variables (cf. ENDERLE et al., 2013; MENARD, 1995, p. 12ff; VENABLES and RIPLEY, 1998, p. 221ff). Similar to design-based estimation, the inverse of those estimated propensity scores can be used for weighing the non-probability sample. Thus, in the following,

$$\omega_{\nu,1}(\mathbf{X}^\rho) = \underset{\widehat{\pi}}{\text{argmax}} \left(\log \left(\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{X}^\nu, \widehat{\pi}) \right) \right)^{-1} \quad (5.13)$$

denotes the propensity weights estimated from a model with only main effects, while

$$\omega_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}^\rho) = \underset{\widehat{\pi}}{\text{argmax}} \left(\log \left(\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{X}^\nu, \widehat{\pi}) \right) \right)^{-1} \quad (5.14)$$

represents propensity weights estimated from a model with all interaction terms. Note that the difference between $\omega_{\nu,1}$ and $\omega_{\nu,2}$ is solely the (number of) estimated parameters. Unlike post-stratification, *both* cases require $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_2(\mathbf{X}^\rho, w^\rho)$, the cross tabulation of the reference data, to be known.

5.5 Simulation study

By estimating pseudo-design-weights, the methodology presented in section 5.4 aim at providing a methodology for estimation from non-probability samples similar to classical design-based estimation. Evaluation and comparison of these methods is done by means of a Monte Carlo (MC) simulation study.

5.5.1 Setup of the simulation study

Application example: The European Social Survey

As an example where respondents have influence on the selected (net-)sample, the European Social Survey (ESS) can be considered. The MC simulation study is designed to mirror specific characteristics of this survey. A short description of the ESS is given by

LYNN et al. (2007, p. 6):

“The ESS is an academically-driven social survey designed to chart and explain the attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns of Europe’s diverse populations. In parallel with its substantive aims, it aims also to provide a model of best practice in methodology and to contribute towards improvement in methodological standards. Further details of the background and objectives of the survey can be found at www.europeansocialsurvey.org.”

From the survey-design, the ESS is a strict probability sample. All sampling schemes of the ESS, which vary between the countries involved, are clearly probability samples. Furthermore, significant efforts were invested in reducing non-contacts and refusals. This includes, for example, re-contacting in the case of non-contact.

Despite all those efforts, the overall response rates clearly indicate that the selection is not solely controlled by the researchers. Figure 5.1 shows the total achieved response rate during the ESS 2012 sampling. After ten attempted contacts, there is still more than 40% non-response. Although non-probability sampling does clearly not only occur in cases on

Figure 5.1: Contact attempts and response rate (ESS 2012)

non-response, it includes (at least) unit-nonresponse. Since the response probability is – at best – fractionally controlled by the efforts of the researchers, it remains unknown.

The reason to choose the ESS as an example is that this survey provides a wide range of information about this and closely related issues. Besides the ‘usual’ survey data, this includes data about the sampling process and interviewer questionnaires. In some of the participating countries, even non-respondent questionnaires have been implemented. For example, this is the case in Germany. If sampled units decide not to participate in the ESS itself, they are asked to answer a very short questionnaire of six questions of socio-demographic nature (country citizenship, gender, age, education and whether they live alone) and one about their political interest. The latter is chosen because political interest is a core variable in the context of many of the topics covered by the ESS. It is supposed to be related with core concepts such as media usage and information behaviour, as well as political attitudes and behaviour (cf. ALMOND and VERBA, 1963, PRIOR, 2010).

Figure 5.2: Contact attempts and response rate (ESS 2008 & 2012)

Based on the German ESS waves 2008 and 2012 and their corresponding non-respondent questionnaires, figure 5.2 shows the estimated share of each level of political interest within both groups. While the distribution for the respondents tends towards a bell-shape (i.e. the outer categories are less common than the inner), frequencies of non-respondents are lower

the higher the reported level of political interest. This indicates that there is a systematic difference between respondents and non-respondents in terms of political interest at least in Germany. There are also visible differences in the distribution and relationship of the other variables surveyed from the non-respondents. Differences in the manifold related variables are presumable, but cannot be judged since they are not observed for the non-respondents.

Simulation environment: The AMELIA-Population

The knowledge of the true population needed to judge the effects of (possibly non-representative) samples and estimation methodology is never available in case of real surveys like the ESS. Therefore, Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations are commonly used to evaluate estimation methodology. Hence, evaluation and comparison of the methods presented in section 5.4 is done by means of a MC simulation study. The population used is the synthetic AMELIA dataset described in ALFONS et al. (2011) and BERGER et al. (2016). However, to mirror the findings mentioned above, it has to be extended by a few variables: Beyond its own role, the variable *party affiliation* is, commonly seen as a predictor for *political interest*, the role of which is discussed above. The *response mechanism* is a model of how surveyed persons react when asked to participate in the ESS. It is thus the mechanism making the sample a non-probability sample.

To generate the variables *party affiliation* and *political interest*, values are sampled from conditional distributions, as for the generic AMELIA-variables (cf. ALFONS et al., 2011). The conditional distributions are derived from the ESS, years 2008–2014. From this data, values are drawn with replacement from within matching groups defined by cross-combinations of certain variables.

The distribution of *party affiliation* is conditioned on gender, 10-year age groups, isced-levels, being in paid-work and percentiles of household-income. Note that to avoid missing values in the population, the conditioning variables have to be reduced for some cases. Figure 5.3 shows the distribution of party affiliation in the original ESS-rounds as well as in the variable generated for AMELIA. It is evident that the marginal distribution differs only slightly, which is due to the fact that the distribution of the socio-demographic variables are slightly different as well.

The *political interest* variable is generated by sampling from the derived distribution,

Figure 5.3: Distribution of party affiliation in AMELIA and ESS waves 2008–2014

conditioned on the variables gender, 10-year age groups, isced-levels, being in paid-work, percentiles of household-income and party affiliation. Figure 5.4 shows the distribution of the original and generated variable. Again, the marginal distribution differs slightly due to the fact that the distribution of the socio-demographic variables is somewhat different as well.

To check the plausibility of the common distribution of the newly generated variables, figure 5.5 compares the original frequencies of the cross-combinations of party affiliation and political interest with those of the generated variables. It becomes evident that the common structure in AMELIA is close to that in the ESS waves 2008–2014.

The *response mechanism* variable is generated by regression models. As we want to model the probability of participating in a sample out of the sample itself, this is not so straightforward. Two approaches are used to generate a response pattern:

In the first response pattern, a *model for the number of contacts* is used for the observed values (set of respondents) of the four combined ESS waves. The number of contacts is modelled by an ordinal regression, using explanatory variables gender, 10-year age groups,

Figure 5.4: Distribution of political interest in AMELIA and ESS waves 2008–2014

isced-levels, being in paid-work, percentiles of household-income, party affiliation and political interest. The idea is that the number of contact attempts required until an respondent participates in the sample might be used as an indicator for the response probability. Like in the ESS, the cutoff value for non-respondents is set to ten contact attempts. Since the results are based only on the respondents, the probabilities have to be rescaled to obtain response rates as in the real ESS data.

The second response pattern models the *probability of responding given independent variables*. As this can not be done by considering only the ESS response set, it makes use of the non-respondent questionnaires in Germany. Using the variables obtained in the non-respondent questionnaire, the probability $P(S_i = 1|Z)$ is modelled by a logistic regression, where $S_i = 1$ if element i participates in the ESS and $S_i = 0$ if i participates in the non-respondent questionnaire. The independent variables represented by Z in this case are gender, age, isced-levels and political interest. Again, the results are rescaled to match ESS response rates.

- \mathbf{X}_U Includes information for the whole universe (population) regarding age-classes of 10 years, gender and isced-levels.
- \mathbf{X}_R Includes data from a probability reference sample about age-classes of 10 years, gender, isced-levels and political interest.
- \mathbf{X} Is the scenario mimicking the non-respondent questionnaire, i.e. the same variables as \mathbf{X}_R for the whole gross sample are used.

5.5.2 Results of the simulation study

Underlying response pattern I: Number of attempted contacts

The first response pattern is based using the number of contacts as an indicator for response probabilities. Figure 5.6 shows the boxplots, absolute relative bias (ARBias) and relative-root-mean-squared error (RRMSE) for the estimated share in each cross- and marginal tabulation cell of party affiliation and political interest over the 10 000 samples. Note that the method labeled by – is the comparison method without any adjustments, i.e. naive estimation without weighting. The lowest value in terms of ARBias and RRMSE in each cell are marked by their red color.

Under this response scheme, the results show that differences between most of the proposed methods are not too big. Even ignoring the response pattern does often not lead to substantial worsened estimates. However, in none of the cells this naive approach is outperforming the methods compensating the selectivity. Hence, ignoring the response mechanism is usually not sensible.

Looking at the bias, post-stratification to calibrate the second moments (eqn. 5.8) on a reference sample, denoted by $w_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_R)$, often yields good results. However, there are a number of cells where other post-stratification methods perform slightly better, as all post-stratification approaches yield quite similar results in this scenario. It is nevertheless obvious that estimating propensity scores often worsens the bias rather than compensating for it. The only competitive propensity model is the one using population information with interaction terms ($\omega_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_U)$).

A not too different picture results when considering the RRMSE: The post-stratifications of the marginal distributions perform slightly better than $w_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_R)$ in many of the cells,

Figure 5.6: Evaluation of the estimates obtained by the different methods for each cross-combination of party affiliation and political interest. Response-Pattern I.

but all post-stratification methods lead to quite similar results. Again, $\omega_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_U)$ is the only sensible choice from the propensity models.

Even though post-stratification seems superior to propensity weights, the results under the first response pattern are ambiguous and do not show a clearly preferable method. Together with the naive reference estimator performing relatively well, this might indicate

- a) low non-response bias in the real ESS, if the number of attempted contacts is a valid indicator of response probability or
- b) poor quality of the number of attempted contacts as an indicator of response probability.

Taking a look at the second response pattern might help to clarify this situation.

Underlying response pattern II: Non-respondent questionnaire

As described above, the second response pattern uses the German non-respondent questionnaire to model the response probabilities. As before, figure 5.7 depicts the estimators for the share in each cross-combination of party affiliation and political interest.

There is visibly more variation between the different estimators in this case, and the naive reference approach is usually more biased than its alternatives. In many cases, post-stratification to the second moments of a reference sample, $w_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_R)$, and propensity-weighting using interaction terms based on the same reference-sample, $\omega_{\nu,2}(\mathbf{X}_R)$, perform quite similar. Often, both seem to be suitable estimators regarding bias as well as RRMSE. However, post-stratification again outperforms the propensity weights in some cells, hence seeming the better choice. As before, propensity weights tend to be less reliable.

Since the auxiliary variables from the reference sample \mathbf{X}_R include the variables used for generating the response probabilities, the good performance using \mathbf{X}_R are as expected. But clearly, the methods using \mathbf{X} perform worse, even though they use the same variables (from the simulated non-respondent questionnaires). Furthermore, the first response pattern also tends to suggest post-stratification of the common distribution using a reference sample as a suitable estimator, even though the RRMSE is sometimes slightly higher.

5.6 Conclusion & Outlook

Altogether, post-stratification results are usually of better quality compared to propensity weights. This might be due to the fact that post-stratification weights are determined *only* by the reference data and not the non-probability sample, while both data sources are used for computing the weights through propensity scores.

Furthermore, it seems generally worth it to consider probability reference samples as source of auxiliary information. Even if this information is subject to sampling errors in this case, the estimates from a sample often perform better than data for the whole universe, as there are simply more variables observed in the sample than in the universe.

In general, the results tended to be better if the multivariate distribution of the auxiliary variables is used rather than only the marginal distributions, even if this might lead to slightly increased variances. Maintaining the relationship between the **X**-Variables in calibration usually compensated better for selection bias than using the variables separately.

Thus, it might be sensible to further investigate approaches to calibrate multivariate characteristics – potentially even covariances or correlations, to not only consider categorical variables. Future research also has to be conducted regarding inference from non-probability samples since this yields essential information for quality reports as part of the European Statistics Code of Practice (EUROSTAT, 2011). Furthermore, the methodology for non-probability samples is dependent of the type of sample (response mechanism) considered. This urges the needs of developing and evaluating further methods for other types of non-probability samples, e.g. online-surveys.

6 Children’s Well-being in Times of Crisis in PIIGS Countries: The Capability Approach as a Multidimensional Approach to Deprivation

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6.1 Introduction

The study presented in this chapter was born upon the InGRID TNA visit of Dr Antoanneta Potsi at the Department of Economics and Management of the University of Pisa and it is a further development with respect to the study already presented in Deliverable 23.1. The results presented here will be published in the book “Human development in times of crisis” to be published soon by Palgrave MacMillan.

Due to the financial crisis and the subsequent economic recession, which started in 2008, five members of the European Union (Portugal, Italy, Ireland, Greece and Spain) became known as PIIGS. The substantial instability of their economies was the main reason for grouping them together. The “common framework” that these five countries shared in time of crisis stimulates interesting analyses aiming to measure and compare the living standards of children in different households across these five countries as well as a more general discussion on the social impact that the economic crisis had on this particular vulnerable sub-group of the society. In particular, our study examines children’s well-being using a multidimensional approach to deprivation through the capability approach. Indeed, the gains made through the use of the capability approach in the knowledge and measurement of well-being demonstrate its potential and encourage its application to different contexts or groups, such as children. Children have, over the last two decades, become visible to policy-makers, politicians, and academics concerned with promoting children’s wellbeing in both the short and the long term. Children are citizens of contemporary societies and they are also key for the future of society from a dual perspective: as citizens who are relevant for the future of democracies and as constituents of the labour force of tomorrow’s economy. The success of an economy and of a society cannot be separated from the lives that members of the society are able to lead (SEN, 1999). SEN (1999) that

the capabilities that adults enjoy are deeply conditional on their experiences as children. Accordingly, childhood is considered a decisive phase in the reproduction of deprivation and social inequality as a resource of deficiencies during this critical life period which may well have long-term effects on later life. The impact of deprivation on children's life quality has two main facets: their entitlements to a good life in the here and now as young children and the impact inequalities have on the societal development and the potential for children's forthcoming adulthood. Literature on previous recessions in different countries and periods suggest that exposure to poverty in early life and during childhood for prolonged periods may have a strong and irreversible impact on physical, cognitive and social health of the childhood population (RAJMIL et al., 2014). It is worth noting that a comprehensive coverage of the impact of the global economic crisis on children's well-being in PIIGS countries would need a dynamic perspective that allows to measure children's well-being before and after this target period of time. This paper offers instead a discussion based on cross-sectional data collected in 2009. Despite the cross-sectional data availability constraint which limits this analysis, the year 2009 marks a time-period of the already underway crisis and such an investigation could offer a better understanding of children's well-being in time of crisis. Hence, the impact of the global economic crisis on Europe and specifically on the PIIGS countries was an evident problem already in 2009. The comparison of children's well-being between these five fragile countries in a multi-dimensional framework improves our knowledge on the social returns of those economies in this period of crisis. To sum up, this chapter is based on a study of children's living conditions and deprivation in the so-called PIIGS by using the data of the EU-SILC 2009 survey. The study aimed to generate knowledge relevant for creating and enabling the conditions in which children can live flourishing lives. Reliable knowledge of social realities and life experiences depends on the availability of the EU-SILC data. In an effort to avoid the homogenisation of children and their deprivation/well-being we disaggregate the children conceptually as well as in empirical analysis according to the factors of gender and age. Further on, we considered significant to investigate the covariates of social class, single parent households and households' educational level. The study associates with the Capability Approach (CA), a flexible and multi-purpose normative framework for the evaluation of human development, well-being and freedom by thinking in terms of human functionings and capabilities. Functionings are "features of the state of an existence of a person" (HAWTHORN, 1987), while capabilities represent what people are able to do or to be (SEN, 1999). ROBEYNS (2005) pointed out that: "The CA is not a theory that can ex-

plain poverty, inequality or well-being; instead, it rather provides a tool and a framework within which to conceptualize and evaluate these phenomena. Applying the CA to issues of policy and social change will therefore often require the addition of explanatory theories". In the next section the background underlining the discourse of children's well-being and the Capability Approach is introduced. Section 3 delineates the methodology used for measuring children's well-being the description of data. Section 4 presents the study's findings and section 5 articulates the conclusions.

6.2 Children's well-being and the Capability Approach

UNICEF (2014) reveals a strong and multifaceted relationship between the impact of the Great Recession on national economies and a decline in children's well-being since 2008. Specifically, it is argued that children are suffering the most and will bear the consequences longest, in countries where the recession has hit hardest. Accordingly, the period of 2009 is of significance as it provides evidence on first implications of the economic downturn and the imposition of austerity measures on children's well-being. In general, in periods of extreme social ferment and rapid change, temporality of people's lives, the process by which lives change in a changing society and the setting in which people live are decisive factors in the mutability of childhood and adulthood (ELDER, 1990, ELDER et al., 1993). The social repercussions of the financial crisis in Europe are serious for the concrete lives of many citizens independent of age and gender. Such periods of extreme social and economic ferment produce major reorientations of society which reshape the life course of individuals, both adults and children as Elder showed in his study on the "Children of the Great Depression" (ELDER, 1990). The new conditions shaped by the economic and social crisis of recent years will be affecting children directly and/or indirectly, especially when the environment consists of various disadvantages (poverty, parental unemployment, social exclusion, migration, etc.) which are aggravated by the current changes in work, safety, welfare state provisions. Times of social crisis have an impact especially on the lives of the most vulnerable members of a society. Crisis could hinder the progress on human development and on poverty reduction and children are disproportionately burdened with unequal chances. The current social and economic conditions compromise the opportunities of children to reach their full potential and put them at an increased risk of having difficult times in childhood and limited chances as they grow up. Having a good life as a child is more than a matter of material circumstances. Limited chances in childhood have

profound impact on one's situation in mid- and old age. KLASSEN (2001) and BIGGERI (2007) argue that deficiencies in important capabilities during childhood not only reduce the well-being of those suffering from the deficiencies, but may also have broader social implications. SEN (1999) stresses the remarkable deprivation, destitution and oppression observed in one form or another, in rich countries as well as poor ones. Poor children suffer a disproportionate share of deprivation and hardship. COMIM et al. (2011) refer to the impact of poverty on children's development by stressing children's disproportional representation among the poor, their suffering from irreversible forms of capability failure in terms of mental, physical, emotional and spiritual development, their vulnerability within the cycle of inter-generational transfer of poverty and the influence of their current well-being for their future. Poverty measures struggle to capture important differences in children's poverty experiences over their lifetimes. BIGGERI et al. (2006) argue that children are subjects of capabilities and that the Capability Approach can be very useful as a framework of thought and as a normative tool, in analysing children's well-being, poverty and deprivation and in individuating social policies for children human development. SEN (1987) argues that it is plausible to identify someone as having a low standard of living on the ground that he or she is deprived of decent housing, or adequate food, or basic medical care. However, for Sen the stock of commodity possession is not the right place to stop. Sen stresses that the standard of living must be directly a matter of the life one leads rather than of the resources and means one has to lead a life. According to SEN (1987), the concern should be on the type of life one succeeds in living with the help of commodities, as commodities are means to other ends. So, the focus has to be on what life we lead and what we can or cannot do, can or cannot be. NUSSBAUM (2011) developed an open-ended and extendable list of dimensions or basic central capabilities for human flourishing as a minimum account of social justice that has proven to be a valuable framework for the operationalization of the approach and inspired this study. The CA has gained increasing significance across the world in recent years, having been embraced by a number of international organizations including the UN, the OECD, and the European Union. There is an implicit agreement conferring the main responsibility for the well-being of their children to parents (MUNOZ, 2010). Parents of all interests are and remain the lawful representatives of their children (SUNKER and SWIDEREK, 2007). As a consequence, the welfare situation of children depends mainly on the cultural, social, and economic position of their parents - with the implication that they will be as wealthy or as poor as their parents are. Whether intended or not the actions of parents in response to situations

of family change inevitably pattern or impinge on their children's upbringing (ELDER, 1990). As members of the same family unit, parents and children would obviously share many situations in the crisis period, though not from the same vantage point, owing to generational differences in childhood environment, and life stage. The impact of financial crisis and its consequent effects on social crisis may be diffused in different ways within the scope of childhood. Moreover, children constitute a financial cost for families, which may fall differentially on different family members. It is significant to understand that within families the dynamics of economic and social crisis have an impact on all family members. Children are part of this process, they contribute to it but they also experience its consequences. HARPER et al. (2009) argue that although parents try to protect their children from the worst impacts of crisis, there are often limits to how much they can do, especially the poorest. Further on, they stress that vulnerabilities depend on both gender and age and are multidimensional. "Girls often experience higher levels of nutrition and educational deprivation than boys, with long term wellbeing implications for themselves and their own children" (HARPER et al., 2009).

6.3 Measuring children's well-being in PIIGS countries

As we previously outlined, the intent of this study is to offer insights on PIIGS's children's well-being beyond monetary deprivation in times of crisis through the Capability Approach (CA). One of the first issues to be resolved in the study of children's well-being from the Capability Approach is the choice of obtaining the data with either nonparticipatory or participatory methods. The analysis carried out in this Chapter refers to the former method, i.e. we employ secondary data to analyse children's well-being according to their functionings and capabilities. The dimensions included in our analysis are constrained by the information contained in EU-SILC survey. More details on the choice of the dimensions can be found in POTSI et al. (2016). Generally, the first step in a multidimensional approach to analyze poverty is the definition of dimensions corresponding to different aspects of poverty and of single items that measure these dimensions. This is a crucial step especially in terms of the CA since the choice of the capabilities to include in the evaluation is not straightforward and it also depends on the available data. Until now, several studies have examined children's capabilities; among them, some relevant researches are PHIPPS (2002), MEHROTRA and BIGGERI (2002), ADDABBO et al. (2014), DI TOMMASO (2007), WALKER and UNTERHALTER (2010), ADDABBO and DI TOMMASO (2008), BIGGERI et al.

(2010), WUST and VOLKERT (2012) and MODRONO et al. (2013). None of these studies is however characterized by the same choices of capabilities and functionings, but rather they differ depending on the context, the area of analysis and the age group. The second step involves the decision of using adequate methodological tools, able to preserve the richness of official data and to improve new measures of deprivation. Accordingly the theoretical and methodological framework needs respectively a discussion on data, items and dimensions and a description of the statistical methods applied.

6.3.1 Data, Items and Dimensions

The data used for this study come from the European Survey on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) with reference to the year 2009 and to the following five countries: Portugal (PT), Italy (IT), Ireland (IE), Greece (EL) and Spain (ES). Data makes up a representative sample of the total population, but in this case we have restricted the age spectra on the age span 0-14. Although significant works in the field consider children as those aged 0 to 17 years inclusive, in line with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Children (UN 1989) the age boundaries 0-14 were chosen. Apart from data constraints (indeed, it is worth noting that some of the items used in our analysis are child-specific and collected only for children under 16), these age groups may well be subject to higher vulnerability and intergenerational dependence. Moreover, until the age of 14 Italian, Greek and Portuguese children attend the same compulsory schools elementary plus secondary lower school / basic education while in the following years they can differentiate their educational path, e.g. choosing between schools more addressed to University studies or to the labour market. Thus, the age of 14 corresponds to decisive breaking point in children's life in most of the PIIGS countries. In Table 6.1 a list of basic capabilities for children has been defined. The items selected were classified into seven components that represent a respective capability: the ability to play, to be well nourished and clothed, to have an adequate financial budget, to have a social life, to live in an adequate housing and in a good environment and to be bodily healthy. The dimensions of concern were selected based on Nussbaum's central human-capabilities-list and on the conceptual framework that delineates the dimensions' fundamentality on what is perceived as elements of a "good" childhood that influence the here and now of children as well as their future development and opportunities. It is worth noting that the list of capabilities proposed reflect the standpoint by GUIO et al. (2012) that in order to adequately measure

children's standard of living it is necessary to look not only at items that solely affects children, but also at those that affects the households in which they live and that is likely to impact on their living conditions. Therefore, we have decided to complement the children's items with some of the items collected at household level, contrary to some other recent analyses of the 2009 EU-SILC module - see, for example, WATSON et al. (2012).

To assess the construct's internal consistency the Cronbach's alpha indicator was used (NUNNALLY and BERNSTEIN, 1994). As shown in Table 6.1, a quite high level of each construct's internal consistency reliability was found since almost all of the Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeded or are close to the 0.7 cut-off.

6.3.2 Fuzzy-set approach to poverty and deprivation

In this study a fuzzy methodology is applied in order to preserve the richness of the CA. In particular, the approach introduced by CHELI and LEMMI (1995) and then updated by BETTI et al. (2006) and LEMMI et al. (2010) for studying poverty is adapted. As CHIAPPERO-MARTINETTI (2006) argues, the fuzzy set theory can be used in order to depict deprivation and well-being indicators in a gradual, rather than a dichotomous, manner. The methodological approach used in this paper (henceforth Integrated Fuzzy and Relative IFR) was born on the assumption that poverty is a multidimensional phenomenon and a vague predicate that manifests itself in different shades and degrees (fuzzy concept) rather than an attribute that is simply present or absent for individuals in the population, as the traditional poverty approach assumes. The fuzzy set vision of poverty is particularly adequate for studying children's living conditions and deprivation mainly for two reasons. Firstly, it includes a non fixed value of poverty risk and deprivation, through the introduction of a membership functions (m.f.), i.e. a quantitative specification of individuals/households degrees of poverty and deprivation depending on the other individuals or households included in the analysis. A membership function's value of 0 is always associated with the lowest risk of poverty and deprivation, whereas a value of 1 is associated with the highest risk. Secondly, the multidimensional framework of the IFR approach proposed by BETTI et al. (2006) works up on several non-monetary indicators, assumed to be the manifest representation of a restricted number of underlying dimensions of deprivation, besides a monetary indicator based on the equivalent disposable income. The multidimensional analysis of poverty seems to be one reasonably grounded way to combine the CA and secondary quantitative data, because it includes monetary and non-

Table 6.1: Capabilities, indicators/functions and Cronbach's alpha values (overall and by Country)

CAPABILITIES	INDICATORS/FUNCTIONINGS	CRONBACH'S ALPHA VALUES					
		Overall	Portugal	Italy	Ireland	Greece	Spain
PLAY	Outdoor leisure equipment	0.78	0.75	0.78	0.58	0.72	0.69
	Indoor games						
	Book at home suitable for their age						
NUTRITION & CLOTHING	Fresh fruit & vegetable once a day	0.75	0.74	0.75	0.74	0.45	0.80
	Three meals a day						
	One meal with meat, chicken, or fish (or vegetarian equivalent) at least once a day						
	Some new (not second-handed) clothes						
	Two pairs of properly fitting shoes						
FINANCIAL	Inability to cope with unexpected expenses	0.65	0.62	0.65	0.70	0.65	0.68
	Arrears on mortgage or rent payments						
	Arrears on utility bills						
	Arrears on hire purchase installments						
	Ability to keep the home adequately warm						
AFFILIATION & SOCIAL LIFE	Celebrations on special occasions	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.52	0.70	0.69
	Internet connection						
	Regular leisure activity						
	Invite friends round to play & eat from time to time						
	Participate in school trips and school events that cost money						
	Child holiday away from home at least 1 week for year						
	Outdoor space in the neighborhood where children can play safely						
SHELTER	The accommodation is too dark	0.62	0.56	0.62	0.41	0.58	0.39
	The dwelling has an insufficient number of rooms compared to the number of persons						
	The dwelling has leaking roof/damp walls/floors/foundations or rot in the window frames						
SAFETY	Suitable place to study or do homework	0.64	0.56	0.64	0.58	0.58	0.55
	Crime, Violence, vandalism						
	Pollution Noise						
BODILY HEALTH	Damaged public amenities in the neighborhood	0.52	0.68	0.66	0.84	0.76	-
	Unmet need for consulting a dentist Unmet need for consulting a GP or specialist excluding dentists and ophthalmologists						

monetary dimensions going beyond the traditional approach based only on the economic or financial situation. As concerns the monetary dimension, the Fuzzy Monetary Indicator (henceforth FM) is computed for each individual by taking into account the share of individuals less poor and the share of the total equivalised income received by all individuals less poor than him. The FM indicator is expressed in the form of a membership function with mean value set equal to the national Head Count of Ratio (HCR), the indicator measuring the share of poor people at national level (i.e. here the number of households with children with equivalised income below the poverty line). It means that at national level the FM value is equal to the conventional at risk-of-poverty rate even if their interpretation is different. In particular, the FM indicator indicates a degree of poverty whereas the HCR indicator measures the share of poor people. On the other side, the computation of the deprivation indicators under the IFR approach involves a long process that can be summarized in seven steps, as it follows: 1) identification of the survey items referring to children's deprivation relevant under the CA (see Table 6.1) transformation of the items into the [0,1] interval, 3) confirmatory factor analysis to define the latent dimensions (i.e. capabilities); 4) computation of the weights within each dimension; 5) calculation of the scores for each dimension; 6) calculation of an overall score (henceforth FS0); 7) calculation of the membership functions (or deprivation indices) related to each dimension (henceforth FS1, FS2, FS3, FS4, FS5, FS6, FS7). FS1, FS2 etc. follow the order presented in Table 6.1. Thus, FS1 is the indicator used for measuring the capability to play. In addition, according to the IFR approach, it is worth noting that also the overall deprivation indicator FS0 value is set equal to the conventional at-risk-of-poverty rate at national level. Whereas, the deprivation rates for individual dimensions (from FS1 to FS7) are not scaled to automatically equal the overall deprivation rate FS0. For details on the formulas involved in these steps and for clarifications on the overall approach the main references are BERTI et al. (2014) and BETTI et al. (2006) In the next paragraph we present the relevant results obtained by applying the process described above to our data.

6.3.3 Assessment of the conceptual framework

The steps from 1 to 3, described above, have been applied for the assessment of the theoretical framework. Thus, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) has been applied for determining whether the hypothesized structure, showed in Table 6.1, provided a good fit to the data in each country after data have been suitable transformed (step 2). In other

words, we tested if the relationship between the observed variables and their underlying latent constructs (dimensions) existed (CHILD, 1990). CFA outcomes provide information on each indicator’s significance. When running CFA, many different fit statistics can be used to help determine whether the model provides adequate fit for the data. To assess the fit of the latent structural model the Adjusted for Degrees of Freedom (AGFI), the Root Square Mean Error of Approximations (RMSEA) and the Non-Normed Fixed Index (NNFI) were calculated. The AGFI accounted for 0.90 or more in three countries and the others for values close to 0.90, achieving a value close to 1 indicates a good fit. The RMSEA, expressing the unexplained or residual variance of the factor structure, accounted for 0.05 in Italy to a maximum of 0.07 in Ireland. Values of the statistic ranging between 0.05 and 0.08 indicate reasonable errors of approximation in the population. NNFI, equal to 0.80 or more in three countries out of five, met the criteria for acceptable fit (0.80 or greater). In the other two countries even if the value of NNFI is lower than 0.80, the remaining two indicators indicate a reasonable fit, therefore we conclude that the conceptual framework is sufficiently supported in all countries considered.

6.4 Findings

6.4.1 Descriptive statistics

The main characteristics of the data set used in the empirical analysis are summarized in Tables 6.2 and 6.3. Table 6.2 shows the country sample size percentage of households with children compared with the overall population of households and the respective percentage for individuals living in these households.

Table 6.2: Country sample size, percentage of households, number and percentage of individuals living in households with children

Country	# households	% of total households	# individuals	% of total individuals
PT	1197	29	4749	41
IT	5030	23	19128	37
IE	1349	34	5556	50
EL	1664	25	6599	36
ES	3662	26	14535	39
Average (all countries)	2580	27	10113	41

In accordance with the map of birth rate across Europe (OECD, 2011), the incidence of households with children varies among the five countries, the lowest share is in Italy and the highest in Ireland followed by Portugal. Table 6.3 presents a set of socio-demographic

characteristics relevant to household with children that are also informative about the different environment prevailing in each country.

Table 6.3: Socio-demographic characteristics by country (percentages)

Household characteristics		Country				
		Portugal	Italy	Ireland	Greece	Spain
Social class	Class 1	37	44	44	38	40
	Class 2	10	18	11	26	12
	Class 3	52	34	36	35	44
	Not classified or missing	1	2	9	1	4
Educational level	High	14	19	43	34	31
	Medium	15	38	20	37	21
	Low	69	43	33	28	42
	Missing	2	0	4	1	5
Single parent		7	7	8	4	6
Children mean age	More than 9 years	37	35	38	37	32
	Between 3 and 9 years	41	34	36	37	36
	Less than 3 years	22	31	26	26	32
Children gender	only male(s)	38	36	33	33	36
	only female(s)	39	39	36	36	38
	male(s) and female(s)	23	24	31	31	26

The sizes of the social classes differ by country, with the proportion in class 1 (large employers, professionals, managers, higher administrative, technical and supervisory) higher in the two more northern countries (Italy and Ireland) of PIIGS. The class 2 “petit bourgeois classes” (small employers and the self-employed) is very large in Greece compared to the other four countries. Finally the size of the lower technical and routine classes is largest in Spain and Portugal. In all PIIGS countries the percentage of low-educated household heads is very high compared to the other educational levels with the exception of Ireland where we observe the highest percentage of high-educated household heads. Compared to the other countries Portugal show the highest percentage of household heads in low educational level, followed by Spain and Italy. Lone parents with minor children account for a very low percentage of household across the five countries, with a very similar shares. Table 6.3 also shows how average children’s age varies across the PIIGS countries. The share of households with a low average children’s age is higher in Italy and Spain than in Portugal, Ireland and Greece. Meanwhile, in the other two age classes the differences across countries are less evident. Finally, the last row of Table 6.3 reveals a similar distribution of the children’s gender in Portugal, Italy and Spain from one side, and in Ireland and Greece from the other side.

6.4.2 Children's well-being across PIIGS

Starting with the traditional analysis to poverty (i.e. considering only the monetary indicator) results confirm that in all PIIGS countries, children are at greater risk of poverty and social exclusion than the general population. In particular, the higher values of the poverty rate for all the households are observed for Greece and Spain, where the percentage of households with an equivalized income below the country specific poverty line is equal to 20,1%. The values observed for Portugal and Italy are slightly lower (18,2% and 18,4% respectively), while the HCR of Ireland is the lowest one (15%). Focusing on households with children, the HCR increases in all the countries, but with very different rates. The higher increase is observed for Italy, where the HCR for households with children (equal to 23,5%) is 28% higher with respect to the HCR for all the households living in the country. The higher values of poverty rates are observed for households with children living in Spain (24,7%) and Greece (24,2%), but in these cases the increase with respect to the overall HCR is less pronounced than in Italy, being equal to +23% and +20% respectively. For Ireland we observed again the lower poverty rate value (16,1%), which represent a very low increase (+7%) when compared with the country overall household HCR. Thus, not only the HCR values observed for Ireland are the lowest, but also the gap between the risk of poverty for children and for the whole population is the lowest. Accordingly to the IFR approach the FM indicator, as expected, reflects the trend of the traditional poverty measure described above. For this reason we do not add further comments on this point. On the other hand, on average, dimension-specific deprivation rates (FS1 to FS7) are much lower than the overall deprivation rate FS0 for the country concerned. For this reason, rather than showing the actual values of the dimension-specific rates, in Figure 6.1 we show for each country the ratios of dimension-specific rates to the overall deprivation rates, The ratios indicate the relative size of the single fuzzy deprivation measures (FS1 to FS7) with respect to the overall rate, allowing us to compare in each country and across countries the relative importance of children's well-being. In general, the smaller the ratio is, the less important the corresponding capability is in relative terms.

Two main groups of dimensions emerge from the results. These ratios show low values for the dimensions Play (FS1), Nutrition & clothing (FS2) and Bodily health (FS7). They indicate that in each country the capability to play, to be adequately nourished and dressed and to be able to have a good health have a small relative importance with respect to the

Figure 6.1: Fuzzy supplementary deprivation rates (using the country specific FS0 indicator as the denominator) for households with children.

overall deprivation. In detail, this last dimension shows the lowest importance in all the countries where it is available, whereas for Spain the lowest value is the one observed for the Play dimension. Moreover, the second lowest value is always observed for the dimensions Play or Nutrition & clothing. At the opposite side, for the dimensions Financial (FS3), Affiliation & social participation (FS4), Shelter (FS5) and Safety (FS6) we can observe higher ratios, meaning that deprivations of these capabilities are elevated and therefore their incidence on the overall deprivation is very high. Looking at the specific countries we can notice that for Portugal, Italy and Spain the two highest ratios are those referring to the Safety and Affiliation & Social participation dimensions. These results can suggest a “duality” of life, internal to own family (dimensions FS1, FS2 and FS7) and external (FS4 and FS6). Deprivation in aspects such as health and play are more amenable to alternative non-monetary resourcing, while this is not always possible for aspects of social life and safety. Even if also for Ireland and Greece these two last dimensions show very high values and therefore similar conclusion can be drawn, it is also true that these two countries also show some relevant differences. Indeed, in the case of Ireland, the higher deprivation is still observed for Safety (FS6), but it is followed by Financial (FS3) and Shelter (FS5) dimensions. Also for Greece the two higher ratios indicate a higher deprivation for the dimensions Safety (FS6) and Financial (FS3). Thus, we can say that for these two countries, while Safety is still a big concern as in the other countries, the

inability to deal with unexpected dues is a more relevant issue with respect to the other three countries. We then explored the level of deprivation of children's capabilities in the five countries according to the socio-demographic characteristics already presented in Table 6.3. This analysis aims to compare differentials between countries in levels of deprivation according to these household characteristics in order to highlight similarities and significant differences that can be useful tools for policy makers. The results are presented in Table 6.4. Since we are principally interested on children's capabilities, in this table we do not present neither results with respect to the monetary nor to the overall deprivation, but we only refer to the seven dimensions described in Table 6.1 (FS1-FS7). In particular, the values reported in Table 6.4 are computed, for each dimension, as the ratio between the categories of the variable concerned over one of the categories chosen as the baseline. The first two columns of Table 6.4 characterise each household using the educational level of the major income earner (in particular, the ratio is between the lower or the medium level of education over the higher level). First of all, we can notice that almost all the ratios are major than one in each country: this indicates a higher degree of deprivation for children living in households characterised by lower educational levels. Moreover, in Portugal and Greece the incidence of education seems to be more pronounced than in the other countries, since the ratios are generally higher than the corresponding ratios in the other countries. Nevertheless, the impact of the educational level is changeable among the seven dimensions. In general, the gap is very low in the Shelter and Safety dimensions, meaning that education does not play an important role in explaining deprivation in such dimensions. The major gaps are instead observed for the dimension FS2 (Nutrition & clothing), especially for Portugal and Greece, and for FS1 (Play), with a particular relevance for Portugal, Italy and Greece. At a general level, these findings could be explained by this simple consideration. Higher levels of education are usually linked with a better job and consequentially with a better remuneration that may have a much stronger influence on the last three dimensions. Whereas the internal and external environment where children live could be less directly affected by better working conditions. The third column of Table 6.4 takes into account lone parents, another relevant household characteristic that can create important disparities for children. Living with a single parent implies a general increase of deprivation for the children along all the dimensions and in all countries: the ratios, computed as the values for not single parents over those obtained for single parents, are almost all major than one (this is always true also for the HCR and FM measures that are not reported in Table 6.4). We can note,

however, that the observed increments are not so pronounced as those resulting for the educational level. The higher ratios are those observed for the dimension FS2 (Nutrition & clothing) for Spain and for the dimensions FS1 (Play) and FS7 (Bodily health) for Greece. It is interesting to note that for these last two dimensions, FS1 and FS7, the ratios of Portugal are instead less than one, implying in this case a lower deprivation for children living with a single parent.

Another contextual variable we investigated is the social class of the household (see fourth and fifth columns of Table 6.4). The values reported in Table 6.4 are the ratios of the estimates obtained for social class 2 and 3 with respect to the estimates for social class 1, chosen as the baseline. Actually social class 1 represents the best benchmark insofar as it includes very high-skilled workers. Therefore, as expected, almost all the ratios are major than one, indicating a higher deprivation for social classes 2 and 3 with respect to social class 1. The main exception regards the FS6 dimension (Community & environment), with average values of the ratios across the countries equal to 0,76 and 0,94 for class 2 and class 3 respectively. Even if the reasons behind this result cannot be easily understood without further information, we can suppose that some of the items included in such dimension, as for example pollution and noise, are certainly more important issues in big cities where it is also higher the concentration of households belonging to social class 3. Therefore, this result can hide a geographic rather than a social class effect. Also for dimensions FS5 (Shelter) and FS7 (Bodily health) the gap is not so pronounced, especially the one between social class 2 and social class 1. At the opposite side, we can observe a pronounced gap for the FS measures FS1 (Play) and FS2 (Nutrition & clothing), even if there are some differences among the five countries. The deprivation is instead higher for social class 3 when considering the fuzzy supplementary measures, an especially FS1 and FS2; the ratios are particularly high for Greece, in this case also for class 2 with respect to class 1. To sum up, these results show the existing social class differentials in children's well-being over the PIIGS countries, which may affect the future capabilities and opportunities of children and can have consequences on the total welfare. We finally present the results characterising the households depending on the age and the gender of the children (last four columns of Table 6.4). The results referring to the mean age of children are computed as ratios comparing the first and the third class of mean age values over the second class, chosen as the baseline. We can notice that the deprivation of households with children aged less than 3 years is minor with respect to that of households with children aged 3 to 9 years.

Table 6.4: Fuzzy supplementary deprivation rates according to some socio-demographic characteristics

Country	Variable	Educational level		Single parent	Social Class	
		Low/High	Medium/High	Yes/No	Class 2/ Class 1	Class 3 /Class 1
Portugal	FS1	10.51	4.4	0.87	2.8	5.8
	FS2	22.68	7.56	1.28	4.43	7.98
	FS3	4.55	2.07	1.21	2.78	2.99
	FS4	3.95	2.03	1	2.22	3.73
	FS5	1.83	0.87	1.13	1.27	2.34
	FS6	0.91	0.98	1.27	0.73	1.07
	FS7	5.13	2.27	0.58	2.41	2.85
Italy	FS1	8.48	3.16	1.57	1.32	5.31
	FS2	6.4	2.19	1.08	1.59	4.6
	FS3	3.04	1.39	1.41	1.65	2.63
	FS4	3.11	1.52	1.24	1.29	2.64
	FS5	1.76	1.08	1.13	1.07	1.63
	FS6	0.92	0.89	1.16	0.85	0.95
	FS7	4	1.38	1.83	1.26	2.68
Ireland	FS1	1.1	0.64	1.74	2.86	3.53
	FS2	4.2	2.43	1.94	0.33	4.06
	FS3	2.69	1.71	1.69	1.1	2.84
	FS4	1.97	1.26	1.52	1.04	2.27
	FS5	1.44	1.34	1.53	0.94	1.4
	FS6	1.37	1	1.17	0.58	0.93
	FS7	5.48	4.56	0	2.73	0.92
Greece	FS1	7.39	2.51	2	6.61	12.04
	FS2	18.27	9.37	1.86	10.05	11.73
	FS3	3.31	2.08	1.47	2.15	2.94
	FS4	4.64	2.4	1.99	2.62	4.79
	FS5	2.09	1.55	1.29	1.59	2.27
	FS6	0.68	0.98	1.25	0.66	0.85
	FS7	1.02	1.05	4.42	1.03	1.64
Spain	FS1	3.65	0.77	1.92	1.62	3.81
	FS2	4.71	1.75	2.87	1.53	5.22
	FS3	2.86	2.19	1.32	1.65	2.86
	FS4	3.1	1.85	1.51	1.28	2.61
	FS5	1.57	1.18	1.18	0.89	1.56
	FS6	0.98	0.94	1.23	1	0.87
Overall	FS1	6.23	2.3	1.62	3.04	6.1
	FS2	11.25	4.66	1.81	3.58	6.72
	FS3	3.29	1.89	1.42	1.87	2.85
	FS4	3.35	1.81	1.45	1.69	3.21
	FS5	1.74	1.21	1.25	1.15	1.84
	FS6	0.97	0.96	1.22	0.76	0.94
	FS7	3.91	2.32	1.71	1.86	2.02

Table 6.5: Fuzzy supplementary deprivation rates according to some socio-demographic characteristics

Country	Variable	Children mean age		Children gender
		Class1/Class2	Class3/Class2	One female / One male
Portugal	FS1	0.75	1.46	1.07
	FS2	0.61	1.2	0.81
	FS3	0.61	0.83	0.93
	FS4	0.77	1.04	1.14
	FS5	0.72	1.1	1.27
	FS6	1	0.9	1.23
	FS7	0.27	0.94	0.65
Italy	FS1	0.36	0.72	1.19
	FS2	0.46	0.73	1.25
	FS3	0.95	0.9	1.11
	FS4	0.74	0.83	1.12
	FS5	0.85	0.86	1.05
	FS6	0.95	0.93	1.1
	FS7	0.36	0.86	1.11
Ireland	FS1	0.59	1.45	1.49
	FS2	1.24	0.63	0.22
	FS3	0.74	0.75	0.82
	FS4	0.83	0.65	1.26
	FS5	1.45	1.33	0.97
	FS6	0.85	0.78	1.03
	FS7	0	0.77	0
Greece	FS1	0.48	1.11	0.9
	FS2	0.39	0.97	0.71
	FS3	1.04	1.23	1.12
	FS4	0.84	1.07	1.01
	FS5	0.73	1.16	1.21
	FS6	0.83	1.11	0.88
	FS7	0.51	1.27	0.52
Spain	FS1	0.57	0.94	0.92
	FS2	0.44	0.59	0.97
	FS3	0.76	0.84	0.95
	FS4	0.83	1.03	0.86
	FS5	0.99	0.95	1.15
	FS6	0.94	0.96	0.93
Overall	FS1	0.55	1.13	1.11
	FS2	0.63	0.83	0.79
	FS3	0.82	0.91	0.99
	FS4	0.8	0.92	1.08
	FS5	0.95	1.08	1.13
	FS6	0.91	0.94	1.03
	FS7	0.28	0.96	0.57

This may depend on the lower needs or lower relevance of younger children in terms of the functionings considered in the present study (see Table 6.1). The only relevant exceptions are observed in Ireland for FS2 (Nutrition & clothing) and FS5 (Shelter). The results are more changeable when considering the third age class (more than 9 years) with respect to the second class (3 to 9 years), even if in this case the gaps are not so pronounced. It is interesting to note that according to the FS measures, Italy is the only country where the deprivation of households with older children (in average) is always lower; the same happens for Spain, with the only exception of FS4, but with a low ratio (equal to 1,03). In the other countries the many differences, in terms of an increase of deprivation, are observed for FS1 (Play) in Portugal and Ireland and for FS5 (Shelter) in Ireland. In Greece we do not observe main differences in deprivation between these two classes of children mean age. Thus, it seems that children with mean age under three years results in a minor deprivation under several dimensions. Lastly, as concerns the gender of the children, to control for the effect of the number of children in the household, we decided to consider only households with one female child and those with one male child. For these households the ratio is computed considering the category “one male” as the baseline. The overall results (averaged over the countries, see bottom of Table 6.4, last column) suggest that households with one female child are less deprived in the FS7 (Bodily Health) and FS2 (Nutrition & Clothing) dimensions. On the opposite for the dimensions FS1 (Play) and FS5 (Shelter) the deprivation is higher when the only child is a male. Looking at the individual countries we can see really changeable results. Indeed, while in Italy the deprivation for households with one female is higher under all the dimensions, the opposite happens for Spain with the only exception of the Shelter dimension.

6.5 Conclusion / Discussion

In this chapter we presented a multidimensional picture of children’s well-being in the PIIGS countries at the initial impact of the economic crisis. The period of 2009 is of significance as it provides evidence on first implications of the economic downturn and the imposition of austerity measures on children’s well-being. The use of the capability approach combined with a fuzzy methodology allowed us to shed light on different dimensions of children’s deprivation in each of the five countries included in the study. By using the data of the EU-SILC 2009 survey, this study gains insights into children’s deprivation in the so called PIIGS countries (i.e. Portugal, Italy, Ireland, Greece and Spain) at the

beginning of the economic downturn and imposition of austerity measures, and generates knowledge relevant for children's well-being. Moreover, by characterizing children households according to some socio-demographic factors we obtained some new and interesting insides that could help to interpret the differences in children's well-being in the PIIGS countries at the beginning of the crisis. The main results suggest that in all the PIIGS households with children have a higher risk of poverty with respect to the general population, as depicted by the traditional poverty indicator based on the household equivalised income. Besides, children deprivation according to seven non-monetary domains has also been explored. The results suggest that in all the countries the capability to play, to be adequately nourished and dressed and to be able to have a good health have a small relative importance with respect to the overall deprivation. At the opposite, aspects external to the household, such as the level of social participation and having adequate safety, are more important. The ability to deal with unexpected dues also play a relevant role especially in Greece and Ireland. The analysis disaggregated by the socio-demographic factors gave interesting results as it clearly shows that times of crisis do not affect all children to the same degree or to the same ways. First of all, children living in households with lower education level of the household major earned are generally more deprived. This is particularly true in Greece and Portugal, especially when considering the deprivation in the Nutrition & clothing domain. Living with a single parent is also a factor determining a higher deprivation, both considering monetary and non-monetary dimensions. In this case the higher impact for children regards the dimensions of Play and Bodily health in Greece. Also the social class of the household have an impact on children's well-being. The results suggest that children living in "white-collar" households are generally less deprived with respect to children living in the other two social classes included in the study. This result holds true in all the PIIGS countries and for almost all the dimensions, with very few exceptions. A higher level of well-being is observed for households where the mean age of the children is less than three years, especially when considering the comparison with households where the mean age is between three and nine years. The deprivation observed for children more than nine years is instead more changeable among the countries and the dimensions. Finally, also the gender of the children seems to have a certain impact on children's well-being when considering households with a female or male only child. We plan in the future to extend the analysis considering also households with two or more children, and including in this case also children of mixed gender. The dynamics of economic and social crisis have an impact on all family members, including children who, as

part of this process, contribute to it but also experience its consequences. However, times of crisis are not equally relevant for all members of the society. As the evidence shows, by escaping from the homogenization of childhood experiences we find that factors such as class, gender, age and educational level of the household's bread-winner play a decisive role in this process. The study sheds light on the blurred picture of children's well-being in the PIIGS countries. In parallel, it raises concern on the significance of investigating and even monitoring the multiple impact and effects of the socio-economic crisis on children's lives and induces policy-makers to take action and inform appropriate public policy.

7 On Multidimensional Poverty: Standard Errors and Extension to the Longitudinal Dimension

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7.1 Simplified Jackknife variance estimates for fuzzy measures of multidimensional poverty

In the literature, several works have been devoted to the computation of standard errors of traditional measures of monetary poverty at national level. By traditional measures of poverty we mean indicators that have been officially adopted by the international statistical institutes like Eurostat, for example the At-risk-of-poverty rate (ARPR), defined as the proportion of population with income below a certain threshold. Applications of different methods for variance estimation of poverty measures can be found in BINDER (1983), BINDER and PATAK (1994), BINDER and KOVACEVIC (1995), PRESTON (1995), KOVACEVIC and YUNG (1997), DEVILLE (1999), ZHENG (2001), BERGER and SKINNER (2003), DEMNATI A. (2004), OSIER (2009), MÜNNICH and ZINS (2011), VERMA and BETTI (2011), GRAF and TILLÉ (2014), OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2015), BERGER and PRIAM (2016). Furthermore, for instance in the framework of Europe 2020 strategy of the European Commission, estimates of poverty and social exclusion at sub-national regional level have become of central interest. In recent years the literature on the estimation of the standard errors of traditional measures of poverty at local level sensibly has expanded. See PIACENTINI (2014) for an analysis on overall OECD countries; VERMA et al. (2010b) on robustness of indicators at regional level; BETTI et al. (2012) on methodology for constructing subnational indicators of deprivation; GIUSTI et al. (2012) for small area methods applications; BETTI et al. (2016) for the use of cumulation methodology; ELBERS and LANJOUW (2003) for poverty mapping.

In the above-mentioned framework of Europe 2020 strategy of the European Commission, purely monetary measures of poverty have been presented together with new multidimensional measures of poverty. Also in the literature, measures of multidimensional poverty have been developed: application can be found in WHELAN and MAITRE (2007), BETTI et al. (2015a), GOEDEME (2013). However, no attention has been paid to standard error

computation of multidimensional measures.

We present a practical methodology for variance estimation for multi-dimensional measures of poverty and deprivation of households and individuals, derived from sample surveys with complex designs and fairly large sample sizes. This methodology is applied in a multi-domain and comparative context. The measures considered are based on fuzzy representation of individuals' propensity to deprivation in monetary and diverse non-monetary dimensions.

The basic idea of the fuzzy approach is to treat poverty and deprivation as a matter of degree, replacing the conventional poor/non-poor dichotomy. An individual degree of poverty is determined by the person's place in the income distribution. The same methodology facilitates the inclusion of other dimensions of deprivation into the analysis: by appropriately weighting indicators of deprivation to reflect their dispersion and correlation, we can construct measures of non-monetary deprivation in its various dimensions.

In dealing with population-based survey samples of households or persons, sampling and non-sampling errors affect the accuracy of the estimates based on these surveys. These are particularly relevant when our concern is the analysis of income poverty and inequality. These are complex statistics based on large sample surveys, normally with complex sampling designs. Unfortunately, information on sampling errors and design effects is often not obtained or at least not reported and utilised in the analysis of substantive results of the surveys. It seems to be a frequent practice to ignore the publication of confidence interval of poverty statistics. Even where published, it is not always clear whether standard errors have been computed accurately. These shortcomings exist even in the most developed settings: in most of the official publication from Eurostat on poverty indicators, for instance, standard errors are not presented, and as GOEDEMÉ (2013) notes, "this is not a feature unique to Eurostat publications".

Application of the variance estimation procedure requires redefinition of the sample structure variables (strata and primary sampling units) in some cases. We call this as the 'construction of computational units'. The procedure used for this purpose for the particular data set used are described.

The primary objective of this work is to extend variance estimation to beyond measures of monetary poverty, specifically to fuzzy formulation of those measures and, as a corollary, to multidimensional measures of deprivation which by their very nature are a matter

of degree i.e. are fuzzy. The second objective is to describe and numerically illustrate computational procedures and difficulties in producing reliable and robust estimates of sampling error for complex statistics derived from fairly large complex sample surveys. We attempt to identify some of these problems and provide solutions in the context of actual situations. In terms of computational tools, we have developed, as a part of the broader research of which this paper is a part, SAS-based software for the application of these procedures; this software can be made available to researchers on request, but is not described here.

7.1.1 Modelling fuzzy measures of multidimensional poverty

This section describes the basic cross-sectional fuzzy measures of monetary and non-monetary deprivation.

As noted, the fuzzy approach treats poverty and deprivation as a matter of degree, replacing the conventional classification of the population into a simple dichotomy. In principle all individuals in a population are subject poverty or deprivation, but to varying degrees. We say that each individual has a certain *propensity* to poverty or deprivation, the population covering the whole range $[0,1]$. The conventional approach is a special case of this, with the population dichotomised as $\{0,1\}$: those with income below a certain threshold are deemed to be poor (i.e. are all assigned a constant propensity to poverty, $= 1$); others with income at or above that threshold are deemed to be non-poor (i.e. are all assigned a constant propensity= 0).

There are several advantages of treating poverty and deprivation as a matter of degree, applicable to all members of the population, rather than as simply a ‘yes-no’ state.

1. Non-monetary deprivation depends on forced non-access to various facilities or possessions determining the basic conditions of life. An individual may have access to some but not to others. Hence non-monetary deprivation is inherently a matter of degree, and some *quantitative approach* such as the present one is essential.
2. Further insight into the relative income situations of individuals and groups can be obtained by incorporating into the poverty rates a measure of the actual levels of incomes received, particularly at the lower end of the income distribution.
3. The fuzzy approach provides more robust indicators of poverty (or more generally,

of deprivation in multiple dimensions) in the *longitudinal* context. The conventional approach measures mobility simply in terms of movements across some designated poverty line, and does not reflect the actual magnitude of the changes affecting individuals at all points in the distribution. Consequently, the degree of mobility of persons near to the chosen line tends to be over-emphasised, while that of persons far from that line largely ignored.

Apart from the various methodological choices involved in the construction of conventional poverty measures, the introduction of fuzzy measures brings in *additional* factors on which choices have to be made. The fundamental factor concerns the choice of ‘membership functions’, providing a quantitative specification of the propensity to poverty of each person given the level and distribution of income of the population.

7.1.1.1 Fuzzy membership function

BETTI et al. (2008)¹ have proposed the following fuzzy measures based on the seminal contributions of CERIOLI and ZANI (1990), and CHELI and LEMMI (1995); it is elaborated further in BETTI et al. (2015a). In the generalised form, the membership functions of monetary or non-monetary deprivation is defined for any individual of rank j in the ascending income distribution as:

$$\mu_{j,K} = \left(\frac{\sum_{\gamma=j+1}^n w_{\gamma} |X_{\gamma} > X_j}{\sum_{\gamma=2}^n w_{\gamma} |X_{\gamma} > X_1} \right)^{\alpha_K - 1} \left(\frac{\sum_{\gamma=j+1}^n w_{\gamma} X_{\gamma} |X_{\gamma} > X_j}{\sum_{\gamma=2}^n w_{\gamma} X_{\gamma} |X_{\gamma} > X_1} \right) \quad j : 1, \dots, n - 1; \quad (7.1)$$

$$\mu_{n,K} = 0$$

where X is the equivalised income² in the monetary deprivation, or the overall score s in the non-monetary deprivation (defined in equation 3 below); w_{γ} is the sample weight of individual of rank γ , and α_K ($K = 1, 2$) are two parameters corresponding, respectively, to monetary and non-monetary dimensions of deprivation. We term the monetary-based indicator as Fuzzy Monetary (FM), and the non-monetary indicator as Fuzzy Supplementary (FS). Each parameter α_K is estimated as described later in this section.

¹ See also the book of LEMMI and BETTI (2006) for further contributions on philosophy, mathematics, economics of the fuzzy set approach to poverty measurement, and the contributions of CHELI and BETTI (1999), BELHADJ (2011), BELHADJ (2012), ALKIRE and FOSTER (2011), BELHADJ and LIMAM (2012).

² Equivalised income of a household is defined based on the total household income and size and composition of the household. Individual persons with the equivalised income so assigned are the units of analysis in all results presented here.

Formula equation (7.1) could be rewritten as:

$$\mu_{j,K} = (1 - F_{j,K})^{\alpha_K - 1} (1 - L_{j,K}) \quad (7.2)$$

where $(1 - F_{j,K})$ is the proportion of individuals less poor (less deprived) than the person concerned, and $L_{j,K}$ represents the value of the Lorenz curve for individual j . Since the membership function is based on elements of the Lorenz curve, L and F, both the parameters α_K have an economic interpretation: the mean of the membership functions are expressible in terms of the generalized Gini measures G_{α_K} , a generalization of the standard Gini coefficient: $\frac{\alpha_K + G_{\alpha_K}}{\alpha_K(\alpha_K + 1)} = ARPR$.

7.1.1.2 Construction of the FS measure

To quantify and put together diverse indicators of deprivation several steps are necessary (BETTI et al. (2015b)):

- (I) Identification of items of deprivation to be included in the analysis;
- (II) Transformation of the items into the $[0, 1]$ interval;
- (III) Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis to identify dimensions of deprivation;
- (IV) Calculation of weights of individual items of deprivation within each dimension (each group of items);
- (V) Calculation of scores for each dimension;
- (VI) Calculation of an overall score and the parameter α of equation equation (7.1);
- (VII) Construction of the fuzzy deprivation measures separately in each dimension, taking their simple average as a measure of overall non-monetary ('supplementary') deprivation.

Based on our empirical data, the dimensions identified by exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis in Step 3 are reported in the first column of Table 7.1 and the deprivation items included in each dimension in column 2. Column 3 shows the original weights, and column 4 the weights rescaled as follows.

Let $s_{i,h}$ be the score of individual i computed for each dimension h in step 5, then the

overall score s_j is calculated with a simple average of the m dimensions, as follows:

$$s_j = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^m s_{j,h}}{m} \quad (7.3)$$

This implies that the final weights have been rescaled so that their sum is equal to one within each dimension.

Table 7.1: Dimensions identified by exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, and the corresponding item weights. Weights are rescaled so that their sum within each dimension is equal to 1.

Dimension	Items of deprivation	Weights	Rescaled weights
1 Basic lifestyle	Meals with meat, fish or chicken	3.25	0.51
	Household adequately warm	2.10	0.33
	Holiday away from home	0.65	0.10
	Ability to make ends meet	0.41	0.06
2 Consumer durables	Car	2.99	0.06
	PC	3.17	0.06
	Telephone	8.28	0.17
	Washing Machine	15.64	0.32
	TV	18.80	0.38
3 Housing amenities	Bath or Shower	11.66	0.40
	Indoor flushing toilet	11.85	0.40
	Leaking roof and damp	2.06	0.07
	Rooms too dark	3.87	0.13
4 Financial situation	Inability to cope with unexpected expenses	0.84	0.09
	Arrears on mortgage or rent payments	2.78	0.29
	Arrears on utility bills	2.38	0.25
	Arrears on hire purchase instalments	3.67	0.38
5 Environment	Crime, Violence, vandalism	2.16	0.39
	Pollution	1.95	0.35
	Noise	1.46	0.26
6 Work & Education	Early school leavers	3.61	0.62
	Low education	0.68	0.12
	Worklessness	0.39	0.07
	Duration of unemployment	1.14	0.20
7 Health related	General health	1.22	0.52
	Chronic illness	0.55	0.23
	Mobility restriction	0.57	0.25
	Unmet need for medical exam.	2.02	0.54
	Unmet need for dental exam.	1.74	0.46

The positive results achieved while applying this methodology to fields other than poverty (see, among other publications, AASSVE et al. (2007), AASSVE et al. (2009) BETTI (2015), BETTI et al. (2011), BETTI et al. (2012), BETTI et al. (2016), BELHADJ (2015) demonstrate its applicability and robustness.

7.1.1.3 Scaling parameter (α)

The traditional ARPR is the most basic and widely used measure of the level or rate of poverty in population. To be practically useful, it is highly desirable (even essential)

that the fuzzy measure of this poverty and deprivation rate are closely comparable to the conventional measure. In order to meet this requirement, we introduce a ‘scaling parameter’ (α) into the function defining the fuzzy measure in Equations equation (7.1) and equation (7.2).

The parameters α are estimated from empirical data separately for fuzzy monetary (FM) and fuzzy supplementary (FS) measures. However, the same condition is imposed in both cases: the mean of the corresponding membership function μ (which we may call the fuzzy ARPRs) is made equal to the conventional ARPR. The analysis is applied at the regional level. Empirically the two parameters have been found to be very closely related to ARPR; BETTI et al. (2015a) report a strong linear relationship between $\ln(\alpha)$ and ARPR.

In practice the true income distribution is not known, and we have to estimate parameters α_K from the empirical distribution which is available. Reliability of the estimates may be improved, for instance by pooling data over samples or over populations. In any case, we assume that, with a ‘large enough’ sample size, the estimators of the two scaling parameters are asymptotically consistent. Once α_K have been estimated as above, the same values may be used in defining all poverty/deprivation related measures for the population concerned. In fact, in specifying the membership functions in Equations equation (7.1) and equation (7.2), we consider α_K values, *by definition*, as fixed parameters for the given population. Hence in estimating variance as well, the values of α_K are taken as constant. This approach would disregard the contribution to variance of the uncertainty in the estimation of parameters α_K . This uncertainty may be reduced by pooling data from different sources, where available.

7.1.2 Outline of the JRR variance estimation computational procedure

A diversity of approaches have been developed for variance estimation of complex statistics from complex surveys, both general and some very specific approaches for particular applications.

Among the former, for the ‘typical’ social surveys based on reasonably large samples but with complex designs, the applicability of at least two broad approaches is well-established in the literature. These are the computational approaches based on (a) Taylor linearization, that estimate using comparisons among certain aggregates for primary selections or replicates within each stratum, and (b) on resampling methodology - such as the Boot-

strap, Balanced Repeated Replication (BRR) and Jackknife Repeated Replication (JRR) - in which the computation are done from comparisons among estimates for replications of the sample, each of which reflects the structure of the full sample.

For the application of any of these two classes of computational methods, the basic assumptions about the sample design have been well-discussed in several sources, see for instance VERMA (1991) for a detailed description. These assumptions are generally met or they can be reasonably approximated in most large scale and official population-based surveys, such as EU-SILC.

All replicated variance estimation procedures are based on comparisons among replications generated through repeated re-sampling of the same parent sample. *Once the set of replications has been appropriately defined for any complex design, the same variance estimation algorithm can be applied to a statistic of any complexity.* The basic requirement in application of these procedures is that the full sample is composed of a number of subsamples or replications, each with the same design and reflecting complexity of the full sample, enumerated using the same procedures. A replication differs from the full sample only in size. But its own size should be large enough for it to reflect the structure of the full sample, and for any estimate based on a single replication to be close to the corresponding estimate based on the full sample. At the same time, the number of replications available should be large enough so that comparison among replications gives a stable estimate of the sampling variability in practice.

In present work we use one of such methods, namely the JRR procedure.

7.1.2.1 Jackknife Repeated Replication procedure

JRR provides a versatile and straightforward computational technique for variance estimation. We have extended and applied this method for estimating variances for subpopulations (including regions and other geographical domains), longitudinal measures such as persistent poverty rates, and measures of net changes and averages over cross-sections in rotational panel designs. In this work we extend the method also to fuzzy measures.

In the standard ‘delete one-PSU at a time Jackknife’ version, each JRR replication is formed by eliminating one sample PSU from a particular stratum at a time and increasing the weight of the remaining sample PSU’s in that stratum appropriately so as to obtain an alternative but equally valid estimate to that obtained from the full sample. Briefly,

the standard JRR involves the following.

Let z be a full-sample estimate of any complexity. We use the subscript i to indicate a sample primary sampling unit (PSU) and h indicate its stratum; $a_h > 2$ is the number of PSUs in stratum h . Let $z_{(hi)}$ be the estimate produced using the same procedure after eliminating primary unit i in stratum h and increasing the weight of the remaining $(a_h - 1)$ units in the stratum by an appropriate factor g_h (see below). Let $z_{(h)}$ be the simple average of the $z_{(hi)}$ over the a_h sample units in h . The variance of z is then estimated as:

$$\text{var}(z) = \sum_h \left[(1 - f_h) \cdot \sum_i g_{(hi)} (z_{(hi)} - z_{(h)})^2 \right] \quad (7.4)$$

$(1 - f_h)$ is the finite population correction and it is usually ~ 1 for samples in typical social surveys.

While one may take factor $g_{(hi)}$ to be independent of the particular i in a given stratum h :

$$g_{(hi)} = a_h / (a_h - 1),$$

it is more appropriate to use (VERMA and BETTI, 2011):

$$g_{(hi)} = w_h / (w_h - w_{hi}), \quad (7.5)$$

where $w_h = \sum_i w_{hi}$, with $w_{hi} = \sum_j w_{hij}$ as the sum of sample weights of ultimate units j in primary selection units i . This means that in each replication (h_i) , the weights for individual units are redefined and rescaled as follows:

- (I) for unit j not in stratum h : $w'_{hij} = w_{hij}$;
- (II) for unit j in stratum h but not in PSU i : $w'_{hij} = g_{(hi)} \cdot w_{hij}$;
- (III) for unit j in stratum h and in PSU i : $w'_{hij} = 0$;

Form equation (7.5) for $g_{(hi)}$ is in line with the jackknife variance estimation for unequal probability sampling proposed by BERGER and SKINNER (2005). The authors, drawing on CAMPBELL (1980), introduce the factor $(1 - w_i)$ – in our notation $\left(1 - \frac{w_{hi}}{w_h}\right) = \left(\frac{w_h - w_{hi}}{w_h}\right)$ – as a correction factor for unequal probabilities, “reducing the contribution of observations which have higher π_i – values [selection probabilities] and thus make smaller contributions to variance”. The inverse of this correction to selection probability is the corresponding

correction to weight – our g_{hi} .

7.1.3 Data and construction of computational units for variance estimation

7.1.3.1 Micro-data for empirical analysis: EU-SILC

The reference data for the present work are based on a subset of micro-data from the EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) survey, which is the major source of comparative statistics on income and living conditions in Europe. The survey is conducted annually in each participating country. The total sample size of EU-SILC national surveys is of the order of 250,000 households, 500,000 adult persons, and 600,000 individuals of all ages per year. EU-SILC covers data and data sources of various types: cross-sectional and longitudinal; household-level and person-level; on income and social conditions; and from registers and interview surveys depending on the country. A standard integrated design has been adopted by nearly all EU countries. The design recommended by Eurostat has been developed and described in VERMA and BETTI (2006). It involves a rotational panel in which a new sample of households and persons is introduced each year to replace one quarter of the existing sample. Each persons enumerated in each new sample is followed-up in the survey for four years, along with the person's whole household. The design yields each year a cross-sectional sample, as well as longitudinal samples of various durations. All micro-level data have been weighted for variations in unit selection probabilities, non-response, other shortcomings in implementation, calibration on the basis of external data, and population size. Mostly the weighting has been implemented centrally by Eurostat; the procedure used has been developed and described in VERMA et al. (2007).

The EU-SILC survey collects comparable multidimensional micro-data on: (a) income, (b) economic hardship, (c) social exclusion, (d) housing, (e) labour, (f) education, (g) health. Information on social exclusion and housing condition is collected mainly at household level while labour, education and health information is obtained for each individual aged 16 and over. The core variable, income at very detailed component level, is mainly collected at personal level and then it is aggregated at household level to construct the household income. The reference income is the household disposable income, which is usually converted into the equivalised household income using a proper conversion scale.

7.1.3.2 Essential information on sample structure for computing sampling error

Variance estimation of measures from surveys like EU-SILC based on complex sample designs requires full information on the sample structure. For implementing the practical variance computation procedures, at a minimum the required information must include specification at the micro level of: (i) sample weights, (ii) stratum, and (iii) primary sampling unit (PSU). In the practical procedures for variance estimation discussed here, generally all the necessary information about the sample structure can be provided in the form of three variables defined for each analysis unit in the sample:

- the ‘*computational primary sampling unit (PSU)*’, to which the unit belongs;
- the ‘*computational stratum*’ in which the computational PSU lies; and
- the *sample weight* of the unit to be used in analysis.

In order to correctly define the computational strata and PSUs, information concerning the following three aspects must be available:

- Detailed description of the sample design, for instance identifying features such as the presence of self-representing units, systematic selection etc.
- Codes of the sample structure in the micro-data files.
- Information connecting the sample structure codes in the micro-data with descriptions of the particular sample design features, so as to be able to identify the design features applicable to particular units.

Very often, sample structure variables as coded in the data files require some redefinition before they can be used for the purpose of variance estimation to make such computations possible, efficient and robust. Of course, any such redefinition is appropriate only if it does not introduce significant bias in variance estimation. To do this in a statistically valid way requires sampling expertise. The computational structure can differ from the actual sample structure because of various considerations such as the following. Firstly, it is often necessary to define computational strata and PSUs to meet the basic requirement of practical methods of variance estimation for complex samples. Below we report some common situations.

1. It may be necessary to regroup ('collapse') strata so as to ensure that each stratum has *at least* two sample PSUs – the *minimum number required* for the computation of variance.
2. Units which are included into the sample automatically ('self-representing units') are in fact strata rather than PSUs, and computational PSUs have to be defined at a lower stage within each such unit.
3. In samples selected systematically, the implied implicit stratification is often used to define computational strata, from each of which an independent sample is supposed to have been selected. Such strata have to be formed by pairing or otherwise grouping of PSUs in the order of their selection from the systematic list, ensuring that each resulting computational stratum has at least two primary selections.
4. Sometimes non-response can result in the disappearance from the sample of whole PSUs. This can disturb the structure of the sample, such as leaving fewer than two PSUs in some strata. Variance computation requires some redefinition of the computational units to meet the basic requirement of having at least 2 PSUs per stratum.
5. The above-mentioned problem arises more frequently and seriously when computing sampling errors for subclasses (subpopulations or other small domains). The risk can be reduced by aggregating PSUs and strata to create fewer, larger computational units.

Though information of the above type on sample structure is collected in all EU-SILC surveys, unfortunately not all of it is included in the micro data available in the public domain to researcher. This restriction on making essential information available results from various policy considerations, some justifiable but other not so justified. In any case, lacking such information in complex samples makes it impossible to compute valid estimates of sampling error. Lack of information on sample structure in survey data files is a surprisingly persistent problem (for two examples covering a long period, see KISH et al. (1976), VERMA et al. (2010a)).

7.1.3.3 Data subset used for the present research

Thanks to a research cooperation with the OECD (PIACENTINI, 2014), we have access for Spain not only to the public cross-sectional 2011 EU-SILC data (UDB), but also to not generally available variables concerning the sample structure, namely: the code for regions at NUTS 2³ level, sampling strata, and primary sampling units PSUs.

Generally, the EU-SILC national surveys are designed with focus on the production of reliable estimates at the national level. Analysis at the regional (subnational) level requires special procedures; see VERMA et al. (2010b) on robustness of EU-SILC based indicators at the regional level. However, Spain EU-SILC survey has a large sample: 13,109 households and 34,756 individuals (for 2011). This permits direct analysis not only at the national also at regional (NUTS 2) level. Since the regions mostly have fairly large sample sizes and form independent sampling domains, we can treat them as domains for comparative analysis, in a way similar to multi-country comparative analyses.

From the Spain EU-SILC 2011 Intermediate Quality Report (INE, 2012) we have a detailed description of the sample design that is important both for understanding whether regions form independent sampling domains, and for the construction of the ‘computational’ PSUs and strata. The available description of the design is as follows:

“The sample is selected following a two-stage design; the first-stage units are stratified. The first stage is made up of census sections. The second stage comprises main family addresses. There was no sub-sampling within those units; all households usually residing in those addresses were surveyed. . . . Each section is made up of around 400 addresses. The second-stage units are the principal family addresses selected for the sample in the census section.

In each Autonomous Community [self-ruling region], first-stage units were stratified by the size of the municipality to which the census section belonged.

The following strata were considered:

Stratum 0: Municipalities of over 500,000 population.

Stratum 1: Provincial capitals (other than the above).

Stratum 2: Municipalities of over 100,000 population (other than the above).

³ NUTS (*Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques*). These are 19 NUTS 2 region in Spain.

Stratum 3: Municipalities of 50,000 to 100,000 population (other than the above).

Stratum 4: Municipalities of 20,000 to 50,000 population (other than the above).

Stratum 5: Municipalities of 10,000 to 20,000 population.

Stratum 6: Municipalities of under 10,000 population.

An independent sample was designed in each Autonomous Community to represent it, because one of INE's survey objectives is to provide data at this level of disaggregation.

To achieve the survey objective of producing acceptably reliable estimates at both the national and at the Autonomous Community (regional) level, we selected, in wave 1 (survey 2004), a sample of 16,000 addresses spread over 2000 census sections. We distributed the sample across Autonomous Communities by allocating one part uniformly and another part in proportion to Autonomous Community size. The uniform part accounted for about 40% of sections.”

From this description, it is clear that regions in Spain are treated as sampling domains, and also how strata and PSUs were constructed. Variables DB040, DB050 and DB060 define, respectively, the region, stratum and PSU for each unit in the micro dataset. The first two variables together define unique strata within each region separately. Using the sample description and the above three variables makes it possible to define the computation strata and PSUs for variance estimation.

7.1.3.4 Construction of computational strata and PSUs

(1) The strata are confined within regions. The regional and the PSU codes in combination directly identify unique computational strata for estimating variances in each region in most cases. In a very few cases (around 10 in all, i.e. on the average less than one per region) a stratum contained only a single PSU. Since the computation procedure requires at least two PSUs per stratum, any stratum containing a single unit was merged with another stratum to provide the final computational stratum.

(2) By design, each PSU should be confined to lie within a single stratum. However, we

found that in some cases, the PSU extended across more than one stratum and occasionally even across different regions. These cases represent a misspecification of the PSU code in the rotating panel design of the survey. For each unit in the sample, the code should specify the *original* PSU where the unit was selected. By design, the original PSUs are confined to lie within strata. It appears that these erroneous cases concern persons who have moved their residence since the survey round they originally entered the sample, and in error, the given code identifies their current rather than the original PSU. Mostly, a bulk of the sample cases in problem PSUs were found within the same stratum, and only a very small proportion (the ‘mover’) were coded to be in a different stratum. There is no way to identify the original PSU in such cases from the information available. In each stratum such ‘movers’ were grouped to form a new, separate PSU in the stratum. In this way the resulting computational PSUs did not cut across computational strata, as required by the design with independent sampling within regions, and also by the variance estimation procedure.

(3) Finally, we found some PSUs with a very few sample cases. When the number of adult persons in a PSU was less than 6, we collapsed the PSU with other PSU(s) such that the resulting computational PSU contained at least 6 persons.

In practice, the above procedure was quite long and demanding, but not complex, and yielded appropriate computational PSUs and strata.

7.1.4 Empirical analysis

Using the numerical data described in Section 7.1.3, this section presents analysis of the estimates of sampling errors for poverty and deprivation related variables. The separate results for each of the 19 regions of Spain allow analysis from a comparative perspective.

7.1.4.1 Statistics analysed

Using the numerical data described in Section 7.1.3, this section presents analysis of the estimates of sampling errors for poverty and deprivation related variables. The separate results for each of the 19 regions of Spain allow analysis from a comparative perspective.

The following basic statistics are considered in turn: mean equivalised income (INC); conventional at-risk-of-poverty rate (ARPR); fuzzy monetary poverty rate (FM); and fuzzy supplementary deprivation rate (FS). These statistics refer, respectively, to mean values

of micro-level variables y_i , z_i , $\mu_{i,1}$ and $\mu_{i,2}$ defined below.

Equivalised income (y_i)

For this variable, total disposable income of each household from all sources and all members for the preceding calendar year is ‘equivalised’ by dividing it by ‘equivalised size’ of the household (E). In the standard Eurostat database used here, E is defined as

$$E = 1 + 0.5(A-1) + 0.3C$$

with A as the number of adults (taken as persons aged 14 and over), and C the number of children aged under 14. In the following analysis, however, for consistency with a parallel OECD research, we have used the definition generally used by OECD, namely

$$E = H^{1/2},$$

where H is the total household size, $H = A + C$.

The equivalised income (y_i) is then ascribed to the household and to each of its members and forms the required analytical variable for studying income distribution of the population. Individual persons with the equivalised income so assigned are the units of analysis in all results presented here.

The data contain a few negative values for household income; these were set to zero for the analysis.

Figure 7.1 shows the frequency distribution of the sample according to increasing equivalised income (y_i). As is well known, the distribution is heavily skewed to the left. (The illustration is for the region with the largest sample size in our data, namely ES61 Andalucía.)

Conventional propensity to poverty (z_i)

Persons with equivalised income (y_i) below the poverty line (P), $y_i < P$, are defined as poor, with $z_i = 1$; others are non-poor, with $z_i = 0$. Following Eurostat, P is taken as 60% of the median equivalised income of the population. This parameter is defined separately for each region, based on its income distribution.

Fuzzy propensity to monetary poverty ($\mu_{i,1}$)

This refers to $\mu_{i,1}$ defined in equations (1) and (2). Subscript $K = 1$ corresponds to monetary poverty. As noted in Section 7.1.1.3, parameter α_1 in these equations is taken

Figure 7.1: Illustration of equivalised income distribution

to be a fixed parameter of the income distribution of the population, determined in practice such that the fuzzy poverty rate FM becomes numerically identical to the corresponding conventional poverty rate ARPR.

Fuzzy propensity to non-monetary (supplementary) deprivation ($\mu_{i,2}$)

This refers to $\mu_{i,2}$ defined in equations (1) and (2). Subscript $K = 2$ corresponds to non-monetary deprivation. As above, parameter α_2 in these equations is taken to be a fixed parameter. It is also determined such that the fuzzy supplementary rate FS becomes numerically identical to the corresponding conventional poverty rate ARPR.

Figure 7.2 provides an illustration of the distribution of the conventional and fuzzy measures of poverty/deprivation in the sample. (These are based on the same dataset as Figure 7.1.). Data are sorted by the ranking of the variable concerned.

7.1.4.2 Simplified variance estimation

Mean equivalised income (mean of y_i values; INC) is an ordinary ratio and its variance is estimated using JRR in a straightforward manner, on the lines described in Section 4. The mean z_i is recomputed using each replicated sample, and the variability between these

Figure 7.2: Illustration of distribution of conventional and fuzzy measures of poverty/deprivation

replicated estimates provides an estimate of variance of INC using equation (7.4).

The situation is more complex in the case of conventional and fuzzy measures of poverty/deprivation. These measures differ from simple ratios in that the variable being averaged is not a predetermined quantity for the individual unit concerned (unlike income y_i for instance), but depends on parameters of the whole distribution which are themselves estimated from the sample. For example, conventional propensity to poverty, z_i , depends on parameter P , the poverty line, itself determined from the sample. In constructing estimate ARPR for JRR replications, we have two options:

(i) Simplified variance estimator

Parameter P is estimated only once from the full sample, which assigns a specific value to z_i for each unit in the sample. From one replication to another, the sample units are changed (and reweighted) as described earlier, but for any units included the already determined values z_i are not changed. The resulting variance estimation amounts to treating the more complex statistic ARPR as an ordinary ratio, just like mean income INC.

(ii) More precise variance estimator

In each JRR replication, parameter P is re-estimated using the replication sample, re-

sulting also in redefinition of z_i values for (at least some) individual units. The resulting variance estimation takes into account the complexity of statistic ARPR. Similarly for FM and FS, the sample dependent parameters involved are their corresponding cumulative distributions F and L defined in equation equation (7.2).

Concerning statistics more complex than ratios, the JRR procedure tends to perform well for the so-called ‘U statistics’ (EFRON, 1982) such as Gini coefficient and other statistics involving cumulation of the income distribution. More generally, this applies to variance estimation of parameters which are smooth functions of sample aggregates. By contrast, an often noted drawback of the Jackknife method is that it may not provide a consistent variance estimation for non-smooth statistics, such as the median or quantiles of the income distribution which are involved in the definition of measures such as ARPR. EFRON (1982) in section 3.4 provides a simple demonstration of this inconsistency for the median.

However, in practical application to survey data based on multistage sampling, we have generally found the JRR method to work well, producing results very comparable for example to those using the linearization method (VERMA and BETTI, 2011). This may result from several factors.

Firstly, the above mentioned demonstration of inconsistency assumes the basic ‘delete one-unit at a time’ Jackknife applied to a simple random sample of elements. SHAO and WU (1989) show that this deficiency of the basic Jackknife method can be rectified by constructing replications by deleting a number of observations simultaneously. We consider it plausible that a similar effect holds in the application of the method to clustered samples, where a whole PSU is deleted even in the basic ‘delete one unit at a time’ version. The problem is further controlled by grouping small PSUs to construct more appropriate computational units, as is often done in practice. Nevertheless, JRR variance estimates for measures such as ARPR based on the median or other quantiles are definitely less stable than those for measures involving cumulation of the income distribution. This may be noted from column (10) of Table 7.2 of our numerical application presented later in the paper, albeit in part because they are based on relatively small samples for individual region in Spain.

Secondly, it is not obvious that the inconsistency problem is more serious in the case of the ‘more precise variance estimator’, (ii), which involves repeated computation of median income to compute ARPR at each replication, compared to the simplified version

(i), where the full-sample median is used as a fixed parameter for each replication. In fact, estimation (ii) has been generally found to have smaller variance, i.e. there is less variability among samples when sample dependence of the median is taken into account in estimating ARPR. See for instance BERGER and SKINNER (2003), VERMA and BETTI (2011). OĞUZ-ALPER and BERGER (2015) test this observation for estimates of net change or trend in conventional poverty rates. The last mentioned authors note that, while variance of the poverty rate can be expected, and generally found, to be smaller when the variability of the poverty threshold is taken into account, this may not necessary apply to the case of variance of net change; nevertheless, in their application (to Turkish EU-SILC survey data), they found this to be the case also for measures of change, albeit to a reduced extent.

Thirdly, for FM and FS, the sample dependent parameters involved are the corresponding cumulative distribution F and L defined in equation equation (7.2), rather than involving explicit dependence on the median as in the case of conventional ARPR. This reduces the problem of numerical instability or inconsistency of the variance estimates.

In any case, in extending variance estimation to fuzzy measures, our analysis at this stage will be confined mainly to the simplified approach, (i).

First, we discuss numerical results of the computation of sampling errors for ARPR in more detail.

7.1.4.3 Sampling error computations for ARPR

Table 7.2 shows estimates of sampling error and design effects for ARPR for each of the 19 regions of Spain. Columns (1)-(8) give the simplified estimates (i) treating the statistic as an ordinary ratio. The regions are ordered according to decreasing sample size n , column equation (7.2), to bring out more clearly the pattern of results. The remaining columns are as follows.

Col. (3) m : at-risk-of poverty rate ARPR

Col. (4) se : standard error of ARPR

Col. (5) $rse\%$: relative standard error of ARPR, $=se/m$ (%)

Col. (6) cv : coefficient of variation among values of conventional propensity to poverty, z_i , among units in the population

Col. (7) $rse(srs)$: estimate of relative standard error under the assumption of simple random sampling,⁴ $= cv/\sqrt{n}$

Col. (8) $deft$: design effect $= rse/rse(srs)$, defined here as the ratio of *standard errors* – standard error of the statistic under the actual complex sample design, divided by what the standard error would be under a simple random sample of the same size.⁵

Table 7.2: Variance estimates for ARPR

(1)	(2)	Simplified variance estimates						More precise variance estimates	
		(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)=(9)/(4)
Region	n	mean (m)	se	$rse=se/m\%$	$cv\%$	$rse(srs)$	$deft$	$se(var)$	$se(var)/se$
ES61	4,136	0.217	0.013	5.88	189.7	2.95	1.99	0.015	1.19
ES51	3,625	0.208	0.014	6.73	195.2	3.24	2.08	0.013	0.94
ES30	3,243	0.229	0.018	7.83	183.3	3.22	2.43	0.011	0.59
ES52	2,69	0.188	0.016	8.53	208.0	4.01	2.13	0.026	1.64
ES11	2,388	0.190	0.016	8.47	206.3	4.22	2.01	0.015	0.91
ES41	2,183	0.239	0.020	8.26	178.7	3.82	2.16	0.015	0.78
ES42	1,94	0.201	0.024	11.94	199.7	4.53	2.63	0.028	1.18
ES21	1,847	0.217	0.021	9.81	189.7	4.41	2.22	0.019	0.87
ES70	1,679	0.227	0.024	10.39	184.5	4.50	2.31	0.020	0.83
ES24	1,617	0.221	0.023	10.20	187.5	4.66	2.19	0.019	0.83
ES12	1,417	0.161	0.017	10.32	228.2	6.06	1.70	0.019	1.15
ES43	1,395	0.196	0.023	11.84	202.4	5.42	2.18	0.022	0.97
ES62	1,383	0.199	0.026	13.10	200.5	5.39	2.43	0.023	0.88
ES23	1,156	0.243	0.029	12.08	176.3	5.19	2.33	0.027	0.91
ES22	1,135	0.186	0.026	14.21	209.2	6.21	2.29	0.028	1.04
ES13	1,111	0.219	0.028	12.83	189.0	5.67	2.26	0.039	1.38
ES53	1,005	0.234	0.020	8.58	181.0	5.71	1.50	0.027	1.37
ES63	438	0.238	0.052	21.72	179.1	8.56	2.54	0.043	0.83
ES64	368	0.295	0.060	20.24	154.5	8.06	2.51	0.047	0.78
	mean	0.216	0.025	11.21	191.7	5.04	2.20	0.024	0.97
	$cv\%$	13.3	48.4	36.6	8.3	29.6	12.6	41.7	26.4

The remaining columns report some results for the more precise variance estimate, (ii), treating statistic ARPR in its full complexity:

Col. (9) $se(var)$: more precise standard error estimates when sampling variability in the value of parameter P is taken into account.

Col. (10) $se(var)/se$: The more precise computations generally give lower estimates for variance. The average value of the ratio of standard errors $se(var)/se$ in Table 7.2 is 0.97,

⁴ Note that the above expression for $rse(srs)$ is valid only under the simplifying assumption that the statistic being considered, ARPR, is an ordinary ratio. More elaborate estimation procedures are normally required for more complex statistics; see for instance VERMA and BETTI (2011).

⁵ It is common to present design effects, written as $deff$ or $deft2$, as ratio of variances rather than of standard errors. In any case, the above are rather large design effects. A part of them arises simply from the fact that income in our data has been measured at the household level but is analysed at the person level. This factor by itself inflates $deft$ by a factor equal to square root of average household size \sqrt{H} .

i.e. estimate of variance is lower by 6%. Previous researchers, for instance BERGER and SKINNER (2003) and VERMA and BETTI (2011), have reported similar, though often larger, effects.

The two rows under the table show simple average of the estimate over the regions, and the coefficient of its variation across regions.

7.1.4.4 Comparison among the four variables

Table 7.3 shows for each variable the following quantities. The table is based on the same data as Table 7.2, and is similarly sorted.

Col. (1) rse%: relative standard error of estimate

Col. (2) cv%: coefficient of variation among units in the population

Col. (3) deft: design effect= $rse/(cv/\sqrt{n})$, where n is the sample size. This is the ratio of standard error of the statistic under the actual complex sample design, to what the error would be under a simple random sample of the same size.

Table 7.3: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

region	n	Mean eq income (INC)			Fuzzy monetary (FM)			Fuzzy supplementary (FS)			Conventional poverty rate (ARPR)		
		rse%	cv%	deft	rse%	cv%	deft	rse%	cv%	deft	rse%	cv%	deft
ES61	4,136	2.49	71.4	2.25	4.32	136.0	2.04	5.80	126.8	2.94	5.88	189.7	1.99
ES51	3,625	2.15	57.6	2.25	4.67	133.7	2.10	5.31	130.7	2.45	6.73	195.2	2.08
ES30	3,243	3.23	60.1	3.07	6.08	124.6	2.78	6.28	121.7	2.94	7.83	183.3	2.43
ES52	2,69	2.57	59.8	2.23	6.69	147.4	2.35	6.62	140.3	2.45	8.53	208.0	2.13
ES11	2,388	2.32	62.3	1.82	6.28	145.6	2.11	5.63	138.5	1.99	8.47	206.3	2.01
ES41	2,183	2.97	61.3	2.26	6.26	122.3	2.39	7.64	118.1	3.02	8.26	178.7	2.16
ES42	1,94	4.53	69.8	2.86	8.56	139.5	2.70	10.87	133.5	3.58	11.94	199.7	2.63
ES21	1,847	2.80	55.8	2.15	6.74	130.7	2.22	8.25	126.3	2.81	9.81	189.7	2.22
ES70	1,679	4.57	80.1	2.34	6.78	126.4	2.20	9.35	122.6	3.12	10.39	184.5	2.31
ES24	1,617	3.82	56.6	2.71	7.51	131.9	2.29	7.57	124.9	2.44	10.20	187.5	2.19
ES12	1,417	2.68	59.0	1.71	7.69	158.7	1.82	8.06	153.9	1.97	10.32	228.2	1.70
ES43	1,395	3.54	70.6	1.87	9.00	141.0	2.38	7.57	136.3	2.07	11.84	202.4	2.18
ES62	1,383	3.58	56.1	2.37	9.40	140.7	2.48	12.30	133.9	3.41	13.10	200.5	2.43
ES23	1,156	4.39	63.4	2.36	8.49	120.9	2.39	9.75	118.6	2.80	12.08	176.3	2.33
ES22	1,135	4.62	54.1	2.88	10.00	141.4	2.38	9.04	140.4	2.17	14.21	209.2	2.29
ES13	1,111	4.27	62.4	2.28	9.05	130.5	2.31	8.35	127.1	2.19	12.83	189.0	2.26
ES53	1,005	3.97	59.9	2.10	8.07	125.8	2.03	10.74	121.1	2.81	8.58	181.0	1.50
ES63	438	9.49	68.2	2.91	12.03	119.4	2.11	17.94	120.9	3.10	21.72	179.1	2.54
ES64	368	9.55	73.2	2.50	14.87	102.2	2.79	19.61	100.8	3.73	20.24	154.5	2.51
mean		4.08	63.2	2.36	8.02	132.6	2.31	9.30	128.2	2.74	11.21	191.7	2.20
cv%		50.9	11.1	16.0	31.0	9.5	11.2	41.3	8.9	19.5	36.6	8.3	12.6

The average value of relative standard error is the lowest for INC (4.1%) and the highest for ARPR (11.2%). The fuzzy indicators have intermediate values: FM (8.0%), and FS (9.3%). This pattern of results persists for individual regions in most cases.

Design effects are very similar for INC, FM and ARPR – averaged over regions roughly

in the range 2.20-2.35. The values for FS are somewhat higher, around 2.75 averaged over the regions. Again, this pattern of results persists for individual regions, though with somewhat greater variability. Apart from the effect of sample size and of some differences in design effects, the population coefficient of variation follows the variation in estimated relative standard errors. The most important conclusion is that fuzzy measures of poverty and deprivation are subject to smaller variance than the traditional poverty rate. Averaged over the regions, the relative values are $ARPR = 1.00$, $FS = 0.83$, $FM = 0.72$, and of course much lower for the very different statistic $INC = 0.36$. This represents a significant advantage of the fuzzy over conventional poverty measures.

7.1.5 To summarize

In this section we have presented a robust computational methodology for variance estimation for multi-dimensional measures of poverty and deprivation of households and individuals, derived from sample surveys with complex designs and fairly large sample sizes. This computational methodology is applied in a multi-domain and comparative context. The methodology proposed uses the JRR method.

The primary result obtained is the extension of variance estimation to beyond measures of monetary poverty, specifically to fuzzy formulation of those measures and, as a corollary, to multidimensional measures of deprivation which by their very nature are a matter of degree i.e. are fuzzy. This is complemented by a the description and numerical illustration of computational procedures, and the difficulties in producing reliable and robust estimates of sampling error for complex statistics.

An important substantive finding of the paper is that fuzzy measures tend to be subjected to reduced sampling error, compared to conventional measures of poverty for a given sample size and design. However, the actual magnitude of the increased sampling precision is uncertain because the simplified variance estimation used here.

In our future research, we intend to extend our computational procedures to produce more precise variance estimates of fuzzy measures, namely by taking into account changes in parameters of the distribution from one JRR replication to another. Our expectation on theoretical considerations is that this would further increase the advantage of fuzzy over conventional measures in terms of sampling precision.

Another, even more ambitious, area of estimation would be deal with fuzzy longitudinal

measures of deprivation, beyond the cross-sectional measures addressed here.

7.2 Fuzzy measures of longitudinal poverty in a comparative perspective

As presented in the previous section, for understanding poverty and social exclusion, it is necessary to consider deprivation simultaneously in its multiple dimensions – low income as well as diverse non-monetary aspects of deprivation. Furthermore, these multiple aspects must be considered longitudinally, identifying the extent to which households and individuals are subject to persistent deprivation. Using fuzzy set representation of individual propensities, this section presents a methodology for and longitudinal analysis of monetary and multi-dimensional poverty and deprivation in a multi-country comparative context.

In the recent literature, several papers have focussed on constructing measures of lifetime or intertemporal poverty; see, for example, PORTER and QUINN (2013), CALVO and DERCON (2009), HOY and ZHENG (2011), BOSSERT et al. (2012), GRADIN et al. (2012), MENDOLA and BUSETTA (2012). DUCLOS et al. (2010) propose measures of chronic and transient poverty but these categories apply to aggregates and not to individuals.

HULME and SHEPHERD (2003) have described the chronically poor as follows: “... *intuitively, we are talking about people who remain poor for much of their life course, and who may ‘pass on’ their poverty to subsequent generations...*”. However, the specific criterion used to identify the chronically poor (and hence the transiently poor) is a subject of continuing debate. FOSTER and SANTOS (2013) distinguish two identification approaches: a *counting approach* and a *permanent income approach*.

In more specific terms, the present contribution represents a continuation and further development in a longitudinal perspective of the work of CHELI and LEMMI (1995), and BETTI et al. (2008)⁶. Aspects of this methodology have been applied at cross sectional level in BETTI et al. (2015a).

There are several advantages of treating poverty and deprivation as a matter of degree, applicable to all members of the population, rather than as simply a ‘yes-no’ state.

1. Further insight into the relative income situations of individuals and groups can be

⁶ Other authors have also contributed to the construction of fuzzy measures of longitudinal poverty, by following alternative approaches. Among others, see CHELI and BETTI (1999), BETTI et al. (2002) and BETTI et al. (2004).

obtained by incorporating into the poverty rates a measure of the actual levels of incomes received, particularly at the lower end of the income distribution.

2. Non-monetary deprivation depends on forced non-access to various facilities or possessions determining the basic conditions of life. An individual may have access to some but not to others. Hence non-monetary deprivation is inherently a matter of degree, and some *quantitative approach* such as the present one is essential.
3. More important is the potential of this approach in studying poverty (or more generally, deprivation in multiple dimensions) in the *longitudinal* context. The conventional approach measures mobility simply in terms of movements across some designated poverty line, and does not reflect the actual magnitude of the changes affecting individuals at all points in the distribution. Consequently, the degree of mobility of persons near to the chosen line tends to be over-emphasised, while that of persons far from that line largely ignored.

7.2.1 Fuzzy set operations appropriate for the analysis of poverty and deprivation

Fuzzy measures have been presented in the previous section, we turn now to rules for the manipulation of multiple fuzzy sets which are appropriate for analysis of deprivation longitudinally and/or in multiple dimensions. In this section we consider a pair of fuzzy sets. These could refer to the propensity to deprivation at two points in time (e.g. for a panel of individuals), or to the propensity to deprivation in two dimensions (e.g. monetary and non-monetary). The formal treatment of the two situations is identical.⁷

Let (μ_1, μ_2) be the propensities to poverty of an individual at times (1, 2). In conventional (non-fuzzy, ‘crisp’) analysis each of these is a $\{0,1\}$ dichotomy. At any given time t there are two possible states, namely of ‘poverty’ ($\mu_t = 1$), and of ‘non-poverty’ ($\mu_t = 0$ or its complement $\bar{\mu}_t = 1$); the two states are exhaustive and mutually exclusive, meaning ($\mu_t + \bar{\mu}_t = 1$).

Fuzzy set operations are a generalisation of the corresponding ‘crisp’ set operations in the sense that the former reduce to (exactly reproduce) the latter when the fuzzy membership functions, being in the whole range $[0,1]$, are reduced to a $\{0,1\}$ dichotomy. Again, at any given time t there are two possible states, ‘poverty’ with propensity $0 \leq \mu_t \leq 1$ and

⁷ Arbitrarily, we will express the following in terms of longitudinal poverty at two points in time.

‘non-poverty’ with propensity $0 \leq \bar{\mu}_t \leq 1$. In the crisp formulation, only one of the above two quantities is non-zero, and an individual belongs uniquely to one or the other of the two states. In fuzzy formulation, generally both the quantities are non-zero, specifying the degree to which an individual belongs to each of the two states. In common with the crisp formulation, these propensities satisfy the constraint ($\mu_t + \bar{\mu}_t = 1$) covering the two possible states.

Considering a pair of two time points, there are four possible states, say PP, PN, NP and NN, where P stands for the state of poverty and N for non-poverty. An individual’s propensities to belong to the four states are given by the intersections as shown below. Since these states are exhaustive, the propensities must add up to 1. This condition is satisfied in the crisp formulation since for any individual only one of these quantities is non-zero and equals 1. While fuzzy set operations are generalisations of corresponding ‘crisp’ operations, there is, however, *more than one way in which the fuzzy set operations can be formulated*, each representing an equally valid generalisation of the corresponding crisp set operations. The choice among alternative formulations has to be made primarily on substantive grounds: some options are more appropriate (meaningful, useful, illuminating, convenient) than others, depending on the context and objectives of the application. In this paper we seek a formulation suitable *specifically for the study of poverty and deprivation*.

The book by KLIR and YUAN (1995) provides an excellent discussion of different types of fuzzy operations, of which the main ones are reported in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

Operation	Fuzzy formulation			
		Standard	Algebraic	Bounded
Intersection	$\mu_1 \cap \mu_2$	$\min(\mu_1, \mu_2)$	$\mu_1 \mu_2$	$\max(0, \mu_1 + \mu_2 - 1)$
Union	$\mu_1 \cup \mu_2$	$\max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 - \mu_1 \mu_2$	$\min(1, \mu_1 + \mu_2)$

Application to the four possible states mentioned above gives the results reported in Table 7.5, where $s_1 = \min(\mu_1, \mu_2)$ and $s_2 = \max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$. Here, the Standard and Bounded operations violate the basic requirement that the propensities for the four mutually exclusive and exhaustive states add up to 1: generally the sum exceeds 1 with the Standard and falls short of 1 with the Bounded operation. The basic requirement is met by the Algebraic operation. However, this operation can give rather unreasonable results in the context of poverty analysis. This can be seen most simply by considering an individual

whose propensity to poverty remains constant from one period to another: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu$. It is reasonable to take the individual's propensity to be in continuous poverty (state PP) to be this constant value μ . However, the Algebraic operation gives it as μ^2 , a generally lower value.⁸

Graphical representation helps in clarifying what the different fuzzy set operations imply. Standard intersection is the overlap between two propensities (μ_1, μ_2) placed on a common base, clearly seen from the following diagram to equal $\min(\mu_1, \mu_2)$; similarly, Standard union can be seen to equal $\max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$. This operation maximises the intersection and minimises the union between the sets. Bounded intersection between (μ_1, μ_2) is, by contrast, the overlap between μ_1 and $\bar{\mu}_2$, the complement of μ_2 . It can be seen from the diagram to equal $\max(0, \mu_1 + \bar{\mu}_2 - 1)$; similarly, union can be seen to equal $\min(1, \mu_1 + \bar{\mu}_2)$. This operation minimises the intersection and maximises the union between the sets.

Figure 7.3:

The above interpretation suggests that if the Standard operation between two sets (μ_1, μ_2) is appropriate for sets representing the same or similar state (e.g. (μ_1, μ_2) both being propensities to poverty), then the Bounded operation is appropriate for sets representing opposite or dissimilar states (e.g. poverty μ_1 and non-poverty $\bar{\mu}_2$).⁹ This leads us the Composite operation appropriate for longitudinal and multidimensional analysis of poverty and deprivation, defined in Table 7.6, where $s_1 = \min(\mu_1, \mu_2)$ and $s_2 = \max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$.

The Composite operation satisfies the basic requirement that the propensities for the four mutually exclusive and exhaustive states add up to 1. This operation also gives reasonable results in the context of poverty analysis. Returning to the earlier example

⁸ To meet the above-mentioned requirement, a fuzzy operation should satisfy the intuitively and substantively desirable condition called 'idempotency', meaning $(\mu \cap \mu) = (\mu \cup \mu) = \mu$. In fact the Standard operation is the only one which satisfies this condition (KLIR and YUAN, 1995).

⁹ Algebraic operation is represented by placing one of the sets (say μ_2) proportionately over the other set (μ_1) and its complement ($\bar{\mu}_1 = 1 - \mu_1$), in the sense that proportion $\mu_1\mu_2$ overlaps and proportion $(1 - \mu_1)\mu_2$ does not. This operation would be appropriate for sets which represent unrelated or independent dimensions.

Table 7.5: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

State	Intersection	Standard		Algebraic		Bounded	
		$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$			$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$
PP	$\mu_1 \cap \mu_2$	$\min(\mu_1, \mu_2) = s_1$	s_1	$\mu_1 \mu_2$	$\max(0, \mu_1 + \mu_2 - 1) = 0$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$
PN	$\mu_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2$	$\min(\mu_1, \bar{\mu}_2) = s_1$	$1 - s_2$	$\mu_1 \bar{\mu}_2 = \mu_1 - \mu_1 \mu_2$	$\max(0, \mu_1 - \mu_2) =$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$
NP	$\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \mu_2$	$\min(\bar{\mu}_1, \mu_2) = s_2$	$1 - s_1$	$\bar{\mu}_1 \mu_2 = \mu_2 - \mu_1 \mu_2$	$\max(0, \mu_2 - \mu_1) =$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$
NN	$\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2$	$\min(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2) = 1 - s_2$	$1 - s_2$	$\bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\mu}_2 = 1 - (\mu_1 + \mu_2) + \mu_1 \mu_2$	$\max(0, 1 - \mu_1 - \mu_2) = 1 - (s_1 + s_2)$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \leq 1$	$\mu_1 + \mu_2 > 1$
Sum	1	$1 + 2s_1$	$1 + 2(1 - s_2)$	1	$1 - 2s_1$	$\max[0, 1 - 2(1 - s_2)]$	

Table 7.6: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

State	intersection	Type of operation	Composite operation	
			$\mu_1 \leq \mu_2$	$\mu_1 > \mu_2$
PP	$\mu_1 \cap \mu_2$	Standard	$\min(\mu_1, \mu_2) = s_1$	s_1
PN	$\mu_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2$	Bounded	$\max(0, \mu_1 - \mu_2) = 0$	$s_2 - s_1$
NP	$\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \mu_2$	Bounded	$\max(0, \mu_2 - \mu_1) = s_2 - s_1$	0
NN	$\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2$	Standard	$\min(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2) = 1 - s_2$	$1 - s_2$
Sum			1	1

of an individual with constant propensity to poverty (μ) from one period to another, the individual's propensity to be in continuous poverty is also $(\mu \cap \mu) = \mu$, as it should obviously be. As another example, a person's propensity to be in poverty at any of the two periods is obtained consistently in any of the three ways:

- (i) as union of the two propensities: $\mu_1 \cup \mu_2 = \max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$, using the Standard operation;
- (ii) as complement of the state “never poor”: $1 - [1 - \max(\mu_1, \mu_2)] = \max(\mu_1, \mu_2)$; or
- (iii) as sum of the three states “PP”, “PN” and “NP”:

$$\min(\mu_1, \mu_2) + \max(0, \mu_1 - \mu_2) + \max(0, \mu_2 - \mu_1) = \max(\mu_1, \mu_2) .$$

As noted, the above framework for analysis of fuzzy sets applies equally to the analysis of multidimensional deprivation. Consider, for example, deprivation in two dimensions: monetary and non-monetary. Analysis of occurrence of deprivation in both dimensions simultaneously parallels the analysis of continuous poverty (poverty at both times); similarly, deprivation in either dimension parallels any-time poverty. Elsewhere, we have termed the first measure as “manifest deprivation”, and the second as “latent deprivation” (BETTI et al., 2008). In terms of propensities (FM, FS) of deprivation in the two dimensions, application of the Standard fuzzy operation gives

$$F_{\text{manifest}} = FM \cap FS = \min(FM, FS)$$

$$F_{\text{latent}} = FM \cup FS = \max(FM, FS).$$

7.2.2 Longitudinal analysis of deprivation conceptualized as a sequence of fuzzy states

In this section we extend the procedure presented in Section 7.2.1 so as to be able to handle in a consistent and substantively meaning manner the analysis of poverty over any

number of time periods (and also for any number of dimensions of deprivation).

The quantities below are defined at the level of individual analysis units. Ratios of their weighted totals would be subsequently used to consistent aggregated measures of longitudinal (and/or multidimensional) deprivation.

Consider an individual with *propensity to poverty*, over T points in time. The corresponding propensities to “non-poverty” are their complements, \bar{m}_N . Considering the two possible states, namely of being “poor” or “non-poor” at each point in time defines 2^T distinct sequences each of length T .

For a *particular sequence*, let X_P be the set of points at which an individual’s propensity of being poor is considered, and X_N be the set of remaining time points at which the propensity of interest is that of being non-poor. The individual’s propensity to follow that particular sequence in the intersection of the T quantities is m_{PN} .

Figure 7.4 provides an example of one such sequence over $T=6$ time points. The sequence consists of propensities of being poor at times $t = (1, 4 \text{ and } 5)$, and of being non-poor at times $t = (2, 3 \text{ and } 6)$.

(This example is one of 2^6 possible sequences for any individual).

The figure immediately gives the required intersection between the six propensities referred to above: it is simply the overlap between the smallest propensity to poverty in the “poor” set, say m_P , and the smallest propensity to non-poverty in the “non-poor” set, say \bar{m}_N . The result can be seen more clearly by ordering the cross-sections according to the magnitude of the propensities, as shown at the right in Figure 7.4.

Algebraically, the overlap can be seen to equal:

$$\max(0, m_P + \bar{m}_N - 1) = \max(0, m_P - M_N) \quad (7.6)$$

with $M_N = 1 - \bar{m}_N = \max(\mu_t, t \in X_N)$, the form on the right expresses the required intersection in terms of propensities to poverty throughout.

Note that equation (7.6) is simply the Bounded intersection between fuzzy quantities (propensity to poverty) m_P and M_N . To summarise, point membership function for a longitudinal sequence of poor/non-poor states is constructed as follows:

- 1) The Standard intersection of propensities to poverty at time points where the state of

Figure 7.4:

interest is that of being “poor” gives their overlap as:

$$m_P = \min(\mu_t, t \in X_P) \quad (7.7)$$

2) The Standard union of propensities to poverty at the remaining time points where the state of interest is that of being “non-poor” gives:

$$M_N = \max(\mu_t, t \in X_N) \quad (7.8)$$

3) The Bounded intersection of the above two quantities gives their overlap, i.e. joint membership function for the particular longitudinal pattern k, as:

$$J_k = \max(0, m_P - M_N), k = 1 \text{ to } 2^T \text{ equation (7.5)}$$

Conventional poverty analysis is a special case of the above. With μ_t a (0,1) dichotomy, only one of the J_k values equals 1 identifying the unique poor/non-poor pattern of the individual concerned; all other J values are zero. With fuzzy conceptualisation, while any J_k value may be non-zero, together they must satisfy the same basic marginal constraints as that in conventional analysis, namely $\sum_{k=1}^T J_k = 1$.

7.2.3 Applications and numerical illustrations

In this section we develop and illustrate some useful longitudinal measures of poverty using the framework developed above for the construction of fuzzy intersections. The numerical illustrations are based on longitudinal dataset of EU Statistics on Income and

Living Conditions (EU-SILC), which covers a four year panel (2009-2012) of respondents. We will refer to these four years as, respectively, year 1 to year 4.

7.2.3.1 Cross-sectional measures

As noted, conventional poverty rate is computed as the weighted population of individuals with equivalised income below the poverty line, taken as 60% of the national median equivalised income in standard analysis. The corresponding fuzzy measure is the weighted mean of appropriately defined propensities to poverty, or more generally monetary or non-monetary deprivation. It is important to reiterate that at the level of individual both fuzzy monetary (FM), and fuzzy supplementary (FS) propensities are scaled such that the resulting poverty/deprivation rates numerically equal the country corresponding cross-sectional poverty rate for each year.

$$r^{(*)} = \sum_i w_i (\sum_t \mu_t / T) / \sum_i w_i = \sum_i w_i \mu_i^* / \sum_i w_i \quad (7.9)$$

where μ_i^* is the average over time t , from 1 to T , for individual i , in a given country, with sample weights w_i . For each country the annual cross-sectional poverty rates have been averaged over the four years. Obviously these rates are identical for conventional and all fuzzy measures.

In the presentation of the results, countries have been ordered according to decreasing poverty rates in order to identify whether the observed patterns are related to the general level of poverty in the country. There is a wide range of variation across countries: the average cross-sectional poverty rates varying from 22.5% (Greece) to 6.7% (Iceland).

7.2.3.2 Measures over time

Let $\mu_{(t)}$ denote ordered series of T propensities to poverty for an individual in decreasing order of magnitude as:

$$\mu_{(1)} \geq \mu_{(2)} \geq \dots \geq \mu_{(T)} \quad (7.10)$$

As before, we use symbols “P” (poor) and “N” (non-poor) of elements to specify the 2^T possible patterns of the above sequence. The presence of symbols “-“ refers to a set of patterns; this symbol covers both possible values “P” and “N”. For example, with $T = 4$, two of the patterns can be “PNPN” and “PPPN”, while “P-PN” stands for the two patterns

combined.

In fuzzy conceptualisation, a person's propensity to be "poor for at least k years" is the sum of propensities over set of patterns each containing at least k "P"s. Consider the set of patterns (in the ordered set in (8)):

"PP... (k values) —....(remaining T-k values)".

The total propensity of this set of patterns is given by the Standard fuzzy intersection of k specified terms, i.e.:

$$\mu^{(k)} = \min(\mu_{(t)}, 1 \leq t \leq k) = \mu_{(k)}$$

Any other set which contains one (or more) "N" value(s) among the first k elements has zero propensity, say $\mu^{(k')}$:

$$\mu^{(k')} = \max(0, \mu_{(t'')} - \mu_{(t')}) = 0$$

where $1 \leq t' \leq k$ is an element which now has an "N", and $k < t'' \leq T$ has to have a "P" to keep the total number of "P" values in the set to be at least k. Hence the total propensity of the required set in order to estimate "poor for at least k years" remains $\mu_{(k)}$, the k^{th} smallest value in the T cross-sectional propensities to poverty.

Fuzzy equivalent of conventional "proportion poor at least for k years" is therefore given by:

$$r^{(k)} = \sum_i w_i \mu_{(k),i} / \sum_i w_i$$

Two cases of particular interest are:

Anytime poverty (equivalent to "poor for at least 1 year") rate:

$$r^{(1)} = \sum_i w_i \mu_{(1),i} / \sum_i w_i$$

Continuous poverty (equivalent to "poor for all the T years") rate:

$$r^{(T)} = \sum_i w_i \mu_{(T),i} / \sum_i w_i$$

Table 7.7 shows the longitudinal rates for k = 1-4, T = 4, compared to the average cross-sectional poverty rate (column (2)) for each country for three types of measures:

- (1) Conventional poverty;
- (2) Fuzzy monetary poverty (FM);
- (3) Fuzzy supplementary (non-monetary) deprivation (FS).

In all cases, ratio $r^{(1)}/r^{(*)}$ considerably exceeds 1.0, and the ratios $r^{84)}/r^{(*)}$ and $r^{(3)}/r^{(*)}$ are below 1.0 (the last one with a single exception in the whole table). In a small minority of cases we found $r^{(2)}/r^{(*)}$ to exceed 1.0. The last mentioned exceptional cases imply that, in the countries concerned, among persons poor for at least 2 of the 4 years, there is a relative high incidence of higher propensities to poverty. The truly remarkable conclusion from the Table 7.4 is that, compared to the fuzzy approach, the conventional approach tends to over-estimate the incidence of anytime poverty and underestimate the incidence of persistent poverty (the overall results for FM and FS are quite similar).

In Table 7.7 we have:

- (1): EU Member States. ranked according to decreasing poverty rate (col (2))
- (2): Conventional poverty rate averaged over 4 years for a panel
- (3): Ratio of rate of “poverty during any of the 4 years” to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (4): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during all of the 4 years” to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (5): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during last 3 years” to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (6): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during last 2 years” to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (7): “Combined ratio” is computed summing numerators and denominators over country of EU

We believe that this results from the fact that in conventional analysis even small changes in the income level around the poverty line (often resulting from reporting errors or random variability) can have a large impact on the estimates.

Table 7.8 further illuminates this effect. It shows that the effect tends to become stronger for measures of more persistent poverty. The ratios $r^{(2)}/r^{*}$, $r^{(3)}/r^{(2)}$, $r^{(4)}/r^{(3)}$ are all smaller than 1.0: this is as expected. However, in all cases the values are smaller with conventional than with fuzzy measures, indicating the increasing degree of relative under-

Table 7.7: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

(1)	Conventional measure						Fuzzy monetary (FM)						Fuzzy supplementary (FS)					
	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)		
country	cs	any/cs	con4/cs	con3/cs	con2/cs	any/cs	any/cs	con4/cs	con3/cs	con2/cs	any/cs	any/cs	con4/cs	con3/cs	con2/cs	any/cs		
1	EL	0.225	1.734	0.392	0.553	0.938	1.597	0.486	0.614	0.916	1.500	0.437	0.510	0.864	1.500	0.437	0.510	0.864
2	LV	0.213	1.823	0.407	0.601	0.941	1.597	0.461	0.641	0.932	1.609	0.468	0.617	0.858	1.609	0.468	0.617	0.858
3	ES	0.206	1.829	0.316	0.442	0.751	1.583	0.423	0.555	0.809	1.669	0.387	0.526	0.795	1.669	0.387	0.526	0.795
4	IT	0.195	1.624	0.453	0.621	0.965	1.473	0.527	0.676	0.953	1.723	0.387	0.496	0.822	1.723	0.387	0.496	0.822
5	LT	0.194	1.721	0.407	0.610	0.850	1.593	0.475	0.673	0.922	1.515	0.600	0.757	0.998	1.515	0.600	0.757	0.998
6	BG	0.180	1.626	0.474	0.647	0.906	1.591	0.577	0.744	1.017	1.611	0.662	0.840	1.136	1.611	0.662	0.840	1.136
7	PL	0.175	1.727	0.408	0.619	0.959	1.556	0.502	0.688	0.966	1.571	0.545	0.693	0.958	1.571	0.545	0.693	0.958
8	EE	0.174	1.692	0.427	0.645	0.935	1.547	0.496	0.655	0.953	1.584	0.481	0.638	0.902	1.584	0.481	0.638	0.902
9	UK	0.171	2.024	0.276	0.388	0.669	1.675	0.332	0.465	0.729	1.555	0.409	0.562	0.809	1.555	0.409	0.562	0.809
10	PT	0.170	1.720	0.432	0.593	0.817	1.597	0.520	0.670	0.927	1.817	0.452	0.610	0.947	1.817	0.452	0.610	0.947
11	MT	0.166	1.758	0.326	0.524	0.838	1.576	0.447	0.620	0.903	1.385	0.372	0.507	0.808	1.385	0.372	0.507	0.808
12	BE	0.163	1.768	0.409	0.607	0.867	1.573	0.467	0.621	0.850	1.517	0.416	0.535	0.824	1.517	0.416	0.535	0.824
13	LU	0.139	1.804	0.408	0.548	0.884	1.727	0.528	0.679	0.970	1.791	0.345	0.467	0.814	1.791	0.345	0.467	0.814
14	HU	0.131	1.758	0.426	0.620	0.999	1.710	0.482	0.660	1.015	1.667	0.465	0.671	1.052	1.667	0.465	0.671	1.052
15	CY	0.129	1.726	0.513	0.783	1.127	1.634	0.608	0.815	1.083	1.906	0.287	0.469	0.789	1.906	0.287	0.469	0.789
16	AT	0.116	2.111	0.248	0.348	0.616	2.151	0.438	0.591	0.965	2.198	0.542	0.730	1.092	2.198	0.542	0.730	1.092
17	FR	0.116	1.898	0.334	0.462	0.794	1.786	0.441	0.592	0.910	1.934	0.422	0.584	0.950	1.934	0.422	0.584	0.950
18	FI	0.111	1.693	0.441	0.612	0.868	1.708	0.561	0.719	1.007	2.037	0.411	0.568	0.887	2.037	0.411	0.568	0.887
19	NL	0.108	1.842	0.291	0.463	0.837	1.889	0.469	0.661	0.998	1.853	0.385	0.613	0.891	1.853	0.385	0.613	0.891
20	DK	0.104	1.686	0.519	0.769	1.047	2.055	0.711	0.905	1.269	2.245	0.438	0.667	1.170	2.245	0.438	0.667	1.170
21	SI	0.084	1.658	0.474	0.606	0.854	2.101	0.830	1.026	1.357	2.863	0.516	0.791	1.339	2.863	0.516	0.791	1.339
22	CZ	0.078	1.864	0.394	0.582	0.959	1.890	0.475	0.698	1.095	2.158	0.435	0.734	1.122	2.158	0.435	0.734	1.122
23	NO	0.077	1.738	0.438	0.636	0.933	1.756	0.485	0.693	0.979	2.045	0.399	0.622	0.965	2.045	0.399	0.622	0.965
24	IS	0.067	2.465	0.213	0.294	0.664	2.273	0.294	0.427	0.863	2.194	0.250	0.443	0.932	2.194	0.250	0.443	0.932
(7)	average EU	0.146	1.784	0.395	0.569	0.878	1.683	0.496	0.661	0.955	1.750	0.447	0.607	0.926	1.750	0.447	0.607	0.926
	maximum	0.225	2.465	0.519	0.783	1.127	2.273	0.830	1.026	1.357	2.863	0.662	0.840	1.339	2.863	0.662	0.840	1.339
	minimum	0.067	1.624	0.213	0.294	0.616	1.473	0.294	0.427	0.729	1.385	0.250	0.443	0.789	1.385	0.250	0.443	0.789

estimation of persistence poverty in the former approach. The same applies in reverse to the ratio ρ , indicating relative over-estimation of transient poverty in the conventional approach.

In Table 7.8 we have:

- (1): EU Member States, ranked according to decreasing poverty rate (col (2))
- (2): Conventional poverty rate averaged over 4 years for a panel
- (3): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during past 4 years” to “continuous poverty during past 3 years”
- (4): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during past 3 years” to “continuous poverty during past 2 years”
- (5): Ratio of rate of “continuous poverty during last 2 years” to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (6): Ratio of ever-poor over past 4 years to average cross-sectional poverty rate (col (2))
- (7): “Combined ratio” is computed summing numerators and denominators over country of EU

The third panel of Table 7.8 compares the ratios directly between the fuzzy and conventional approaches (by taking ratio of ratios). The pattern of the ratio of measures of persistent poverty is highly consistent across countries. With merely a couple of exceptions, ratios ρ_k , $k = 2, 3, 4$ are notably higher with the fuzzy compared to the conventional approach. While ratio ρ is lower with the fuzzy approach, as expected. However, it is little higher with the fuzzy compared to the conventional approach. This is the case mostly in richer northern European countries with low levels of poverty. Most of these countries use income registers to construct EU-SILC data; these registers are generally more accurate than survey interviews and more successful in capturing small but real changes in personal incomes.

7.2.3.3 Eurostat at-persistent-risk-of-poverty rate

This rate has been defined by Eurostat as the proportion of persons who are equation (7.1) poor in the current year (year 4); and were also poor in at least two of the preceding years (years 1, 2, 3).

In fuzzy formulation, this can be computed on the basis of the combined propensity of

Table 7.8: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

	Conventional measure						Fuzzy monetary (FM)						Ratio FM/conventional					
	(1) country	(2) cs	(3) cont4/cont3	(4) cont3/cont2	(5) cont2/cs	(6) any/cs	(3) cont4/cont3	(4) cont3/cont2	(5) cont2/cs	(6) any/cs	(3) cont4/cs	(4) cont3/cs	(5) cont2/cs	(6) any/cs	(3) cont4/cs	(4) cont3/cs	(5) cont2/cs	(6) any/cs
1	EL	0.225	0.710	0.589	0.938	1.734	0.792	0.670	0.916	1.597	1.240	1.110	0.977	0.921				
2	LV	0.213	0.676	0.639	0.941	1.823	0.719	0.688	0.932	1.597	1.134	1.067	0.991	0.876				
3	ES	0.206	0.715	0.588	0.751	1.829	0.761	0.686	0.809	1.583	1.339	1.258	1.078	0.865				
4	IT	0.195	0.729	0.644	0.965	1.624	0.779	0.710	0.953	1.473	1.163	1.089	0.988	0.907				
5	LT	0.194	0.667	0.717	0.850	1.721	0.706	0.730	0.922	1.593	1.168	1.104	1.084	0.926				
6	BG	0.180	0.733	0.715	0.906	1.626	0.775	0.731	1.017	1.591	1.215	1.148	1.123	0.979				
7	PL	0.175	0.659	0.646	0.959	1.727	0.730	0.712	0.966	1.556	1.231	1.111	1.007	0.901				
8	EE	0.174	0.662	0.689	0.935	1.692	0.758	0.688	0.953	1.547	1.163	1.016	1.018	0.915				
9	UK	0.171	0.711	0.579	0.669	2.024	0.715	0.637	0.729	1.675	1.205	1.199	1.089	0.828				
10	PT	0.170	0.728	0.726	0.817	1.720	0.777	0.723	0.927	1.597	1.205	1.130	1.134	0.928				
11	MT	0.166	0.622	0.626	0.838	1.758	0.721	0.686	0.903	1.576	1.371	1.182	1.078	0.896				
12	BE	0.163	0.674	0.700	0.867	1.768	0.752	0.731	0.850	1.573	1.142	1.023	0.981	0.890				
13	LU	0.139	0.745	0.620	0.884	1.804	0.778	0.700	0.970	1.727	1.293	1.238	1.097	0.957				
14	HU	0.131	0.687	0.621	0.999	1.758	0.731	0.650	1.015	1.710	1.130	1.063	1.016	0.972				
15	CY	0.129	0.655	0.695	1.127	1.726	0.746	0.752	1.083	1.634	1.185	1.040	0.961	0.947				
16	AT	0.116	0.713	0.566	0.616	2.111	0.742	0.613	0.965	2.151	1.764	1.696	1.567	1.019				
17	FR	0.116	0.722	0.582	0.794	1.898	0.746	0.650	0.910	1.786	1.324	1.281	1.147	0.941				
18	FI	0.111	0.720	0.706	0.868	1.693	0.780	0.714	1.007	1.708	1.273	1.174	1.161	1.009				
19	NL	0.108	0.629	0.553	0.837	1.842	0.709	0.662	0.998	1.889	1.608	1.427	1.191	1.025				
20	DK	0.104	0.675	0.734	1.047	1.686	0.785	0.713	1.269	2.055	1.369	1.177	1.212	1.219				
21	SI	0.084	0.783	0.709	0.854	1.658	0.809	0.756	1.357	2.101	1.749	1.693	1.589	1.267				
22	CZ	0.078	0.677	0.607	0.959	1.864	0.680	0.638	1.095	1.890	1.205	1.199	1.141	1.014				
23	NO	0.077	0.688	0.681	0.933	1.738	0.700	0.708	0.979	1.756	1.109	1.090	1.049	1.010				
24	IS	0.067	0.725	0.443	0.664	2.465	0.689	0.495	0.863	2.273	1.380	1.453	1.301	0.922				
(7)	average EU	0.146	0.693	0.648	0.878	1.784	0.750	0.692	0.955	1.683	1.268	1.179	1.096	0.945				
(8)	maximum	0.225	0.783	0.734	1.127	2.465	0.809	0.756	1.357	2.273	1.764	1.696	1.589	1.267				
(9)	minimum	0.067	0.622	0.443	0.616	1.624	0.680	0.495	0.729	1.473	1.109	1.016	0.961	0.828				

four (of the possible $2^4=16$) patterns:

$$r^{(EU)} = \sum w_i \mu_i^{(EU)} / \sum w_i$$

where for individual i

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^{(EU)} = & \min(\mu_4, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3) + \max(0, \min(\mu_4, \mu_2, \mu_3) - \mu_1) \\ & + \max(0, \min(\mu_4, \mu_1, \mu_3) - \mu_2) + \max(0, \min(\mu_4, \mu_1, \mu_2) - \mu_3) \end{aligned}$$

Equivalently, the above may be written as

$$\mu^{(EU)} = \min(\mu_{(3)}, \mu_4)$$

where $\mu_{(3)}$ is the 3rd largest (i.e. the 2nd smallest) of the four cross-sectional propensities μ_1 to μ_4 . Note the similarity of the measure “poor at least 3 of the 4 years”:

$$\mu^{(3)} = \mu_{(3)}$$

Table 7.9 compares the fuzzy measures of the rate, with the conventional measures published by Eurostat. Overall, the fuzzy version is over 10% higher, though there is considerable variability across individual countries.

This is quite a large difference in the at-persistent-risk-of-poverty rate between the conventional and fuzzy measures, and can have important policy implications. It should be recalled that the two approaches begin from identical cross-sectional poverty rate for each the 4 years being considered. The fuzzy approach indicates that, despite the cross-sectional poverty rates being identical, poverty at the individual level may be more persistent than appears on the basis of conventional analysis.

In Table 7.9 we have:

- (1): EU Member States, ranked according to decreasing poverty rate (col (2))
- (2): Conventional poverty rate averaged over 4 years for a panel
- (3): Traditional at-persistent risk of poverty rate computed by Eurostat
- (4): FM: persistent FM
- (5): Ratio of the two measures FM/traditional

Table 7.9: Dimensions identified by exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, and the corresponding item weights

	(1) country	(2) cs	(3) EUROSTAT	(4) FM	(5) RATIO (4)/(3)
1	EL	0.225	13.80	15.12	1.096
2	LV	0.213	12.30	14.64	1.190
3	ES	0.206	13.30	13.16	0.989
4	IT	0.195	13.10	14.30	1.092
5	LT	0.194	12.60	12.38	0.982
6	BG	0.180	12.90	14.09	1.092
7	PL	0.175	10.70	11.67	1.091
8	EE	0.174	12.00	11.90	0.992
9	UK	0.171	8.60	9.43	1.097
10	PT	0.170	11.40	12.05	1.057
11	MT	0.166	9.70	10.82	1.115
12	BE	0.163	9.90	10.29	1.039
13	LU	0.139	7.10	10.31	1.452
14	HU	0.131	8.40	8.67	1.032
15	CY	0.129	8.30	9.84	1.185
16	AT	0.116	8.70	8.75	1.006
17	FR	0.116	7.00	7.69	1.098
18	FI	0.111	7.40	8.69	1.175
19	NL	0.108	5.80	7.71	1.329
20	DK	0.104	5.70	9.32	1.635
21	SI	0.084	6.10	8.58	1.406
22	CZ	0.078	4.30	4.79	1.113
23	NO	0.077	6.60	5.13	0.777
24	IS	0.067	2.10	3.30	1.573
(7) Average EU		0.146	9.075	10.109	1.114

7.2.3.4 Rates of exits from and re-entry into poverty

The following three measures are shown in Table 7.10. In conventional framework the measures are:

- (I) E2: of persons poor in the preceding year (year 3), the proportion who have become non-poor in the current year (year 4).
- (II) E3: of persons poor in the preceding two years (years 2 and 3), the proportion who have become non-poor in the current year (year 4).
- (III) R3: of persons poor in year 2 but who become non-poor in year 3, the proportion who have re-entered poverty in year 4.

In the fuzzy formulation, ratio is taken of weighted sums of appropriate propensities. At the individual level, propensities in the numerator and in the denominator in terms of cross-sectional propensities μ_2 , μ_3 and μ_4 for years 2-4 are as follows:

(I) E2N: $\max(0, \mu_3 - \mu_4)$; E2D: μ_3

Note that two patterns PN and PP constitute the set P- with respective propensities:

$$\max(0, \mu_3 - \mu_4) + \min(\mu_3, \mu_4) = \mu_3$$

(II) E3N: $\max(0, \min(\mu_2, \mu_3) - \mu_4)$; E3D: $\min(\mu_2, \mu_3)$

(III) R3N: $\max(0, \min(\mu_2, \mu_4) - \mu_3)$; E3D: $\max(0, \mu_2 - \mu_3)$.

Exit measures E2 and E3 both arise from *change* in status from poverty to non-poverty. Hence in both cases. The conventional measure, compared to the fuzzy measure, over-estimates the change for reasons noted above. For example, averaged over countries, 35% of persons poor at year 3 move out of poverty in year 4 (E2), and 25% of those poor at years 2 and 3 are non-poor at year 4 (E3) according to the conventional measures. The corresponding figures for the fuzzy measures are under 30% and 20% respectively. The pattern is very consistent across individual countries. The ratio of fuzzy to conventional measures is under 1.0 in practically all cases. The picture is more mixed in the case of R3. This may be because the measure is affected by movement both into and out of poverty; also the denominator often involves relatively small numbers.

In most countries the ratio of fuzzy to conventional measures is in the range 0.9-1.2. Larger values exist in a number of countries, often 'register' countries making the overall fuzzy to conventional ratio a little larger than 1.0 (=1.06).

In Table 7.10 we have:

E2: ratio (poor year 2, but not year 3)/(poor year 2)

E3: ratio (poor year 2 and 3, but not year 4)/(poor year 2 and 3)

R3: ratio (poor year 2 and not poor 3, but not year 4)/(poor year 2 and not poor 3)

Row (7): for RATIO FM/Conventional, "combined ratio" is computed summing numerators and denominators over country of EU

Table 7.10: Comparison of variance estimates for INC, FM, FS and ARPR

(1) country	(2) Conventional measure			Fuzzy monetary (FM)			Ratio FM/conventional				
	cs	E2	E3	R3	E2	E3	R3	E2	E3	R3	
1	EL	0.225	0.335	0.233	0.248	0.278	0.169	0.295	0.829	0.727	1.186
2	LV	0.213	0.352	0.235	0.306	0.307	0.196	0.325	0.872	0.831	1.060
3	ES	0.206	0.406	0.305	0.377	0.325	0.211	0.380	0.800	0.693	1.008
4	IT	0.195	0.305	0.198	0.340	0.237	0.158	0.344	0.778	0.798	1.013
5	LT	0.194	0.394	0.256	0.302	0.317	0.187	0.285	0.805	0.730	0.946
6	BG	0.180	0.248	0.204	0.318	0.214	0.177	0.221	0.862	0.865	0.693
7	PL	0.175	0.311	0.230	0.165	0.263	0.167	0.243	0.846	0.728	1.425
8	EE	0.174	0.318	0.202	0.376	0.247	0.156	0.287	0.776	0.770	0.763
9	UK	0.171	0.500	0.387	0.303	0.409	0.251	0.307	0.817	0.648	1.015
10	PT	0.170	0.313	0.200	0.249	0.252	0.173	0.308	0.804	0.863	1.237
11	MT	0.166	0.293	0.253	0.224	0.264	0.178	0.237	0.902	0.704	1.057
12	BE	0.163	0.346	0.279	0.243	0.281	0.189	0.245	0.814	0.677	1.009
13	LU	0.139	0.363	0.210	0.322	0.308	0.148	0.362	0.849	0.703	1.127
14	HU	0.131	0.308	0.184	0.282	0.267	0.161	0.313	0.866	0.875	1.108
15	CY	0.129	0.299	0.230	0.159	0.230	0.129	0.230	0.771	0.559	1.440
16	AT	0.116	0.434	0.281	0.287	0.354	0.271	0.254	0.815	0.963	0.884
17	FR	0.116	0.385	0.302	0.296	0.311	0.214	0.327	0.806	0.709	1.105
18	FI	0.111	0.299	0.254	0.194	0.232	0.180	0.275	0.778	0.708	1.420
19	NL	0.108	0.299	0.308	0.133	0.297	0.248	0.149	0.993	0.806	1.123
20	DK	0.104	0.376	0.139	0.263	0.285	0.161	0.236	0.758	1.159	0.900
21	SI	0.084	0.235	0.166	0.326	0.171	0.129	0.318	0.730	0.779	0.974
22	CZ	0.078	0.336	0.267	0.166	0.301	0.175	0.208	0.896	0.655	1.258
23	NO	0.077	0.308	0.192	0.245	0.265	0.183	0.278	0.861	0.954	1.135
24	IS	0.067	0.569	0.357	0.091	0.461	0.361	0.186	0.810	1.010	2.036
(7)	average EU	0.146	0.347	0.245	0.259	0.287	0.190	0.276	0.825	0.778	1.064
	Maximum	0.225	0.569	0.387	0.377	0.461	0.361	0.380	0.993	1.159	2.036
	Minimum	0.067	0.235	0.139	0.091	0.171	0.129	0.149	0.730	0.559	0.693
	Simple average	0.146	0.347	0.245	0.259	0.287	0.190	0.276	0.827	0.788	1.124

8 SAE of Poverty Indicators Using Amelia Data

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8.1 Introduction

The aim of the present work is to test the Amelia data-set using well-known and established methodologies on small area analysis. A brief summary on the AMELIA data-set is given as well as on the used population. The chosen measures and the SAE methodologies are described. Finally the results on the simulations performed are reported.

8.2 Definition of the Measures

In the present work the reference poverty measures are the average equivalized income, the Head Count Ratio (HCR) and the Poverty Gap (PG) as defined by FOSTER et al. (1984).

Denoting by p the poverty line and j a given small area, different poverty indicators are defined by the mean of the variable

$$F_{\alpha ij} = \left(\frac{p - y_{ij}}{p} \right)^{\alpha} I(y_{ij} \leq p), \quad i = 1, \dots, n_j$$

Setting $\alpha = 0$ defines the HCR.

Similarly, setting $\alpha = 1$ defines the PG.

8.3 SAE

In this section the main SAE methodologies used in the simulations are presented, namely the EBLUP estimator, the M-quantile methodology and the Empirical Best Predictor.

When the interest of the analysis is in poverty measures for small area that are not fully represented in the sample, there is need to use small area estimation methodologies.

The idea can be summarized as follows. We are interested in obtaining an estimate of a domain specific parameter m_j , ($j = 1, 2, \dots, D$). Let \mathbf{x}_{ij} be a known vector of p auxiliary variables for each population unit i in small area j and assume that information for the

variable of interest y is available only for the sampled units.

Area-specific random effect terms are considered in order to take into account the between area variation through the correlation among units within a small area. The basic unit level linear mixed model is the nested error regression model formulated by BATTESE et al. (1988). It can be expressed as follows:

$$y_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + u_j + e_{ij}.$$

Given the previous model, the Empirical Best Linear Unbiased Predictor (EBLUP) of the mean of y in small area j is:

$$\hat{m}_j^{EBLUP} = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} y_{ij} + \sum_{i \in r_j} \hat{y}_{ij} \right]$$

where $\hat{y}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \hat{u}_j$ are the values predicted under the assumed model; where s_j denotes the n_j sampled units in area j , r_j denotes the remaining $N_j - n_j$ units in the area (out of the sample), $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ and \hat{u}_j are obtained by substituting an optimal estimate of the covariance matrix of the random effects into respectively the best linear unbiased estimator of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and the best linear unbiased predictor of u_j .

The MSE formula derivation of the EBLUP estimator can be found in RAO (2003).

$$MSE \left[\hat{m}_j^{EBLUP} \right] = MSE \left[\hat{m}_j^{BLUP} \right] + E \left[\hat{m}_j^{EBLUP} - \hat{m}_j^{BLUP} \right]^2$$

The second order approximation of the MSE of the EBLUP estimator is equal to:

$$MSE \left[\hat{m}_j^{EBLUP} \right] = g_{1j}(\delta) + g_{2j}(\delta) + g_{3j}(\delta),$$

where $g_{1j}(\delta)$ identify the MSE of the BLUP estimator when $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is known, $g_{2j}(\delta)$ accounts for the variability in the estimator $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ and $g_{3j}(\delta)$ incorporates the variability of the estimate of the variance components δ .

CHAMBERS and TZAVIDIS (2006) have developed an approach to small area estimation based on the quantiles of the conditional distribution of the variable of study (y) given

the covariates (BRECKLING and CHAMBERS, 1988).

The bias adjusted M-quantile predictor of m_j , the mean of the variable of interest in area j , is (CHAMBERS et al., 2014):

$$\hat{m}_j^{MQ} = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} y_{ij} + \sum_{i \in r_j} \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T \hat{\beta}_{\bar{q}_j} + \frac{N_j - n_j}{n_j} \sum_{i \in s_j} \omega_{ij}^{MQ} \phi \left\{ (y_{ij} - \hat{y}_{ij}) / \omega_{ij}^{MQ} \right\} \right], \quad (8.1)$$

where s_j denotes the n_j sampled units in area j , r_j denotes the remaining $N_j - n_j$ units in the area (out of the sample), $\hat{y}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T \hat{\beta}_{\bar{q}_j}$, ω_{ij}^{MQ} is a robust estimator of the scale of the residuals in area j .

The analytic MSE estimator for \hat{m}_j^{MQ} is equal to:

$$MSE \left(\hat{m}_j^{MQ} \right) = \hat{V} \left(\hat{m}_j^{MQ} \right) + \hat{B} \left(\hat{m}_j^{MQ} \right)^2$$

and its first order approximation is:

$$MSE(\hat{m}_j^{MQ}) = (1 - n_j N_j^{-1})^2 \left[(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{r_j} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{s_j})^T \hat{V} \left(\hat{\beta}_{\bar{q}_j} \right) (\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{r_j} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{s_j}) + \hat{V}(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_{r_j}) + \frac{1}{n_j^2} \sum_{i \in s_j} \left[\omega_{ij}^{MQ} \phi \left\{ (y_{ij} - \hat{y}_{ij}) / \omega_{ij}^{MQ} \right\} \right]^2 \right].$$

The majority of the small area literature focuses on the estimation of domain averages, but recent methodology has also focused on the estimation of non-linear statistics (incidence of income poverty, the poverty gap and percentiles of the income distribution function). More specifically, until very recently the estimation of poverty indicators was based on the so called World Bank (WB) method, proposed firstly by ELBERS and LANJOUW (2003). From a small area perspective MOLINA and RAO (2010a) proposed the Empirical Best Predictors (EBP) that is the best estimation method for in-sample domains when the normality assumptions of the nested error regression model hold.

The poverty measures defined in Section 2 can be decomposed as follows. For a small area j

$$F_{\alpha ij} = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} F_{\alpha ij} + \sum_{k \in r_j} F_{\alpha kj} \right]$$

The unknown part $F_{\alpha kj}$, $k \in r_j$ can be estimated as follows,

$$\hat{F}_{\alpha kj} = n_j^{-1} \sum_{i \in s_j} \left(\frac{p - \hat{y}_{ik}}{p} \right)^\alpha I(\hat{y}_{ik} \leq p)$$

where $\hat{y}_{ik} = x_k' \hat{\beta}(\hat{\theta}_j) + e_i$, $\hat{\theta}_j$ is an estimate of the average value of the M-quantile coefficients of the units in area j and e_i here is the sample residual defined by the M-quantile fit to y_i .

The previous quantity can be computed by Monte Carlo simulation as follows:

- (I) Fit the M-quantile small area model using the sample values y_s and obtain estimates $\hat{\theta}_j, \hat{\beta}(\hat{\theta}_j)$.
- (II) Generate an out of sample vector of size $N_j - n_j$ using

$$\hat{y}_k^* = x_k' \hat{\beta}(\hat{\theta}_j) + e_k^*, k \in r_j$$

where e_k^* , $k \in r_j$ is drawn from the empirical distribution function of the M-quantile model residuals. Residuals can be drawn either from the domain (area) j residuals or from all the residuals.

- (III) Repeat the process H times. Each time combine the sample data y_i , $i \in s_j$ and out of sample data \hat{y}_k^* , $k \in r_j$ for computing $F_{\alpha ij}$
- (IV) Average the results over H simulations to obtain an estimate of $F_{\alpha j}$.

The MSE of the estimator of the defined poverty measures can be estimated analytically using the bootstrap methodology, as suggested in MARCHETTI et al. (2012). Briefly, the procedure can be summarised as follows.

Starting from sample s , selected from a finite population Ω without replacement, fit the M-quantile small area model and obtain estimates of the parameters which are used to compute the model residuals. Then generate B bootstrap populations, Ω^{*b} . From each bootstrap population, select L bootstrap samples using simple random sampling within the small areas and without replacement in a way such that $n_j^* = n_j$. Using the bootstrap samples, obtain estimates of the small area parameters, τ_j . Bootstrap estimators of the bias and variance of the estimated target small area parameter, $\hat{\tau}_j$, are defined respectively

by

$$\widehat{Bias}(\widehat{\tau}_j) = B^{-1}L^{-1} \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{l=1}^L (\widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl} - \tau_j^{*bl})$$

$$\widehat{Var}(\widehat{\tau}_j) = B^{-1}L^{-1} \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{l=1}^L (\widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl} - \widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl})$$

Where τ_j^{*bl} is the small area parameter of the b th bootstrap population, $\widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl}$ is the small area parameter estimated with the l th sample of the b th bootstrap population and $\widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl}$ and $\widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl} = L^{-1} \sum_{l=1}^L \widehat{\tau}_j^{*bl}$. The bootstrap MSE estimator of the estimated small area target parameter is then defined as

$$\widehat{MSE}(\widehat{\tau}_j) = \widehat{Var}(\widehat{\tau}_j) + \widehat{Bias}(\widehat{\tau}_j)$$

Molina and Rao (2010) proposed an Empirical Best Prediction (EBP) approach to poverty estimation, which attempts to minimize the effect of potential outliers in the data by modelling a logarithmic transformation of the outcome variable and relies on the use of a nested error regression model. This method can be applied to estimate practically any (linear or nonlinear) function of the values of a target associated with the units of a finite population, when this variable or some transformation of it follows a linear model, so also to the HCR and PG.

Suppose that there exists a one-to-one transformation $g_{ij} = T(y_{ij})$ of the reference variable such that the vector \mathbf{g} containing the values of the transformed variables g_{ij} for all the population units satisfies $\mathbf{g} \sim N(\mu, V)$. Thus, the FGT poverty measures presented in Section 2 is a nonlinear function of the vector \mathbf{g} . The Best Predictor (BP) of $F_{\alpha j}$ is

$$\widehat{F}_{\alpha j}^B = E_{\mathbf{r}}(F_{\alpha j} | \mathbf{g}_s)$$

If we use the decomposition of the FGT indicator as proposed above in sample and out-of-sample elements and introducing the conditional expectation inside the sum, the BP becomes

$$\widehat{F}_{\alpha j}^B = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} F_{\alpha ij} + \sum_{i \in r_j} \widehat{F}_{\alpha ij}^B \right]$$

Molina and Rao propose to use an empirical approximation to BP by Monte Carlo simulation of a large number L of vectors \mathbf{g}_r generated from the conditional distribution of

\mathbf{g}_r given \mathbf{g}_s . Let $G_{ij}^{(l)}$ be the value of the out-of-sample observation G_{ij} , $i \in r_j$, obtained in the l th simulation, $l = 1, \dots, L$. A Monte Carlo approximation to the best predictor of Y_{ij} for $i \in r_j$ is given by

$$\hat{F}_{\alpha j}^B \approx \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L F_{\alpha ij}^{(l)}, i \in r_j$$

In practice, the mean vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and the covariance matrix \mathbf{V} usually depend on an unknown vector of parameters θ . Molina and Rao propose to take an estimator $\hat{\theta}$ of θ such as the maximum likelihood (ML) estimator or the residual ML (REML) estimator.

Then the expectation can be approximated by generating values $G_{ij}^{(l)}$ from the estimated density function of the variable. The resulting predictor, denoted $\hat{F}_{\alpha ij}^{EB}$ is called empirical best predictor (EBP) of $F_{\alpha ij}$. Finally, the EBP of the poverty measure $F_{\alpha j}$ is given by

$$\hat{F}_{\alpha j}^{EB} = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} F_{\alpha ij} + \sum_{i \in r_j} \hat{F}_{\alpha ij}^{EB} \right]$$

MOLINA and RAO (2010a) obtain a parametric bootstrap MSE estimator by following the bootstrap method for finite populations of GONZÁLEZ-MANTEIGA et al. (2008). This bootstrap method can be readily applied to other complex parameters not necessarily of the separable form as the FGT measures. The procedure is very similar to the previous described for the M-quantile estimator.

Starting from sample \mathbf{s} , selected from a finite population Ω without replacement, fit model and obtain estimates of the parameter, using for example the REML method. Then generate independently the area and unit specific errors. Then construct B bootstrap populations, Ω^{*b} . From each bootstrap population, select L bootstrap samples using simple random sampling within the small areas and without replacement. Using the bootstrap samples, obtain estimates of the small area parameters. A Monte Carlo approximation to the theoretical bootstrap estimator of MSE is then calculated.

8.4 Empirical Results

The AMELIA data-set has been created under the project Advanced Methodology for European Laeken Indicators (AMELI). The aim of AMELIA is to provide a realistic synthetic universe that is based on the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) data and its structures. The dataset contains variables at both personal and

household level and include variables regarding social, economic, and regional attributes. All these variables are compared with the EU-SILC ones.

The AMELIA data-set has a hierarchical structure, shown below:

- The AMELIA country itself
- 4 regions
- 11 provinces
- 40 districts
- 1,592 cities/communities
- 3,781,289 households
- 10,012,600 persons

A deeper description of the data-set can be found in BERGER et al. (2016)

Given the large dimension of the AMELIA's population, in order to test this data-set a sub-sample has been selected from it by means of stratified random sampling where the starters are represented by the districts. This sub-sample is regarded as our population. It comprises of 38,160 households and it is representative of the entire population. The population size over the districts ranges from 250 to 3400 households. The sub-sample contains variables at both households and individual level. The individual level ones are referred to the main breadwinner of the household.

Household variables:

CIT: city identification code

DIS: district identification code

PROV: province identification code, NUTS2 level

REG: region identification code

DOU: degree of urbanisation

UEP: Unemployment profile

HHS: household size

EHHS: equivalised household size

EDI: equivalised disposable household income

HY010: total household gross income

HY020: total disposable household income

Individual variables:

PID: personal identifier for the main breadwinner

AGE: age

INC: personal income

SEX: gender

ISCED: highest ISCED level attained

BAS: basic activity status

MST: marital status

COB: country of birth

EDU: current education activity

SEM: self-employment dummy

SUP: managerial position

From this population 1,000 samples have been selected by stratified random sampling, so that all districts are represented with sample sizes ranging from 5 to 34 observations (mean equal 10.21 and median equal 10). Districts are the target areas for SAE methodologies. All the simulations have been performed with R software.

We chose a common set of auxiliary variables for all the small area models: the degree of urbanisation, the household size, the equivalised household size, and for the main breadwinner the age, the gender, the education level, the basic activity status, the marital status, the country of birth, the current education activity, a self-employment dummy, the managerial position.

In Table 8.1 the results of the simulation study are presented. The area mean incomes

are estimated with M-Quantile and EBLUP estimators, the HCR and PG are estimated estimated with M-Quantile and EBP. We estimated the MSE of the mean estimator s using the above defined analytic MSE estimators, while the HCR and PG MSEs have been estimated through the use of the bootstrap methodologies described above. In table 8.1 the percentage relative bias, the percentage relative root mean square error and the percentage relative bias of the root mean squared error estimators are reported. The table shows the mean values computed over areas and simulations.

As concern the point estimation of the means the estimator that performs the best seems to be the EBLUP. It has got the minimum RB and RRMSE (0.7% and 17.1% respectively) with respect to the mean M-Quantile estimator. However, looking at the MSE estimates the EBLUP shows a very high relative bias (110.8%), while the M-Quantile shows a lower bias (-37.7%).

Analyzing all the M-quantile based estimates we can see that they have in mean a negative RB, so they slightly underestimate the measures (-10.8% for the mean, -11.9% for HCR and -8.5% for PG). These three values are quite close so it also seems that the M-Quantile performs similarly for all the measures used in the simulations.

On the other hand, the EBPs results show an high positive relative bias (23.9% for the HCR and 79.4% for the PG). This can be probably due to the use of the logarithm transformation that in this case may not be appropriate. So, from the simulations, it seems that the EB overestimates the measures and it works differently for HCR and PG.

The RRMSE is a bit more stable for EBLUP (17.1%), HCR and PG using the M-Quantile and HCR using the EB; there are all quit close (17.1%-25.6%). On the contrary, the relative root MSE of the EBP estimator of the PG is large (114.2%).

Looking at the relative bias of the root MSE estimates of the HCR and the PG, we can observe that it is negative for the EBPs estimators (-38.0% HCR and -67.5% PG), while it is positive for the M-quantile estimators (44.6% HCR and 103.4% PG).

Starting from this simulation results, deeper investigations are needed to understand the unexpected behavior of the proposed estimators.

Table 8.1: Simulation results (means over areas): percentage relative bias (RB) of point estimates and root mean squared error estimates and relative root mean squared error of point estimates.

Estimates	Point Estimation		Root MSE estimation
	RB	RRMSE	RB
<i>MEAN MQ</i>	-10.2	36.3	-37.7
<i>MEAN EBLUP</i>	0.7	17.1	110.8
<i>HCR MQ</i>	-11.9	21.1	44.6
<i>HCR EB</i>	23.9	25.6	-38.0
<i>PG MQ</i>	-8.5	21.6	103.4
<i>PG EB</i>	79.4	114.2	-67.5

9 Cross–Border Statistics

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9.1 Introduction

Reliable, timely and regionally disaggregated information on central social indicators are a prerequisite of target-oriented European and national policies. To meet these demands, national statistical institutes increasingly do not only rely on classical design-based methods but also employ model-based estimation methods. An important example for the use of statistical models to efficiently exploit the data available are small area estimation techniques i.e. model-based techniques specifically designed to provide reliable estimates for small subsamples.

Model based estimates are usually generated by national statistics. This firstly causes that estimates are produced for regional sub-entities within national borders only. The results are generally not comparable across borders due to national peculiarities in the data and differences in the underlying methods and models. European policies however do not only focus on countries but prominently target European regions: More than one third of the European Union’s budget is devoted to its Cohesion policy, which aims at improving the economic situation of European regions, diminishing disparities between regions and fostering cross-border cooperation (see EUROPEAN COMMISSION (2017a) and EUROPEAN COMMISSION (2017b)). Correspondingly, there is a demand for regional information that is comparable across national borders. This is specifically true for regions with an institutionalized cross-border cooperation such as the Greater Region, a closely integrated region consisting of Luxembourg, Saarland, Rhineland-Palladium, Lorraine, Wallonia, the Federation Wallonia-Brussels and the German-speaking Community of Belgium (see <http://www.granderegion.net/> and Figure 9.1).

Figure 9.1: The Greater Region

Secondly, the national approach to model-based data-production implies that models are based on national data only, therewith disregarding structures that are valid across borders. This constrained approach does not suit the reality of many indicators: Environmental indicators such as measures of air or water quality hardly consider borders. It also seems reasonable to assume that social indicators such as poverty, employment and commuter balances are highly dependent of what is located behind a national border. Again this is specifically true for closely-integrated cross-border regions as the Greater Region, which records the highest cross-border mobility of workers in the European Union (see GRANDE REGION (2017)). In this case model-based estimation techniques might benefit from also exploiting patterns valid across borders.

Consequently, there is a need for *border statistics*, which we understand as a cross-border approach to model-based data production. Consistent with the shortcomings identified above, we formulate two corresponding aims:

- Providing model-based estimation results that are comparable across borders

- Efficiently exploiting all the data available in cross-border studies by incorporating information on what is located behind borders and using structures that are valid across borders in model-based estimation methods.

In this report, we want to present a methodology for small area estimation (SAE) in a border region. The starting point is to estimate the variable of interest in an integrated approach, i.e. using one model for all areas under study based on a joint dataset of cross-nationally comparable covariates. While this approach exploits patterns valid across borders, it also implies the strong assumption that the relationship between the variable of interest and covariates is constant for all areas on both sides of the border. It seems, however, more plausible, that there is an (ex-ante unknown) group of areas that is best explained by national patterns while others indeed gain from an integrated model. Applying work done in the context of rental price estimation (ARTICUS and BURGARD, 2014), we, therefore, suggest a mixture-based approach that offers flexibility in this regard. In this framework several models are specified for different unknown groups of areas and the estimation of model parameters as well as the assignment of areas to groups is then performed simultaneously. The suggested approach will be applied in a pilot study for regional poverty measurement in the German and Luxembourgian parts of the Greater Region.

The report is structured as follows: We start by briefly introducing the standard area-level-approach to SAE. We then propose the innovative mixture-based extension of the standard approach, which is deemed more suitable for SAE in a border-region. We then describe the above-mentioned pilot study and close with a summary and an outlook.

9.2 Small Area Estimation

When a survey is conducted, there often is not only an interest in making statistical inferences about the entire population being studied, but also in obtaining reliable information for specified subentities, called *areas* or *domains* depending on whether the disaggregation of the population is by region or by content. To specify the problem we consider the following setting (MÜNNICH et al., 2013): A population \mathcal{U} of size N is divided into m pairwise disjoint subpopulations $\mathcal{U}_i, i = 1, \dots, m$. A sample \mathcal{S} of size n is drawn, with $\mathcal{S}_i = \mathcal{S} \cap \mathcal{U}_i$ designating the sample realized in \mathcal{U}_i . Now the aim is to simultaneously estimate a vector of m area-specific parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m)$, e.g. means $\boldsymbol{\mu}$.

The disaggregation of the available sample often results in small sample sizes for the subentities. Under these circumstances, conventional direct estimators (which by definition only use the information from the area under consideration) lead to an unacceptably large standard error. Note, however, that such direct estimators are generally design-unbiased. Methods of SAE are designed to produce reliable estimates even for very small subsamples (see RAO and MOLINA (2015) or JIANG and LAHIRI (2006) for an overview). The strategy is to apply indirect techniques that make use of additional information as, for example, sampled information from other areas. This additional information is often included through a model, assuming a (fixed) relationship between auxiliary information and target variable, that is constant over all areas. This relationship is then used to stabilize the estimation. In the literature this strategy is often referred to as "borrowing strength" (GOSH and RAO, 1994).

A basic approach in SAE is to estimate a linear mixed model, either on level of the observation units or on aggregated level of the areas (JIANG and LAHIRI, 2006). As we only got aggregated information on regional poverty levels, we use the standard area level model as defined by FAY and HERRIOT (1979). It is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir} &= \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i + e_i \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, m \\ v_i &\overset{i.i.d}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_v^2) \\ e_i &\overset{ind}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_{e,i}^2).\end{aligned}$$

$\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}$ is the direct estimate as obtained as a weighted mean from the sample realized in area i . e_i is the error term, which in this case is the sampling error of the direct estimate with known variance $\sigma_{e,i}^2$. \mathbf{x}_i^T denotes the vector of auxiliary information for area i with corresponding regression coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. The area-specific random effect is denoted by v_i . It is assumed that v_i and e_i are independently distributed.

When estimating this model, we are not as much interested in the model coefficients themselves as in the prediction of the target variable out of the model. The Empirical Best Linear Unbiased Predictor (EBLUP) of the parameter of interest μ under this model

is given by RAO and MOLINA (2015)

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mu}_i^{FH} &= \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \hat{v}_i \\
&= \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \hat{\gamma}_i (\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir} - \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \\
&= \gamma_i \hat{\mu}_i^{Dir} + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i) \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}
\end{aligned}$$

with

$$\hat{\gamma}_i = \frac{\sigma_v^2}{\sigma_{e,i}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_v^2}.$$

This estimator is called the Fay-Herriot-estimator $\hat{\mu}_i^{FH}$ for the parameter of interest. $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ and \hat{v}_i denote the BLUE for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and the BLUP for v_i , respectively (see HENDERSON et al. (1959) and SEARLE et al. (1992) for estimation and prediction of parameters for a mixed model). Note that $\hat{\mu}_i^{FH}$ can be expressed as a composite estimator of the synthetic estimator $\mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ obtained from the fixed part of the model and the direct estimator $\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}$. Weights are given by the area-specific shrinkage factor $\hat{\gamma}_i$, that is the model variance $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$ relative to the total variance $\sigma_{e,i}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_v^2$. If the model-variance is small compared to the design variance, $\hat{\gamma}$ is close to zero and the synthetic estimator dominates. Intuitively, $\hat{\gamma}$ can be understood as a relative measure of confidence in the model- and the design-based estimator.

9.3 Exploiting cross-border-patterns in Small Area Estimation

The national approach to SAE implies that models are based on national data only, thereby disregarding structures that are valid across borders. This does not suit the reality of many social indicators. It seems reasonable to assume that, for example, the regional level of poverty is highly dependent on factors that extend across the national border. If this is the case, model-based methods should exploit these patterns, too.

A first step towards this goal is to estimate poverty in an integrated approach, i.e. using a joint data-set for all countries containing comparable covariates. This allows to exploit patterns that are valid across borders. However, an integrated model implies the strong assumption that the relationship between poverty and covariates is constant for all areas under consideration, disregarding which country they belong to and their proximity to the border. This seems overly restrictive. There might be groups of areas where social indicators of interest are best explained by national patterns while others, e.g. those

located close to the border, indeed gain from an integrated model. We, therefore, suggest to apply an innovative finite mixture model-based approach for SAE (Articus and Burgard, 2014) which offers more flexibility in this regard (see MCLACHLAN and PEEL (2000) or FRÜHWIRTH-SCHNATTER (2006) for a comprehensive overview on mixture models). This framework provides an opportunity to specify several models for different groups of areas while group membership does not have to be predetermined. The assignment of areas to groups and the estimation of model parameters for different models is then performed simultaneously. Finally, small area estimates can be predicted from the mixture as a weighted average of component predictions, where weights are given by the probability of subgroup membership.

According to the scenario just introduced, we now assume that the m areas $i = 1, \dots, m$ considered above are divided into K classes $k = 1, \dots, K$ and that for each class there is a specific relationship between response variable and auxiliary information. The direct estimate for a given area i belonging to cluster k is appropriately modelled by a Fay-Herriot-type linear mixed model with class-specific model parameters β_k and model variance $\sigma_{v,k}^2$, i.e. $\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir} | (z_i = k) = \mathbf{x}_i^T \beta_k + v_{i,k} + e_i$, with $v_{i,k} \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{v,k}^2)$ and e_i as in the standard FH model defined in the previous section. $z_i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ is a latent variable identifying class membership,

As z_i is unknown we do not only need to estimate class-specific models but also have to infer class membership from the data. A natural approach to solve this problem in an integrated way are finite mixture models. In this framework, the allocation to subgroups and the estimation of model parameters are performed simultaneously.

The marginal density of $\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}$ under a mixture of K mixed models is given by

$$f(\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}; \mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \phi(\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}; \mathbf{x}_i^T \beta_k, \sigma_{v,k}^2 + \sigma_{e,i}^2), \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (9.1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_K)$ with $\pi_k > 0$ for all k , and $\sum_k^K \pi_k = 1$ denotes the vector of K unconditional probabilities $Pr(z_i = k)$.

We propose the following Finite Mixture Fay-Herriot-type estimator (FMFH) for μ_i that accounts for the existence of unobserved subgroups of areas:

$$\hat{\mu}_i^{FMFH} = \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{\xi}_{i,k} \cdot \hat{\mu}_i^{FH,k}, \quad (9.2)$$

where $\xi_{i,k}$ is the conditional probability that area i belongs to class k ,

$$\xi_{i,k} = Pr(z_i = k | \hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}, \mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\pi}) = \frac{\pi_k \phi(\hat{\mu}_i^{Dir}; \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_k, \sigma_{v,k}^2 + \sigma_{e,i}^2)}{\sum_{j=1}^K \pi_j \phi(\hat{\mu}_j^{Dir}; \mathbf{x}_j^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_k, \sigma_{v,k}^2 + \sigma_{e,j}^2)}, \quad (9.3)$$

and $\hat{\xi}_{i,k}$ is derived using $\hat{\pi}_k$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k$ instead of π_k and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k$. $\xi_{i,k}$ can be understood as an area-specific measure of class membership.

We, thus, estimate the statistic of interest as a weighted mean of predicts from model 1 to K , where the area-specific weights are given by the conditional probabilities that area i belongs to model k . See COLE and BAUER (2016) for a discussion of conditional prediction from mixture models.

In order to gain insights into the subgroup assignment, and, at the same time, support the clustering performance of the model, mixture models can be extended to include additional covariates to model the mixture weights (DAYTON and MACREADY (1988), WEDEL and KAMAKURA (2000)). Usually a multinomial logit model is assumed, i.e.

$$\pi_{i,k} = \pi_k(\mathbf{w}_i, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_k) = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{w}_i^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_k)}{\sum_{j=1}^K \exp(\mathbf{w}_i^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_j)}, \quad (9.4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ denotes the parameters and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1 = \mathbf{0}$ for identifiability. We include this approach as a further extension into our pilot study.

9.4 Pilot Study: Poverty Measures in a Border Region

9.4.1 Data

For the pilot study, direct estimates for the at-risk-of-poverty rate (ARPR) on LAU1-level for both the border region of Germany, i.e. Rhineland-Palladium and Saarland, and Luxembourg were provided by official statistics. For Germany, the estimates are based on the German Mikrozensus of 2009. For Luxembourg the ARPR-estimates are provided for 2014 and are based on the HBS. According to common practice at STATEC, data over three consecutive years is cumulated to increase the sample size, i.e. the estimates are based on income data for 2013 to 2015 (prices are adjusted to the price level of 2014). The realized area specific sample sizes range from 87 to 2875 (with mean 804.4) for Luxembourg and from 16 to 1533 (with mean 145.7) for the German parts of the Greater Region. Square roots of estimated variances are illustrated in Figure 9.2. Note that the precision of direct

Figure 9.2: Square root of estimated variances of direct estimates

estimates is of course largely affected by the area-specific sample sizes. Both German and Luxembourgian estimates on this highly disaggregated regional level are usually not published by official statistics because they by far fail to meet precision requirements

As auxiliary information, for Germany a large number of social indicators on LAU1-level is available from the data collection INKAR (See BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR BAU-, STADT- UND RAUMFORSCHUNG (BBSR) (2016)). For Luxembourg information on canton-level is less readily available, but STATEC provided special evaluations for a selection of social indicators.

Regarding the preconditions of a successful implementation of a border study, two peculiarities of the data set have to be noted: First of all the size of Luxembourg and the German part of the Greater Region differ considerably. This is not only true in terms of area but also – and more importantly – with respect to the number of subentities on LAU 1-level: While there are only 12 cantons in Luxembourg, there are 263 (collective) municipalities in Rhineland-Palladium and Saarland. This implies an imbalance regarding the influence of data points from the two countries: The additional information contained in data from Luxembourg is not very likely to largely affect the estimation for the German part. For

a future study it would, therefore, be desirable to obtain data from the French and Belgian part of the Greater region, too, to achieve a more balanced border-study situation. Secondly, note that sample sizes for Luxembourgian cantons are generally larger than for German areas. This is partly due to the cumulation of information over consecutive years. Luxembourgian estimates will, therefore, likely be dominated by the direct estimate. Finally, note that the use of data for two different countries in an integrated approach poses specific difficulties. The information usually is not readily comparable because underlying definitions and categories as well as the survey process differ. An example from the study at hand is information on real estate and construction activity. While German official statistics in related statistics routinely define the first category of *detached houses* as one- or two-family-homes, in Luxembourg only single-family detached houses are counted in this category. The respective information for the two countries did thus show structural breaks and was not usable in this study. Standardized European evaluations as provided by EUROSTAT are usually not available on a highly disaggregated regional level such as NUTS3 or even LAU1. Therefore, data collection for a cross-border study requires special attention and close cooperation with data providers from the participating countries in order to build a harmonized data set.

9.4.2 Models and Estimation Results

We estimate the ARPR using for different approaches:

- FH.sep
Separate standard FH-models, i.e. one model for Luxembourg and one for the German parts of the Greater region
- FH.int
One joint standard FH-model for all areas in the study
- FMFH
A Finite Mixture of two FH-models
- FMFHconc
A Finite Mixture of two FH-models with concomitant variables.

Model selection was preceded by a careful check of cross-border comparability of available indicators. Then stepwise selection procedures and standard diagnostic tools (see BROWN

et al., 2001) were applied to select covariates from the remaining set of indicators. Based on the respective results we chose the net migration rate and the unemployment rate as covariates in all models. Scatter plots of the auxiliary information against the ARPR are depicted in Figure 9.3. Black dots mark German areas and red dots represent Luxembourgian cantons. Additionally the regression line from a linear regression are included in the plot. It can be seen that the relationship between ARPR and covariates differ between the two countries, especially for the net migration rate.

Figure 9.3: Scatter plots of covariates vs. ARPR

To model the mixture weights in FMFHconc, we propose using a measure of proximity to the border as illustrated in Figure 9.4 as a covariate in the submodel. This will yield valuable insights into the existence and nature of cross-border patterns and thereby will help to understand the specific requirements of border statistics.

Figure 9.4: Distance to nearest city in km

In Figure 9.5 scatterplots of predicts from the 4 different small area models are depicted. It shows that the estimation of a joint model for German and Luxembourg does not yield considerably different results than the estimation of one model for each country. This can be explained by the peculiarities of the data for this pilot study: Firstly, Luxembourg with only 12 data points is too "small" to influence the estimation for German regions. Secondly, relatively large subgroup-specific sample sizes for Luxembourg imply that the estimates are dominated by the direct estimates, disregarding of whether a joint or separate models are estimated: Shrinkage factors for Luxembourgian areas range 0.6 to 0.9801 (median = 0.885) and 0.5 to 0.9655 (median = 0.81) for FH.int and FH.sep, respectively. Thus, while estimated coefficients differ for Luxembourgian areas, model predictions for a large share of areas are almost equal. It obviously makes a difference whether standard or mixture-based methods are employed. This is not only due to differences in estimated model coefficients, but again can also be explained by different model variances: While we , for example, estimate $\sigma_u = 0.0017$ for FH.int, FMFH yields $\sigma_u = 0.0011$ for the first component and $\sigma_u = 0.0005$ for the second.

Figure 9.5: Scatterplots of small area estimates

Figure 9.6 shows boxplots of the square roots of MSE-estimates for the 275 areas in the study. It can clearly be seen that all SAE techniques applied outperform direct estimation in terms of MSE. The comparison between FH.sep and FH.int shows that the estimation of a joint model for all areas under study does not perform better than one model for each country. Regarding the rationale and motivation for border studies, this result seems discouraging. It can, however, be explained by the above-mentioned peculiarities of the data set: The large imbalance between the size of the two countries under study combined with the fact that design variances for Luxembourgian areas are generally lower than for German ones implies that the estimation of joint model is not likely to yield better – or other – results than two separate models. Finally, the figure reveals that results can be improved considerably if innovative mixture-based estimators are employed instead of standard approaches.

Figure 9.6: Square Root of MSE estimates

Figure 9.7: Mixture weights for component 1 in FMFHconc

The map in Figure 9.7 shows the conditional probabilities $\xi_{i,k}$ that an area belongs to component 1 in FMFHconc. Indeed, a slight cross-border pattern can be detected, i.e.

areas located relatively close to a city behind the border tend not to be assigned to component 1. On the other hand, areas with a large distance to cities behind borders seem to be better explained by this component.

9.5 Summary and Outlook

We proposed and applied a mixture-based approach to SAE in border statistics. It allows to efficiently exploit patterns valid across national borders without drawing the strong assumption that the relationship between the variable of interest and covariates is constant for all areas under study. Border-related variables might be included to model the mixture weights in order to support the mixture-based clustering and at the same time gain further insights into present border effects. The suggested method was applied in a pilot study for poverty measurement on a highly disaggregated regional level in parts of the Greater Region.

This study comes with several limitations regarding the current status of data availability. First of all and most importantly, so far only data for the German and Luxembourgian part of the Greater region could be obtained. This is problematic because of the large imbalance regarding the number of areas and thus data points in the model: While the German part of the Greater Region consist of 263 LAU 1-level units, Luxembourg is only separated into 12 cantons. Including the Luxembourgian data in the study is thus not very likely to decisively influence the estimation for Germany. For the future a collaboration with Belgian and French data providers is envisioned to cover the whole Greater Region. We expect to obtain more balanced results in terms of reciprocal influence of cross-border patterns on the estimation. A second issue is the availability of comparable covariates: Despite close cooperation and valuable support from STATEC, so far only a limited number of comparable social indicators is available. Here, too, further work is envisioned.

Note that this last point, i.e. the availability of suitable data sources, is a fundamental issue for any successful implementation of model-based SAE techniques in a border context. The provision of data for small area studies is already an issue in a national study because suitable statistics are usually not readily available due to disclosure and quality concerns. Naturally, it becomes even more problematic when data providers from different countries are involved and comparability of indicators becomes an additional criterion. Laying the foundation for a successful implementation of border statistics thus requires close cooperation of data providers from all countries involved to build a harmonized set of

covariates on a disaggregated regional level. We do, however, strongly believe that it is worth the effort!

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10 Future Challenges in Small Area Estimation

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10.1 Introduction

The European Union urges the need for adequate regional policies in order to support economic growth, sustainable development and quality of life (http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/what/investment-sbpolicy/). This is in line with Europe's 2020 Strategy for a smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth in the European Union. In order to provide a sound statistical basis for measuring these challenging goals at regional levels, advanced statistical methodologies must be developed. Small area estimation forms an important basis for these developments and has become an important methodology in official statistics production. Small area estimation has been one of the few areas in the production of official statistics where the need for using models has been accepted. This has created many opportunities for exciting research and has facilitated the collaboration between NSIs and universities. At the same time the use of models has also created many challenges. It is the responsibility of researchers to recognize these challenges and work on possible solutions.

The aim of this chapter is to summarise some of the challenges we currently face or we will face in the future in the production of small area statistics. The chapter is structured as follows. Before identifying future challenges, the next section reviews some commonly used model-based methods for small area estimation. Section 3 proceeds by describing some key challenges with using unit-level small area estimation methods. We first describe the challenges a data analyst faces when the assumptions of the model are not satisfied and describe possible solutions to this problem. The second part of this section focuses on challenges due to data access requirements. This is a commonly faced problem in real data applications. The requirement for access to Census micro-data -assumed by many methodologies- increases disclosure risk. In addition, updating the small area estimates in the intracensal period is a further practical problem. We describe a potential solution to these problems that can be offered via the use of area-level models, which however creates other methodological problems. In Section 3.3 we describe the challenges posed due attempts to achieve better data harmonization and outline open research problems. It is

well known that small area point estimates must be accompanied by precision estimates. Furthermore, the use of models in an official statistics context makes the need for developing an evaluation framework of paramount importance. Section 4 attempts to summarise these discussions by presenting alternative approaches to Mean Squared Error estimation and evaluation frameworks. Section 5 then summarises the challenges posed by the use of new forms of data for example, mobile and remote sensing data in the production of official statistics. We conclude this chapter by a summary of the main points.

10.2 Use of models for small area estimation

In order to identify future challenges in small area estimation methodologies, we think it is important to provide a brief review of methodologies in common use. Small area estimation is one of the few areas in survey sampling where the use of models is widely accepted as necessary. Model-based methods assume a model for the population and sample data and construct optimal predictors of the target parameters under the model. The term predictor instead of estimator is conventionally used as, under the model, the target parameters are assumed to be random. Here we describe how to use a model to produce small area estimates of linear and nonlinear indicators of interest. For example, users of small area statistics are interested in the estimation of indicators for example Laeken indicators such as the At Risk of Poverty and the Gini coefficient. To this set we add average and median income, which are also of interest for National Statistical Institutes (NSIs) (FABRIZI et al., 2014).

The most widely used approaches for estimating non-linear indicators require the use of unit-level survey data for the outcome variable and the covariates, and unit-level Census micro-data for the covariates. Area-level models for non-linear indicators (Gini coefficient) have been proposed in the literature (FABRIZI and TRIVISANO, 2016). We will return to the use of area-level models later in this report. The starting point for model-based small area estimation in the case of unit-level data is the unit-level nested error (random effects) regression model (BATTESE et al., 1988) and in particular methodologies that allow for estimates of both linear and non-linear indicators. Two popular methodologies for estimating linear and non-linear indicators are the World Bank method (ELBERS et al., 2003) and the Empirical Best Predictor (EBP) method (MOLINA and RAO, 2010b). We now provide a brief discussion about the similarities and differences between these two approaches. To start with both models make use of a nested error regression model that

is estimated by using survey data. The response variable, which is not available in the Census, is a welfare variable, e.g. income or consumption. The explanatory variables, used for modelling the welfare variable, are available both in the survey and in the Census datasets. After the model is fitted using the survey data, the estimated model parameters are combined with Census micro-data to form unit-level synthetic Census predictions of the welfare variable. The synthetic values of the welfare variable alongside a defined poverty line are then used for estimating non-linear indicators for example, the HCR and the Gini coefficient. Linear statistics can also be estimated by using the synthetically-generated welfare predicted values.

Let us now describe in more detail the EBP approach. Under the EBP approach Census predictions of the welfare outcome are generated by using the conditional predictive distribution of the out-of-sample data given the sample data. The point of departure of the EBP method is the following unit-level nested error regression model,

$$y_{ik} = \mathbf{x}_{ik}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + u_k + \epsilon_{ik}, u_k \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2); \epsilon_{ik} \sim N(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2), \quad (10.1)$$

where u_k denotes the domain random effect. A random effect is necessary when the covariates we include in the model do not explain the between domain variability. Assuming normality for the unit-level error and the domain random effects, the conditional distribution of the out-of-sample data given the sample data is also normal. The synthetic values of the welfare variable for the entire area population (of size N_k) are then generated from the following model,

$$y_{ik}^* = \mathbf{x}_{ik}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + \tilde{u}_k + u_k^* + \epsilon_{ik}^*, u_k^* \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2 \times (1 - \gamma_k)); \epsilon_{ik}^* \sim N(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2); \gamma_k = \frac{\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_u^2 + \frac{\sigma_\epsilon^2}{n_k}}, \quad (10.2)$$

where $\tilde{u}_k = E(u_k | y_k)$ is the conditional expectation of u_k given the within-area sample data y_k . In (10.2), $\mathbf{x}_{ik}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + \tilde{u}_k$ is the conditional mean of y_{ik} in the population given the sample data, whereas $u_k^* + \epsilon_{ik}^*$ that are generated from the above normal distributions create the conditional covariance structure of the y_{ik} 's in the population. Implementation of (10.2) requires replacing the unknown quantities $\boldsymbol{\beta}, \sigma_u, \sigma_\epsilon$, with estimates and simulating L synthetic populations of the welfare outcome, \mathbf{y}^* . With each vector of \mathbf{y}^* linear and non-linear indicators are computed in each domain k and the estimates are averaged over L . A moderate number of Monte-Carlo simulations $L = 50$ or $L = 100$ is used in practice. Note also that the EBP approach includes small area estimation of domain averages using the

unit-level model (BATTESE et al., 1988) as a special case. MSE estimation for model-based small area estimation both for in-sample and out-of-sample domains is performed using bootstrap methods under the unit-level nested error regression model.

Let us now compare the World Bank and EBP methods. Although both methods use a nested error regression model, one key difference is the level at which we specify the random effect. In the World Bank method it is common to specify the random effect at the cluster level whereas in the EBP method the random effect is specified at the domain level. The second important difference between the two methods is that the World Bank method simulates population realizations of the outcome from the estimated marginal distribution, while the EBP method simulates population realizations of outcome from the estimated conditional distribution. We now distinguish two cases. When clusters coincide with the target domains, MOLINA and RAO (2010b) demonstrate the superior performance of the EBP method -when compared to the World Bank method- for in-sample domains. For out-of-sample domains the predicted random effect is 0 and hence (10.2) becomes,

$$y_{ik}^* = \mathbf{x}_{ik}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + u_k^* + \epsilon_{ik}^*, u_k^* \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2); \epsilon_{ik}^* \sim N(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2). \quad (10.3)$$

Therefore, when domains and clusters coincide, EBP point estimates for out-of-sample domains coincide with the point estimates obtained by applying the World Bank method. It is straightforward to see that these are regression synthetic estimates. For example, for domain averages, $E(y_{ik}^*) = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ since $E(\epsilon_{ik}^*) = 0$ and $E(u_k^*) = 0$, which is the regression synthetic estimator with regression coefficients estimated under the linear mixed model.

Let us now focus on the more common case where target domains and clusters do not coincide. Also in this case the World Bank method simulates population realizations from the estimated marginal distribution while the EBP approach simulates population realizations from the estimated conditional distribution. However, as it is the case in most realistic situations, between domain variation is very small compared to between unit variation and the difference between the two distributions is small. The real difference between the two approaches is that the World Bank method is usually applied at a much finer geography (clusters) than the EBP method. In applications of poverty estimation most of the variability not associated with between household variability is associated with between cluster variability. In this context the World Bank method is well suited to SAE of poverty measures. Having said this, MOLINA et al. (2016) recently proposed EBP methodology

that allows for a two-fold nested error regression model that can accommodate both cluster and domain random effects.

10.3 Challenges with using unit-level model-based methodologies

Let us now focus on the challenges posed by the use of model-based methodologies we described in the previous section. We distinguish between challenges that relate to the model assumptions and challenges that relate to the use of data. In each case we discuss alternative methodologies.

10.3.1 Challenges due to the model assumptions

The methodologies we described in the previous Section rely on parametric assumptions. For example, developing an Empirical Best predictor is only possible under specific distributions one of which is the Normal distribution. It is of course reasonable to ask what are the options available to the data analyst when the assumptions of the model are not satisfied? We identify the following three options:

Use of optimal transformations: One approach to rectify the possible misspecification of the model assumptions is to attempt to find an appropriate transformation. Doing so means that the analyst can keep using standard estimation tools and software for small area estimation. The challenge in this case is in finding the most appropriate transformation. The papers by ELBERS et al. (2003) and MOLINA and RAO (2010b) considered the use of a logarithmic transformation. However, is a logarithmic transformation the most appropriate one? Can alternative transformations offer better predictive power? ROJAS-PERILLA et al. (2015) currently investigates the use of a wide range of transformations including the log-shift and power transformations (BOX and COX, 1964, GURKA et al., 2006). One key difference between the logarithmic transformation and these additional transformations is the adaptive feature offered by the so-called transformation parameter λ . This transformation parameter needs to be estimated using the data and different approaches including maximum likelihood estimation have been proposed under a linear model. However, little attention has been paid to studying the use of data driven transformations under the nested error regression model. GURKA et al. (2006) used Box-Cox transformations where the transformation parameter is estimated using restricted maximum likelihood theory. ROJAS-PERILLA et al. (2015) explore the use of different adaptive

transformations and estimation methods. Let us focus in more detail on on two types of transformations, namely log-shift and power transformations. Denote by $T_\lambda(y_{ik})$ the transformed outcome, the log-shift transformation is defined by

$$T_\lambda(y_{ik}) = \log(y_{ik} + \lambda). \quad (10.4)$$

An empirical approach to choosing λ in (10.4) is to define a grid of values for λ , fit the nested error regression model by using each of the transformed outcomes $T_\lambda(y_{ik})$ and select the transformation that makes the distribution of the residuals as close as possible to normal. This means select a transformation that makes the skewness of the distribution of the residuals close to 0 and the kurtosis close to 3. Note, however, that here we deal with two sets of residuals and to the best of our knowledge there is no formal approach to defining the distance from normality. An alternative approach and one that is currently researched is to use a scaled version of the log-shift transformation and select the value of λ that maximizes the residual log-likelihood or the log-likelihood under the model. To illustrate how the scale is selected let us focus on the second family of transformations, namely scaled power transformations. Here the Box-Cox transformation is defined by

$$T_\lambda(y_{ik}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(y_{ik}+c)^\lambda - 1}{\alpha^{\lambda-1}\lambda}, & \lambda \neq 0 \\ \alpha \log(y_{ik} + c), & \lambda = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (10.5)$$

for $y_{ik} > -c$, that means, c is a fixed parameter, which makes the data positive for making possible the use of the Box-Cox transformation and α is the geometric mean of y_{ik} (BOX and COX, 1964, GURKA et al., 2006). Conditional on α , the Jacobian of the transformation is equal to 1. Using the scaling by the geometric mean leaves the likelihood function under the nested error regression model unaffected and as a result standard software for fitting this model with the transformed data can be used. This is of practical importance as it allows the estimation of the small area model with the transformed outcome using standard software.

Current research shows that the use of transformations can help in improving small area estimation. However, even if the best possible transformation of the data has been found, there is still the real possibility of departures from the model assumptions. Such departures can affect the quality of small area estimates and the extend of the impact depends on what is being estimated. Furthermore, departures from the assumptions of the model are likely to impact on the quality of precision estimates. Recall that the estimation of uncer-

tainty is based on the use of parametric bootstrap and misspecification of the assumptions used to generate the bootstrap world will lead to incorrect estimates of precision. It is apparent that evaluation of the small area point and uncertainty estimates must be at the center of small area estimation. We return to this point later.

Empirical Best Prediction with alternative parametric assumptions: The second option when the Gaussian assumptions are not met is to use alternative parametric specifications that are more realistic. The difficulty with this approach is that EBP is only possible under specific distributions. One such distribution that may be appropriate in applications involving income is the Generalised Beta distribution of the second kind (GB2). The use of this distribution is studied by GRAF et al. (2015). A complication with using alternative distributions is that new tools estimation and inference must be developed and training for the users is needed. Finally, the misspecification of the model assumptions remains a real possibility also with this approach.

Use of robust methodologies: The third option is to use methodologies that minimize the use of parametric assumptions. One such methodology that aims at estimating the quantiles of the empirical quantile process has been proposed (WEIDENHAMMER et al., 2014). This is achieved by using a nested error regression model for the quantiles of the underlying empirical distribution of the data. Estimation of the quantiles of the empirical quantile process is facilitated by the use of the Asymmetric Laplace Distribution for the unit-level error term. In addition, estimation of the random effects can be made entirely non-parametric by using a discrete mixture (MARINO et al., 2016). Although methodologies of this type reduce the reliance on parametric assumptions, these methods also require the development of new estimation and inference tools and investment in additional training for the users.

10.3.2 Challenges due to data access requirements

In addition to the use of parametric assumptions, unit-level methodologies require access to Census and/or administrative microdata. How realistic is this in real applications? Reports from NSIs experimenting with unit-level methodologies indicate that access to Census microdata proves to be problematic. To start with there are disclosure control

risks while the data management problems should not be underestimated. One approach to simplifying access to the Census data is by considering models that include only categorical covariates. Combinations of categorical covariates can be expressed in tabular form. However, if the combination of covariates is very detailed, disclosure risks will remain. A second problem that NSIs report is the difficulty with updating the small estimates in the intracensal period. This is a problem when Census covariates are used in small area estimation which means that these covariates are updated only every ten years. One possible solution to this problem is to replace Census covariates with more frequently updated data from administrative data sources. Access to such data sources are, however, not straightforward. In addition, the quality of administrative data is another concern.

One approach to reducing the data required for estimation is to consider the use of area-level models. Area-level models have been used in small area applications for estimating averages and proportions. However, as we explained earlier in this report the interest of NSIs extends well beyond averages. FABRIZI and TRIVISANO (2016) considered the use of area-level models for estimating Gini coefficients for small areas. There are at least two key challenges associated with the use of area-level models for estimating non-linear indicators. The first is the requirement for using unbiased direct estimators and the second is the estimation of the variance of these direct estimators. More work is needed on both topics and the input from researchers working on design-based theory will be invaluable.

Regarding the updating of estimates during the intracensal period, one approach will be to replace Census covariates with covariates from frequently updated data sources e.g. administrative and survey data. Doing so requires the development of methodologies that will account for the potential sources of error in such data. For example, covariates from survey data cannot be treated as fixed. Instead, methodology must recognize the fact that the covariates themselves are survey estimates, which will increase the uncertainty of small area estimates. Hence, attempting to solve one methodological problem, naming updating the small area estimates, can potentially create more methodological problems. It is not clear what is the best approach to handling these challenging issues and research in these areas is urgently needed.

10.3.3 Challenges due to data harmonization

For some time now National Statistical Institutes in Europe have been reviewing approaches to streamlining survey design and data collection processes across multiple sur-

veys that on many instances collect information on similar topics. Such a streamlining process is likely to create breaks in the series of survey estimates known as survey discontinuities. To give an example, the Welsh Government (WG) in the UK has reviewed the way in which social surveys are conducted in Wales. For a range of reasons, including value for money grounds, WG has instituted a new National Survey (NSn) from 2016. The NSn collects information previously collected in five other surveys, the 2012-15 National Survey (NSo), Welsh Health Survey (WHS), Active Adults Survey (AAS), Arts in Wales Survey (AiWS) and the Welsh Outdoor Recreation Survey (WORS). The NSn has a longer questionnaire which allows many of the questions from the original surveys to be included. The process of agreeing the NSn has involved consultations with the customers for the existing surveys and negotiations to ensure that the new structure is best able to meet their needs, and that they are happy to support it. As part of these, it is important to demonstrate to the users that the design and methodology for the new survey is appropriate and good quality, and to produce estimates of the change in the series (discontinuity) caused by the change from one design to another. In addition, there is need for estimating survey discontinuities at disaggregated geographical areas (domains).

Current methodology for domain estimation of survey discontinuities employs either direct or model-based estimation. Direct estimation is design unbiased but may suffer from low precision due to the usually small sample size of the pilot survey used for estimating discontinuities. In contrast model-based estimation currently implemented via the use of area-level models can improve the precision of the estimates of survey discontinuities. However, as it is well known model-based estimates can suffer from shrinkage which it is likely to impact upon the estimated discontinuity. Therefore, a number of challenges exist in this area of research. To start with, it is important to study alternative estimators of discontinuities. It is also important to study the impact of shrinkage on the estimated discontinuities. In applications, the covariates used in models are coming from surveys. Therefore there is need to account for measurement error (sampling error) in the covariates. An alternative approach to estimating discontinuities is via the use of multivariate area-level models. It is also of equal importance to define measures of precision and develop methods for adjusting and benchmarking the series of domain survey estimates. Finally, transferring the methodologies across NSIs in Europe will be of significant added value.

10.4 Challenges with measuring the uncertainty and evaluating small area estimates

10.4.1 Measuring uncertainty

The previous Sections focused on the methodological challenges we face with current methods and outlined possible solutions. In this Section we focus on another challenging theme, namely measuring the uncertainty and evaluating small area estimates. The small area estimates are a set of numbers of identical definition and simultaneous interest. In what sense can one set of estimates considered to be better than another? Is it enough that the underlying model is the preferred one according to some model selection criterion? Is it enough that the average MSE of one set is lower than the other? Given two sets of ‘optimal’ estimates, derived under two different models, is it meaningful to compare the respective MSEs directly? Should one rely on the design- or model-based MSE? Are ensemble properties of the small area estimates such as the range or ranks of the estimates relevant? These are all examples of questions to which, in our opinion, there are hardly any definite answers. A detailed discussion on evaluation is beyond the scope of this report. Our approach below is to describe some aspects of evaluation, which we believe are *necessary* to be taken into consideration in any application.

Let θ_k be the target parameter of area k , for $k = 1, \dots, m$. Let $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m\}$ be the collection of them. Let $\hat{\theta}_k$ be the estimator of θ_k and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ the collection of them. Here we assume that one is interested in *all* elements of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ at the same time. In other words, one can not fix only on one particular θ_k , or a few of them, and disregard how estimators perform in the rest of the areas.

The first question for uncertainty assessment is, “what is the target of estimation?”. Generally speaking, in small area estimation one may distinguish between the *area-specific* and *ensemble* targets of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. An ensemble characteristic of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is defined by using all θ_k ’s. For example, let $\bar{\theta}_w = \sum_{k=1}^m N_k \theta_k / N$ be the population mean, where N_k is the population size in area k and $N = \sum_{k=1}^m N_k$, or let $G = \sum_{k=1}^m (\theta_k - \bar{\theta})^2 / (m - 1)$ be the dispersion (i.e. population variance) of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, where $\bar{\theta} = \sum_{k=1}^m \theta_k / m$. Other examples include the range, the order statistics and the ranks of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Although the various ensemble target parameters may be very important for purposes such as benchmarking, subgroup analysis, fund allocation, evaluation and monitoring (see e.g. GHOSH, 1992, SHEN and LOUIS, 1998), area-specific

prediction seems to have been the focus in the majority of applications. The most common uncertainty measure for area-specific prediction is MSE. Below we explain the three *types* of MSE in use.

Let y_k denote generically all the observed data in area k , for $k = 1, \dots, m$. Let $\mathbf{y} = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$ be the collection of them. Provided a population model of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the (*unconditional*) MSE is given by $E[(\hat{\theta}_k - \theta_k)^2]$, where the expectation is over both $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \mathbf{y} . PRASAD and RAO (1990b) develop second-order accurate analytic MSE estimator under the linear mixed model, which corrects the bias of the direct plug-in MSE estimator. Jackknife methods have been developed for the same purpose under a wider range of models (JIANG et al., 2002). Bootstrap (most commonly parametric) is more generally applicable, especially if either the target parameter or the performance measure is non-differentiable (HALL and MAITI, 2006, PFEFFERMANN and CORREA, 2012). Using bootstrap is particularly relevant for uncertainty estimation of indicators such as the Gini coefficient and the HCR. For example, for the EBP method simple unconditional MSE estimation uses a plug-in parametric bootstrap as follows. Notice that the procedure here is not second-order accurate, unlike the more sophisticated bootstrap methods cited above. Generate B bootstrap populations using the fitted (plug-in) super-population model $\mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{X}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{e}^*$, where the u_k 's are independent and identically distributed variables from $N(0, \hat{\sigma}_u^2)$. Compute the population value of the target parameter from each bootstrap population, θ_k^* . From each bootstrap population select a bootstrap sample and compute bootstrap estimates of the target parameter, $\hat{\theta}_k^*$, by using the same method as the one used with the original sample. Finally, compute the average of the B squared bootstrap errors – defined as the difference between $\hat{\theta}_k^*$ and θ_k^* – as an estimate of the unconditional MSE.

BOOTH and HOBERT (1998) argue for the use of *conditional MSE of prediction (CMSEP)* in the case of non-normal mixed models including generalised linear mixed models. The CMSEP is given by $E[(\hat{\theta}_k - \theta_k)^2 | y_k]$, where the corresponding within-area y_k is held fixed. When all the model parameters are known, the best predictor is $\hat{\theta}_k = E(\theta_k | y_k)$, and the only natural measure of its uncertainty is the CMSEP that reduces to $V(\theta_k | y_k)$. LOHR and RAO (2009) propose a second-order accurate jackknife estimator of the conditional MSE. For a practical example, ZHANG (2009) applies the CMSEP to estimates of small area compositions subjected to informative missing data.

The third type of MSE we describe is the *finite-population (FP) MSE* given by $E[(\hat{\theta}_k - \theta_k)^2 | \boldsymbol{\theta}]$, where only the observed data \mathbf{y} are allowed to vary. The FP-MSE is often evaluated

with respect to the sampling design (RIVEST and BELMONTE, 2000). CHAMBERS et al. (2011) develop an FP-MSE estimator where the sampling distribution of \mathbf{y} is specified with respect to different models in common use. The fact that $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is held fixed means the FP-MSE is an uncertainty measure for the actual population from which the sample is selected instead of over all possible populations from which the sample could have been selected. This is a familiar interpretation that appeals to many users. However, because the FP-MSE is a small-area parameter itself, *unbiased* estimation is unstable whether it is with respect to the sampling design or model. Hence, one needs to treat the estimation of FP-MSE as a small area estimation problem in its own right.

So the challenging question is which MSE? For example, take model (1), where $\theta_k = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k\boldsymbol{\beta} + u_k$, should one consider u_k to be fixed and calculate the FP-MSE, or random and calculate the unconditional MSE or CMSEP? Tukey’s remark on this matter is that one should “focus on the questions, not models” (Discussion of Nelder, 1977, JRSSA). There are times when the target parameter θ_k is of a hypothetical construct, such as disease prevalence, mortality rates used for life expectancy calculation, etc. It is then quite appropriate to consider the u_k ’s to be random *in nature*, and to use the unconditional MSE or the CMSEP as the uncertainty measure. But there are also many other situations, such as when θ_k is the area unemployment rate, where it is clearly defined as a descriptive statistic of the given finite population. One can still treat u_k as a random effect in order to achieve a sensible bias-variance trade-off, e.g. using model (2). Still, should one report the model-based MSE or the FP-MSE as the uncertainty measure, for an estimator that is derived under a random effects model? We believe that while it is inferentially consistent to report the model-based MSE here, one is entitled to question its relevance, when θ_k is a descriptive statistic and the assumption $E(u_k) = 0$ may be doubtful. In such a case, the FP-MSE is attractive for many survey practitioners. However, as explained above, the estimation of the FP-MSE needs to be treated as a small area problem in its own right.

Interval estimation may be considered besides MSE estimation. Let $C_k = (\hat{\theta}_{kL}, \hat{\theta}_{kU})$ be an interval estimator of θ_k , where $\hat{\theta}_{kL} < \hat{\theta}_{kU}$. The simplest procedure is to set the bounds e.g. as $\hat{\theta}_k \pm 1.96 \cdot \hat{\text{MSE}}(\hat{\theta}_k)^{1/2}$, aimed at the 95% nominal confidence level. See PFEFFERMANN (2013b, Section 6.2) for a review of interval estimation methods. Let $\delta_k = 1$ if $\theta_k \in C_k$ and 0 otherwise. Analogously to the unconditional MSE, the unconditional *coverage* of C_k is given by $\alpha_k = E(\delta_k) = P(\theta_k \in C_k)$, where both $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \mathbf{y} are allowed to vary. Similarly, one can speak about conditional coverage of C_k given by $E(\delta_k|y_k)$, and FP-coverage given

by $E(\delta_k|\boldsymbol{\theta})$. Notice that any model-based C_k that treats θ_k as random can have rather erratic area-specific FP-coverage compared to the nominal level of confidence. ZHANG (2007) defines $\alpha = \sum_{k=1}^m E(\delta_k|\boldsymbol{\theta})/m$ to be the FP *simultaneous coverage* of the C_k 's, all aimed at the same nominal confidence level. For the population from which the sample is selected, this gives the proportion of area parameters that are expected to be covered by their interval estimates without specifying which areas these are. It is shown that, as $m \rightarrow \infty$, α converges to the nominal level of the C_k 's, provided the underlying population model of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is correct.

10.4.2 Method evaluation

In the previous Section we described different uncertainty measures. In addition to measuring the uncertainty associated with $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ under the assumed model, an analyst is more generally interested in *method evaluation*. An analyst may be interested in comparing different point estimators, assessing how a MSE estimator performs in reality when approximations are used in its derivation, or assessing how a small area estimator behaves under departures from the underlying model assumptions. Method evaluation is generally a different matter to uncertainty assessment. For instance, the FP-MSE of a design-based direct estimator is calculated over all possible y_k conditional on θ_k , whereas the CMSEP of a model-based $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is calculated over all possible θ_k conditional on y_k . It is thus inappropriate to conclude that the latter is more accurate than the former on the basis that the CMSEP is smaller than the FP-MSE. Broadly speaking, method evaluation can be design-based or model-based, as we describe below. It is also possible to combine both sources of uncertainty, where the distribution of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ follows from a population model and the distribution of \mathbf{y} from the sampling design. The evaluation can be performed analytically provided the required closed-form expressions can be derived. More often, though, both design-based and model-based simulation studies are used for method evaluation.

Conducting a design-based simulation study is very common in practice. Indeed, it is hard to imagine that an NSI will produce any small area statistics on a regular basis without validating the FP performance of the adopted method under realistic conditions. Typically, a census or similar population dataset is fixed as the population from which samples are repeatedly taken. When such population data are unavailable, there exist various proposals in the literature how one can generate a pseudo-population for the *in-sample* areas from the sample data at hand (e.g. Sverchkov and Pfeffermann, 2004).

However, a model will be necessary in order to generate a pseudo-population for the *out-of-sample* areas. For each simulated sample, a given estimation method is applied to obtain a replicate set of small area estimates. Within a design-based simulation study different estimation methods or models can be directly compared to each other in terms of their FP performances. We consider this to be a suitable approach for method evaluation, which establishes how a method is expected to perform over repeated sampling from a finite population, *regardless* of whether the underlying model is correct or not.

Unlike in a design-based simulation study, where the different estimation methods are subjected to the same sampling variation and the population may be based on real data, model-based method evaluation generally requires the use of a model for generating the population. This is common when researchers develop new methods and they are interested in evaluating the properties of estimators (point and MSE) both when the model assumptions hold and under specific assumptions about model misspecification (sensitivity analysis). The design of model-based studies requires careful thinking about the choice of the *evaluation model* used for generating the population. A general question is whether it is meaningful to compare directly the MSE of an estimator $\hat{\theta}_{kA}$ of θ_k derived under model M_A to that of another estimator $\hat{\theta}_{kB}$ of θ_k under model M_B , which may involve different random effects or correlation structure. Notice that it is always possible to evaluate the MSE of $\hat{\theta}_{kA}$ under model M_B even though the estimator is motivated and computed under model M_A and *vice versa*. Since the MSE of $\hat{\theta}_{kA}$ will differ according to whether the evaluation model is M_A or M_B , there is a need to level the ground in order to avoid misleading comparisons. A relevant example is when using parametric bootstrap under the setting of the EBP method for MSE estimation of both the EBP and the world bank estimators. One may e.g. carry out the simulation of both $\hat{\theta}_{kA}$ and $\hat{\theta}_{kB}$ under the model M_B if M_A is nested in M_B . When M_A and M_B are not nested in each other but are from the same class of models, one may use as the evaluation model M_C which encompasses both. But it may not be obvious how to find an encompassing model when M_A and M_B belong to different classes of models.

It should be mentioned that, in addition to the methods described above, there are several informal evaluation approaches that are of relevance to practitioners, such as compatibility with external data, quantitative or qualitative, evaluation by subject-matter experts, bias and goodness of fit diagnostics from the point of view of practitioners, as described in BROWN et al. (2001). Finally, a set of small area estimates is expected to be numerically

consistent and more efficient than unbiased direct estimates. One can further compare the aggregated area estimates to the corresponding direct aggregate estimates for the same purpose. If aggregated model-based (indirect) estimates are not consistent with aggregate direct estimates, an analyst can use benchmarking techniques to achieve consistency. Benchmarked small area estimates offer an attractive property for NSIs (see PFEFFERMANN, 2013b, for a discussion on benchmarking methods). A more challenging issue is benchmarking of aggregated ensemble properties, such as the population quantiles, which can be derived from the collection of within-area quantiles.

10.5 Challenges with the use of news forms of data

The discussion in previous sections assumed the availability of Census and survey data. However, the use of the so-called big-data for official statistics purposes becomes more pressing. The official statistics community is actively researching approaches to incorporating big data for example, mobile data and remote sensing data in the production of official statistics. For example, there are some recent examples of the use of new sources of data in small area estimation. SCHMID et al. (2016) examined the use of mobile phone data as auxiliary information in area-level models and WAGNER et al. (2016) studied the use of remote sensing data with non-parametric models. Both papers provide a framework for incorporating new forms of data in the production of official statistics. GROSS et al. (2017) study the estimation of population densities when using register geo-referenced data that are protected for disclosure control purposes via the addition of measurement error in the geo-coordinates.

Despite a number of research activities, many important questions remain unanswered. First and foremost the publication of an official statistic must be accompanied by an estimate of its precision. When using survey data, there is a well defined theoretical framework-design-based or model-based- that can be used to do so. Such a framework becomes less clear when using the so-called big data sources. This problem is inextricably linked to the lack of understanding about the process that generates the big data. Unless this process is well defined, defining a framework for measuring uncertainty is challenging. There are additional challenges with the use of new forms of data. Standardization of measurement is not easily controlled and this is likely to impact on data quality. Linking or simply combining data from different sources creates additional challenges with data quality and data comparability. Furthermore, it is not immediately clear why or how big

data for example, mobile phone data can be used as predictors in models. Using big data blindly runs the risk of over-interpreting spurious correlations. Incorporating the various sources of measurement error into a framework of measuring uncertainty remains an open and very challenging problem.

10.6 Conclusions

This chapter outlined some of the major challenges in the production of official statistics. Our primary aim is to propose solutions that will maximize the uptake of academic research by NSIs. This in return will strengthen the collaboration between academic research and practice. To start with, we focused on describing the challenges we face with currently used model-based methodologies and outlined potential solutions. Although the use of unit-level models offers considerable flexibility, the focus of future research should be on maximizing the use of area-level models for producing estimates of complex, non-linear indicators that are of interest to NSIs. This will reduce the dependence on using Census micro-data and also offer possibly better approaches for dynamically updating small area estimates. The chapter also focused on challenges for achieving better harmonization of data, measuring the precision and evaluating the quality small area estimates and using new forms of data in the production of official statistics. Many of these challenges remain unresolved. We firmly believe that intensifying the cooperation between researchers and NSIs across Europe working on these problems will have a considerable positive impact on the quality of the official statistics produced.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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